

Origins of Enhanced Prismatic Slip in Mg Alloys: Atomic Scale Investigation

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Abstract

The limited ductility of hexagonal close-packed (HCP) magnesium (Mg) is primarily attributed to the low activity of non-basal slip systems. Unlike basal slip systems, non-basal systems like pyramidal and prismatic slips exhibit significantly higher critical resolved shear strength (CRSS) values, often differing by several orders of magnitude. This substantial disparity is largely due to dislocations on pyramidal and prismatic planes that are prone to transition onto the basal plane, thereby hindering their glide on non-basal planes. While the activation of the pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ is responsible for general ductility of Mg alloys by providing $\langle c \rangle$ slip direction, enhancing the activation of $\langle a \rangle$ prismatic slip can improve ductility of Mg alloys in particular under in-plane strain conditions such as rolled sheets by introducing three additional $\langle a \rangle$ slip systems beyond those of basal slip.

Experimental investigations on single crystalline samples have demonstrated that even dilute additions of alloying elements such as zinc (Zn), aluminum (Al), and lithium (Li) can significantly soften prismatic slip at low temperatures[1, 2]; for instance, a 40% reduction in CRSS was observed with 0.45 atomic percent Zn. However, this softening effect diminishes at room temperature, where the CRSS of Mg-0.45 at% Zn equals that of pure Mg, and at temperatures above room temperature, prismatic slip may even strengthen.

Despite these phenomena being identified over five decades ago, the underlying mechanisms influencing solute effects on prismatic slip remain elusive. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) has shed light on the varied behaviors of dislocation glide in pure Mg at different temperatures, including the jerky glide of screw prism dislocations at low temperatures and basal-prism-basal cross-slip at temperatures greater than room temperature[3–5]. Yet, microscopy investigations specifically targeting the prismatic slip in single crystalline Mg alloys are scarce, with a few exceptions such as one study on the Mg-Li system[6]. Although theoretical and simulation efforts[7–11] have attempted to model and predict solute effects on CRSS through different mechanisms such as the kink-pair nucleation and migration, decrease in relative energies of basal and prismatic cores, and roughening of partials by solute pinning, none have conclusively explained the profound impact of solutes like Zn on prismatic slip.

In the present thesis the role of solutes on prismatic slip of Mg alloys is investigated using computational methods in atomic scale, namely density functional theory (DFT) and molecular statics (MS). To this aim we separately investigate the effect of solutes on edge and screw prism dislocations at different temperatures.

First, we explore the strengthening effect of solutes, focusing only on Zn, at high temperatures. Experimental studies on pure Mg have established that low-temperature behavior is dominated by screw dislocation glide. However, in this research, we investigate the hypothesis that at higher temperatures, edge dislocations could surpass screw dislocations in strength. We aim to determine if the observed strengthening at elevated temperatures is actually attributable to edge strengthening rather than screw strengthening. Therefore, first we study the role of solute strengthening of prismatic edge dislocations as a possible explanation for the higher-T strengthening. Mg-Zn is studied using first-principles inputs in a parameter-free solute strengthening theory. First-principles DFT is necessary to accurately assess the strong solute chemical interaction energies in the core of the compact edge dislocation. Such calculations are subtle due to motion of the dislocation in the presence of the solute, and methods to obtain reliable results with acceptable computational cost are discussed. While interaction energies of Zn in the prism edge core can be quite large (± 0.34 eV), the edge solute strengthening of prismatic slip in dilute Mg-Zn remains well below experiments at high temperatures. By observing the large difference (0.68 eV) in Zn/dislocation interaction energies across the core of the edge dislocation we went on also on investigating strengthening by dynamic strain aging based on cross-core diffusion as an explanation for the higher-T strengthening. First-principles calculations provide the required information on vacancy-mediated solute migration barriers for Zn solutes around the dislocation core. Results for Mg-0.0045Zn show that cross-core diffusion notably increases the stress for prismatic edge dislocation glide but that the strengthening remains roughly 30% of the experimental strength. After concluding that edge strengthening cannot explain the experimental results, and recognizing that the strength is predominantly controlled by screw dislocation glide across all temperature regimes, we shifted focus to the softening phenomena occurring at low temperatures. Given that screw dislocation glide necessitates kink nucleation, we developed a new DFT-accurate Neural Network Potential (NNP) for Mg-Zn. This included incorporating a comprehensive set of DFT calculations on dislocations in both pure Mg and Mg-Zn alloys into the training database.

Using the newly trained NNP, we employed the nudged elastic band (NEB) method to explore the solute effects on the energy barrier of the kink-pair mechanism. Results indicated that while solutes can reduce the energy barrier for kink-pair nucleation at specific sites, they also pin kink migration, thereby effectively not decreasing overall energy barrier for dislocation glide. We also examined the recently suggested single-kink mechanism[12], which requires half the energy barrier of the kink-pair mechanism by assuming that basal-prism-basal cross-slip begins at the corners of a dislocation loop in pure Mg. Extending this theory to include solute effects, we assessed the implications of solute addition for the single-kink mechanism. Our findings reveal that the presence of solutes can result in strengthening, softening, or have no impact on the energy barrier, depending on the solute's position and interaction energies. Therefore, the effect of solutes on the single-kink mechanism is unlikely to account for the significant low-temperature softening observed. Our studies further indicate that, for the site with the strongest binding energy of Zn to the prism screw, the energy barrier remains consistent with that of pure Mg, which explains why the strength is comparable to pure Mg in

experiments at high temperatures. This is because this site is shared between the initial and final basal cores, resulting in the same solute-basal dislocation interaction energy.

Subsequently, inspired by single-kink mechanism we investigated the effect of Zn on the expansion of dislocation loops on the prismatic plane. Results indicated that while Zn at the most favorable site for prism core does not inhibit the glide of the edge component of the loop, it significantly affects the transition region from edge to screw component at the corners of the loop where the constriction of dissociated basal dislocation occurs. Zn pins the constriction point, while allowing the edge component to continue its glide on prismatic plane and elongate this constricted segment. Our simulations show that when this constricted length becomes sufficiently large, basal-prism cross-slip occurs at a stress that can be approximately three times lower than that for pure strength, which demonstrates the significant effect that even a very dilute amount of solutes can have on prismatic slip strength. This pinning effect diminishes with increasing temperature, aligning with experimental observations.

Key words: Mg alloys; plasticity; Prismatic slip; Density functional theory; Molecular statics; Mg-Zn; Cross-core diffusion; solute strengthening; cross-slip

Résumé

La ductilité limitée du magnésium (Mg) à structure hexagonale compacte (HCP) est principalement attribuée à la faible activité des systèmes de glissement non-basal. Contrairement aux systèmes basaux, les systèmes non-basaux, tels que les glissements prismatiques et pyramidaux, présentent des valeurs de contrainte critique de cisaillement résolu (CRSS) beaucoup plus élevées, différant souvent de plusieurs ordres de grandeur. Cette disparité importante est en grande partie due au fait que les dislocations sur les plans prismatiques et pyramidaux ont tendance à se transférer sur le plan basal, entravant ainsi leur glissement sur les plans non-basaux. Alors que l'activation du glissement pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ est responsable de la ductilité générale des alliages de Mg en fournissant une direction de glissement $\langle c \rangle$, l'amélioration de l'activation du glissement prismatique $\langle a \rangle$ peut améliorer la ductilité des alliages de Mg, notamment sous des conditions de déformation dans le plan, comme pour les tôles laminées, en introduisant trois systèmes de glissement supplémentaires $\langle a \rangle$ au-delà de ceux du glissement basal.

Des investigations expérimentales sur des échantillons monocristallins ont démontré que même des ajouts dilués d'éléments d'alliage tels que le zinc (Zn), l'aluminium (Al) et le lithium (Li) peuvent considérablement adoucir le glissement prismatique à basse température[1, 2]; par exemple, une réduction de 40 % de la CRSS a été observée avec 0,45 % atomique de Zn. Cependant, cet effet d'adoucissement diminue à température ambiante, où la CRSS du Mg-0,45 at.% Zn est équivalente à celle du Mg pur, et à des températures supérieures à la température ambiante, le glissement prismatique peut même se renforcer.

Malgré l'identification de ces phénomènes il y a plus de cinquante ans, les mécanismes sous-jacents influençant les effets des solutés sur le glissement prismatique demeurent insaisissables. La microscopie électronique en transmission (TEM) a permis de mieux comprendre les comportements variés du glissement des dislocations dans le Mg pur à différentes températures, y compris le glissement saccadé des dislocations prismatiques vis au pas à basse température et le glissement croisé basal-prismatique-basal à des températures supérieures à la température ambiante[3-5]. Cependant, les études microscopiques ciblant spécifiquement le glissement prismatique dans les alliages de Mg monocristallins restent rares, à quelques exceptions près, comme une étude sur le système Mg-Li[6]. Bien que des efforts théoriques et de simulation[7-11] aient tenté de modéliser et prédire les effets des solutés sur la CRSS à travers différents mécanismes tels que la nucléation et la migration de paires de coudes, la diminution des énergies relatives des cœurs basaux et prismatiques, et le piégeage des solutés par rugosité des partiels, aucun n'a expliqué de manière concluante l'impact profond

de solutés comme le Zn sur le glissement prismatique.

Dans la présente thèse, le rôle des solutés sur le glissement prismatique des alliages de Mg est étudié à l'aide de méthodes computationnelles à l'échelle atomique, notamment la théorie de la fonctionnelle de la densité (DFT) et la statique moléculaire (MS). À cette fin, nous examinons séparément l'effet des solutés sur les dislocations prismatiques à composante vis et coin à différentes températures.

Premièrement, nous explorons l'effet de renforcement des solutés, en nous concentrant uniquement sur le Zn, à haute température. Les études expérimentales sur le Mg pur ont établi que le comportement à basse température est dominé par le glissement des dislocations vis. Cependant, dans cette recherche, nous examinons l'hypothèse qu'à des températures plus élevées, les dislocations coin pourraient surpasser les dislocations vis en résistance. Nous visons à déterminer si le renforcement observé à des températures élevées est effectivement attribuable au renforcement des coins plutôt qu'à celui des vis. Ainsi, nous étudions d'abord le rôle du renforcement par soluté des dislocations coin prismatiques comme une explication possible du renforcement à haute température. Le système Mg-Zn est étudié à l'aide d'une théorie de renforcement par soluté sans paramètre, alimentée par des calculs DFT de premier principe. Ces calculs permettent d'évaluer avec précision les fortes énergies d'interaction chimique du soluté dans le cœur compact de la dislocation coin. Bien que les énergies d'interaction du Zn dans le cœur de la dislocation coin prismatique puissent être assez élevées ($\pm 0,34$ eV), le renforcement par soluté du glissement prismatique dans le Mg-Zn dilué reste bien inférieur aux résultats expérimentaux à haute température.

Après avoir conclu que le renforcement par dislocation coin ne peut pas expliquer les résultats expérimentaux, et en reconnaissant que la résistance est principalement contrôlée par le glissement des dislocations vis à toutes les températures, nous avons recentré nos recherches sur les phénomènes d'adoucissement à basse température. En utilisant un nouveau potentiel neuronal (NNP) pour Mg-Zn basé sur des calculs DFT précis, nous avons exploré les effets des solutés sur la barrière énergétique du mécanisme des paires de coudes via la méthode NEB. Les résultats montrent que les solutés peuvent réduire la barrière d'énergie pour la nucléation de coudes, mais ils entravent également leur migration, n'entraînant ainsi pas une diminution globale de la barrière énergétique pour le glissement des dislocations.

Inspirés par le mécanisme de simple coude, nous avons ensuite étudié l'effet du Zn sur l'expansion des boucles de dislocation sur le plan prismatique. Les résultats montrent que le Zn affecte de manière significative les régions de transition entre les composantes vis et coin aux coins de la boucle. Nos simulations montrent que lorsque cette longueur contrainte devient suffisamment grande, le glissement croisé basal-prismatique se produit à une contrainte environ trois fois inférieure à celle du Mg pur, démontrant ainsi l'impact significatif que même une très faible quantité de solutés peut avoir sur la résistance au glissement prismatique.

Mots-clés : Alliages de Mg; plasticité; glissement prismatique; théorie de la fonctionnelle de la densité; statique moléculaire; Mg-Zn; diffusion inter-cœur; renforcement par soluté; glissement croisé.

Contents

Acknowledgements	i
Abstract (English/Français/Deutsch)	iii
List of figures	xi
List of tables	xv
1 Introduction and background	1
1.1 Slip systems of HCP Mg	3
1.2 Thermally activated dislocation glide	3
1.3 Prismatic slip in Mg	4
1.3.1 Pure Mg	5
1.3.2 Solute effects	8
1.4 Scope and structure of the Thesis	10
2 Computational Methods	13
2.1 Density Functional Theory (DFT)	14
2.1.1 Smearing methods	16
2.1.2 Atomic Forces	17
2.2 Molecular Statics (MS)	18
2.3 Nudged Elastic Band Method (NEB)	20
2.4 Transition State Theory (TST)	22
2.5 Stroh formalism for dislocation solution	24
3 First-principles modeling of dislocation cores	27
3.1 Prism edge dislocation core in HCP Mg	29
3.2 Edge dislocation cores in BCC structures	32
4 Solute strengthening of edge prism dislocation	43
4.1 Solute strengthening theory for edge dislocations	43
4.2 Yield strength of Mg prism edge dislocations	45
4.2.1 Elasticity estimates of solute/dislocation interaction energies	45
4.2.2 First-principles methodology for computing solute/dislocation interaction energies	46
	ix

4.3	Prediction of yield strength for Mg prism slip	50
4.4	Discussion and Summary	51
5	Strengthening of edge prism motion by dynamic strain aging	55
5.1	Cross-core diffusion in Mg-Zn	56
5.1.1	Mechanism	56
5.1.2	Energetics	57
5.1.3	Kinetics	59
5.2	Results	63
5.3	Discussion	67
6	Solute-induced softening of prism screw	71
6.1	Solute effects on the stability of prism screw	72
6.2	Training of an NNP for Mg-Zn	73
6.3	Kink-pair mechanism	80
6.3.1	Pure Mg	80
6.3.2	Solute effect on kink-pair mechanism	84
6.4	Single-kink mechanism	90
6.4.1	Pure Mg	90
6.4.2	Solute effect on single-kink mechanism	93
6.4.3	Case studies	96
6.5	A new mechanism for solute softening	100
6.5.1	Pure Mg	100
6.5.2	Solute effect	103
6.5.3	Solute effect on loop expansion	105
7	Discussion and conclusion	109
8	Outlook	111
	Bibliography	122
	Curriculum Vitae	123
	Curriculum Vitae	123

List of Figures

1.1	Schematic illustration of a typical crystallographic texture developed in magnesium alloy sheets and illustration of basal $\langle a \rangle$ slip in magnesium and magnesium alloys	2
1.2	The three slip systems of HCP Mg crystal structure with the corresponding CRSS values	3
1.3	Stress required for the glide of the basal, prismatic, and pyramidal dislocations as a function of temperature	5
1.4	Energy profile along the dislocation path and the effect of stress	6
1.5	Kink-pair mechanism	6
1.6	locking unlocking mechanism for prismatic slip	7
1.7	2d and 3d-NEB path for basal-basal transition through prismatic plane in pure Mg	8
1.8	CRSS versus temperature for pure Mg and a number of Mg-Zn alloys	9
2.1	A schematic of a PES with two meta-stable regions	21
2.2	Partitioning of the potential energy surface according to transition state theory	23
3.1	A schematic of a typical simulation cell for implementing the fixed boundary condition for the relaxation of dislocation structure	29
3.2	The variation of the dislocation line energy as a function of the radius of a cylinder surrounding the center of the dislocation.	30
3.3	Surface forces in perfect HCP cell and common neighbor analysis of edge prism dislocation core	32
3.4	Distribution of ionic forces in calculations with super-cells of different shapes and different smearing parameters	35
3.5	Ionic forces due to free surface in super-cells of different dimensions oriented in $\{110\}$ slip system of Mo	37
3.6	Ionic forces due to free surface in super-cells selected for different elements. . .	38
3.7	Geometry of the super-cell (before relaxation) used for the relaxation of dislocation cores with fixed boundary condition	39
3.8	Common neighbor analysis of edge dislocation cores in Nb, Ta, and Mo on $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ slip systems.	40
3.9	Edge component of Nye tensor for edge dislocations on (a) $\{110\}$ and (b) $\{112\}$ slip planes in Nb.	41

3.10	Edge component of Nye tensor for edge dislocation on (a) {110} and (b) {112} slip planes in Ta.	41
3.11	Edge component of Nye tensor for edge dislocation on (a) {110} and (b) {112} slip planes in Mo.	42
4.1	Atomistic structure and atomic pressures p for the prism edge dislocation in pure Mg as obtained from an MEAM interatomic potential	47
4.2	The prismatic edge core structure obtained by first principles calculation and site labels	48
4.3	Position of the edge dislocation before DFT relaxation and after relaxation when a Zn solute has been placed at site 2	48
4.4	position of the extra plane of the dislocation after DFT relaxation for a solute at site 8 with and without the pinning solute at site 6	51
4.5	Interaction energies of Zn with the prism edge dislocation.	52
4.6	Critical resolved shear stress for prism slip as a function of temperature as predicted for the prism edge dislocation and as measured experimentally . . .	52
5.1	The difference in the Zn/dislocation interaction energy Δw_n between the sites n below and above the glide plane	56
5.2	Potential cross-core diffusion paths considered in this study.	59
5.3	Schematic representation of the sequence of atomistic configurations relevant to the cross-core diffusion process involving a vacancy, a solute, and a dislocation and corresponding energies	61
5.4	NEB calculation of cross-core diffusion migration barrier for different paths around the edge core	63
5.5	Solute concentration profiles after cross-core diffusion over the dislocation waiting time versus site n in the core	65
5.6	Energy versus dislocation glide distance (in units of b) due to cross-core diffusion at the waiting time and under zero stress, for different temperatures	66
5.7	Energy versus glide distance, after cross-core diffusion over the waiting time, for different applied stresses	67
5.8	Yield strength versus temperature, as measured and as predicted by solute strengthening plus cross-core diffusion.	68
6.1	DFT relaxation of screw prism core with one Zn solute at two different sites in the core	74
6.2	Super cell and final solute/screw dislocation interaction energies obtained by DFT	75
6.3	Deviation of NNP from DFT reference values (%) for lattice constants, elastic constants, stable and unstable stacking fault energies for basal and prismatic slip, respectively	76
6.4	The energy difference between the linear interpolated configurations starting basal to prism	77
6.5	The MEP for basal-prism-basal cross-slip in 2d calculated by NNP.	77

6.6	The GSFE curve for the prismatic plane	78
6.7	Zn/screw interaction energy maps obtained by NNP and DFT	79
6.8	CNA of the cross-section of the core of a basal dislocation formed at 2d periodic relaxation and the screw component of a dislocation loop. Also shown is Zn/screw basal interaction energy map as calculated for the core in the dislocation loop.	80
6.9	The MEP for the kink-pair mechanism in pure Mg, calculated using the newly developed NNP for the Mg-Zn system.	83
6.10	CNA analysis of the dislocation core structures in basal(b_1)-prism(p)-basal(b_2) double cross-slip process.	85
6.11	MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with a solute (colored in red) placed at site $B1$	86
6.12	MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes $B1$ and $B2$, with $B2$ placed at the basal-basal kink nucleation position.	87
6.13	MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes $B1$ and $B2$, with $B2$ placed at the lower basal-basal kink nucleation position.	88
6.14	MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes $B1$ and $B2$, with $B2$ placed in the middle of the two kinks.	89
6.15	MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes $B1$ and $B3$, with $B3$ placed at the upper basal-basal kink nucleation position.	89
6.16	Schematic of single-kink mechanism and the energy evolution as a function of l during the process.	91
6.17	Schematics of the effect of solute on the energy profile of the single-kink mechanism.	95
6.18	Solute effect on the single-kink mechanism energy profiles and CRSS value as a function of temperature.	97
6.19	A schematic of a PES with two meta-stable regions	99
6.20	The equilibrium loop shape under the applied shear stress of 320 MPa to prevent it from collapse.	101
6.21	The configurations obtained via applying additional stress on the the loop shown in Figure 6.20 and relaxed. a) total stress, 1000 MPa, b)total stress, 1100 MPa.	101
6.22	Configurations during relaxation steps of the loop shown in Figure 6.20 under total applied shear stress of 780 MPa.	102
6.23	Solute effect on the cross-slip of the screw component when the solute is located on the transition region of the loop (red colored).	103
6.24	Solute effect on the cross-slip of the screw component when the solute (red colored) is located away from the transition region of the loop	104

6.25 Interaction of Zn solute (colored with red) with an expanding loop. The stress level is 580 MPa and steps (a)-(d) are the steps during relaxation. 106

6.26 Solute effect on the cross-slip of the screw component when the solute (red colored) is located away from the transition region of the loop 107

List of Tables

3.1	Bulk properties calculated using two different smearing parameters	36
4.1	Zn/edge dislocation interactions energies in eV at three sites in the core as calculated by DFT and NNP for a single solute in a super-cell with thickness c and for a single solute plus a pinning solute at site 6 in a super-cell with thickness $2c$. The effects of the pinning solute are small.	50
6.1	Comparison of lattice parameters in (\AA) and elastic constants in GPa, obtained using VASP and Quantum ESPRESSO (QE).	75
6.2	Comparison of maximum Zn/dislocation interaction energy for different dislocations obtained using NNP and DFT. All values are in eV.	80

1 Introduction and background

The use of lightweight Mg alloys in automotive and aerospace industries could lead to significant reductions in weight, superior energy efficiency and therefore lower emissions. This is particularly crucial in aerospace applications, where reducing overall weight improves fuel efficiency and increases payload capacity, leading to significant cost savings and enhanced performance. Mg is known to be the lightest engineering metal with a density less than 25% of the traditional steels and about 75% of the aluminium alloys. Mg alloys offer a great potential for various applications in automotive and aviation industries with properties such as high specific strength, high castability, machinability, damping capacity, bio-compatibility and also good corrosion resistance [13].

In spite of their many excellent properties, the poor formability and brittleness of Mg alloys at room temperature have severely constrained their possible applications in manufacturing non-castable parts. As a result, most commercial Mg alloys available today are produced using die-casting methods [14]. However, the mechanical properties of these cast products often fall short of meeting the required performance standards, particularly in terms of strength and ductility. The formability issues of Mg alloys stem from their hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystal structure, which has fewer slip systems compared to cubic crystal structures like aluminum and steel. This makes plastic deformation more difficult at room temperature, resulting in limited ductility and a higher tendency for cracking.

To improve the ductility of Mg alloys, several strategies have been developed. One common approach is elevated temperature forming, which allows for the activation of additional slip systems in the HCP structure, improving ductility [15]. This reduces the flow stress and enhances the plasticity of Mg alloys, significantly improving their formability. Forming at high temperatures, while improving the ductility of Mg alloys, presents several disadvantages such as undesirable grain growth, increase in the risk of oxidation, and significantly higher production cost and energy consumption [16]. Another effective strategy has been the addition of new alloying elements. Adding elements such as aluminum, zinc, lithium and rare earth metals can improve the ductility of Mg alloys by either facilitating the activation of non-basal slip systems and/or modifying the microstructure through mechanisms such as grain

Figure 1.1: Schematic illustration of (a) a typical crystallographic texture developed in magnesium alloy sheets and (b) illustration of basal $\langle a \rangle$ slip in magnesium and magnesium alloys [35]

refinement, precipitation, etc [17–24].

The poor sheet formability of Mg alloys are due to the formation of strong basal texture during deformation [25]. Figure 1.1 shows a typical texture of a Mg alloy after undergoing rolling deformation. The majority of the grains are aligned with their basal planes parallel to the rolling direction and perpendicular to the sheet's normal, making deformation along the normal (through-thickness) direction very difficult. Weakening of this basal texture has been reported to increase the formability of Mg alloys. Studies have shown that the addition of rare-earth elements can have a strong effect on basal texture weakening [26–29]. Computational studies [30–33] using first principles and molecular statics/dynamics showed that the origin of high ductility of Mg-RE alloys is due to the enhanced activation of pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ slip activity which results from the reduction in relative energy of pyramidal I and pyramidal II screw dislocations, leading to easy cross-slip and double cross-slip between these planes. The double cross-slip process acts as a Frank-Read source for generating dislocation loops and compensating the detrimental effect of pyramidal-basal transition of edge dislocations.

The activation of prismatic slip can be an effective strategy to improve the sheet formability of Mg alloys by providing 3 additional $\langle a \rangle$ slip systems to those of the basal slip system resulting in weakened basal-texture. It was reported that the addition of dilute amount of Zn, Al, and Li can soften the prismatic slip [1, 2, 34]. However, the underlying mechanisms behind these solute effects on prismatic slip is not well understood. Unveiling these mechanisms can help us in designing new alloys suitable for room temperature in-plane deformation processes such as rolling. Therefore this thesis, by focusing on Mg-Zn system, aims at studying the possible effects of solutes on the activity of prismatic slip.

This chapter is organized as follows: section 1.1 reviews the slip systems in Mg. Section 1.2 discusses the dependence of the dislocation glide strength on temperature. Finally, our current understandings of the prismatic slip in pure Mg and the effect of solutes on the activity of prismatic slip by both experimental and computational studies will be discussed in section 1.3.

Figure 1.2: The three slip systems of HCP Mg crystal structure with the corresponding CRSS values; a) basal, b) prismatic, and c) pyramidal I (yellow) and pyramidal II (blue)

1.1 Slip systems of HCP Mg

The poor formability is connected to the anisotropic flow behavior of Mg alloys, which arises from the disparate slip systems in the hexagonally-close-packed (HCP) crystal structure. The slip systems of HCP are shown in figure 1.2. Mg has two independent $\langle a \rangle$ type slip systems on the basal (0001) plane with a very low CRSS of ~ 0.5 MPa. The Von-Mises criterion for homogeneous plasticity requires at least five independent slip systems, and so non-basal slip systems or twinning must be activated. However, the CRSS of non-basal prismatic $(10\bar{1}0)[11\bar{2}0]$, pyramidal I $(10\bar{2}1)[11\bar{2}3]$ and pyramidal II $(11\bar{2}2)[11\bar{2}3]$ slip systems are approximately 100 times higher than that of basal slip. In order to have sufficient number of active slip systems to accommodate plasticity in HCP structures, the activation of non-basal slip systems is required. This can be achieved by increasing the activation energy of the basal slip and/or decreasing the activation energy of non-basal slip systems. In HCP crystals, slip can occur via $\langle a \rangle$ and $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations. Slip in the $\langle a \rangle$ direction occurs on the basal, pyramidal I, and prismatic planes while slip in the $\langle c+a \rangle$ direction occurs on the pyramidal I and pyramidal II planes. Slip in the $\langle c \rangle$ direction is provided by the $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations since the glide of $\langle c \rangle$ dislocations requires even higher energy and it has not been observed. Plasticity in $\langle c \rangle$ direction can also be accommodated by twinning, however twinning leads to anisotropy and in addition twin boundaries can act as barriers against the movement of dislocations [36–39].

1.2 Thermally activated dislocation glide

It is well known that the mechanical properties of materials are strongly affected by temperature. Therefore, to accurately predict and understand the mechanical properties of crystalline materials, it is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of how dislocations, as carriers of plasticity, behave under varying temperatures. Studies have shown that, in most cases, the strength of materials decreases with increasing temperature. An example of such

behavior is shown in Figure 1.3a for basal and prismatic slips in pure Mg. However, materials can sometimes behave in significantly different ways. Figure 1.3b shows that the strength of pyramidal slip increases with decreasing temperature within a certain temperature range 100-300K .

A gliding dislocation encounters two types of barriers that it must overcome. The first type of barrier arises from the long-range elastic interactions between the gliding dislocation and the forest dislocations, as well as other microstructural elements. Consequently, this barrier is primarily influenced by the sample's history and is only minimally affected by temperature changes through variations in the crystal's elastic constants. The second barrier, which arises from local short-range interactions, is significantly affected by temperature. This type of barrier is typically responsible for the pronounced dependence of material strength on temperature, as in materials shown in Figure 1.3. Dislocations can surmount these local barriers with the assistance of thermal vibrations, leading to a decrease in material strength as the temperature rises. Figure 1.4a shows a typical energy profile of a gliding dislocation from a global minimum position, x_1 , to a local minimum position, x_2 . The activation energy to move the dislocation in the forward and backward directions are E_b^f and E_b^r , respectively.

Figure 1.4b shows the effect of applying increasing external stress on the activation energy of dislocation glide where at large stresses the barrier gradually decreases and finally vanishes where the dislocation can glide spontaneously without any resistance. The overall plastic strain-rate is determined by the net rate at which the dislocation can glide in a certain direction. Orowan's [40] equation for the strain-rate is $\dot{\epsilon} = \rho_m b v$, where ρ_m is the density of mobile dislocations, b is Burgers vector, and v is the average velocity of the dislocation. The velocity is related to the net rate of thermally activated dislocation glide, $R = v_0 e^{-E_b(\tau)/kT}$, where v_0 is attempt frequency. k is Boltzmann's constant and T is temperature. Therefore, Orowan's equation can be written as:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_0 [\exp(-E_b^f(\tau)/kT) - \exp(-E_b^r(\tau)/kT)] \quad (1.1)$$

with $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ as a reference strain-rate.

1.3 Prismatic slip in Mg

This section reviews briefly the important results of both experimental and computational studies that have been done in the past decades on prismatic slip in pure Mg and Mg alloys. In-situ TEM experiments have provided significant insights into prismatic slip and its possible mechanisms. However, atomic-scale details, which are crucial for understanding the effects of solutes and designing new alloys, remain elusive. To address this, several computational studies have been conducted to explore the underlying atomic-scale mechanisms and provide quantitative analyses that can aid in modeling the process.

Figure 1.3: Stress required for the activation of a) basal (B) and prismatic (P) [3], and b) pyramidal slip [41] systems as a function of temperature. The error bars in (a) show the microscopic stresses deduced from the radii of curvature of edge dislocations observed by in-situ TEM

1.3.1 Pure Mg

Couret and Caillard [3, 4] were pioneers in investigating the microscopic mechanisms of prismatic slip employing in-situ microscopy across a range of temperatures. Their observations revealed the predominance of large, straight screw dislocations throughout the temperature range, reporting that prismatic slip is governed by screw dislocation glide. Although the findings at low temperatures are quite convincing about the predominance of screw dislocations, the higher temperature data (above room temperature) are limited. They also noted a considerable difference in the velocities of edge and screw dislocations at low temperatures with edge dislocations moving significantly faster, highlighting the substantial barriers impeding screw dislocation glide. This velocity difference reduces as the temperature increases.

By measuring activation volumes and observing that dislocation velocity is proportional to dislocation length, Couret and Caillard concluded that in the thermally activated regime ($T > 150$ K, see figure 1.3), screw dislocations glide via a kink-pair mechanism or a jog-pair mechanism (depending on the plane considered as the primary glide plane). The steps of this mechanism are illustrated schematically in Figure 1.5. The kink-pair mechanism initiates with the cross-slip of a dissociated basal dislocation to a prismatic screw core (Figure 1.5a-b), creating two basal-prismatic kinks. Upon reaching a critical length l , the prismatic segment cross-slips back onto the adjacent basal plane, forming two basal-basal kinks with a height of h (Figure 1.5c). These basal-basal kinks then separate, allowing the entire dislocation line to glide a distance of h . The value of $h = c/2$ if the dislocation cross-slips back onto the adjacent basal plane, of $h = c$ if the cross-slip occurs at the second next basal plane.

Figure 1.4: a) Schematic of an energy profile along the dislocation path under zero applied stress and b) the effect of stress on the energy barrier

Figure 1.5: Steps during kink-pair (jog-pair) mechanism: a) The initial dissociated basal dislocation cross-slips to prism screw, b) prism cross-slips back onto the next basal plane, c) separation of basal-basal kinks, and glide of the whole dislocation line by $h[3]$.

At low temperatures, where strength remains unaffected by temperature (Figure 1.3), dislocations were observed to glide in a jerky manner. This led to the proposal of an alternate mechanism for low temperature regime, termed locking-unlocking (Figure 1.6). In this mechanism, dislocations that are pinned at stable basal states, intermittently unlock themselves by cross-slipping on the prism plane and glide across several Peierls valleys before becoming locked again by dissociation at another basal plane.

Atomic-scale computational studies have also shed some lights on our better understanding of prismatic slip. A number of NEB calculations based on DFT and MS methods have been done to determine the energy difference between the dissociated screw basal dislocation and prism dislocation. One very accurate recent DFT studies are shown in Figure 1.7a. The energy difference between the infinitely long prism and basal dislocations (in periodic length of $l = 1b$) is about 62 meV/b. Although the energy profile around the prism configuration is quite flat, no meta-stability was reported, leading the authors in conclusion that the screw prism is unstable against dissociation onto the basal plane. However, this is not definite and a meta-stability

Figure 1.6: Locking-unlocking mechanism suggested for low temperature (jerky) prismatic slip in Mg. *a* to *c*) cross-slip of basal to prism core, *d* to *f*) locking of dislocation by dissociation onto another basal plane[5]

may occur in larger cells or under certain configurational forces. Stricker and Curtin [42] used NEB to study the transition from one basal plane to another for a long $l = 10b$ screw dislocation. They employed a DFT-accurate NNP [43] (they called it NNP63) for pure Mg. Minimum energy path, MEP, for basal-prism-basal transition is predicted to be the kink-pair mechanism with an activation enthalpy of about $\Delta H = 1.6eV$ which is nearly two times higher than the value deduced from the experimental results ($\Delta H = 0.8 \pm 0.1eV$). On the other hand the activation length is very close to the experiments ($l_c = 8 - 9b$). Also, they reported that the NEB for the transition of one basal to another with $h = c$ is merely two consecutive identical energy paths corresponding to $h = c/2$. To address the huge difference in activation enthalpies of NEB and experimental results, Liu and Curtin [12] proposed the single-kink mechanism instead of kink-pair mechanism. In single-kink mechanism the cross-slip occurs at the transition region of the dislocation loop where screw component gradually transforms to non-screw component. They verified this by molecular dynamics simulations using NNP63 potential. This new mechanism requires the nucleation of only one basal-basal kink which reduces the activation energy by half, leading to better agreement with experiments.

The low-temperature regime ($T < 150, K$) remains less understood due to limited experimental studies. Experiments indicate that screw dislocations glide on the prismatic plane in a jerky manner under a resolved shear stress of only 100 MPa. In contrast, NEB calculations suggest that overcoming the cross-slip barrier requires approximately 900 MPa, revealing a significant

Figure 1.7: 2d and 3d-NEB path for basal-basal transition through prismatic plane in pure Mg. Energy difference versus replica numbers as determined in a NEB calculation of the cross-slip process for an screw dislocation in a simulation cell with periodic length a) $l = 1b$ obtained via DFT calculations [45] and b) $l = 10b$ obtained via NNP63, between two neighboring basal planes with a distance of $h = c/2$ [42]

discrepancy. Liu et al. [44] proposed glide instability of prismatic screw dislocations on the prismatic plane as the mechanism governing the low temperature regime. Using various NNP potentials, they found that one potential (NNP77) predicts an instability stress of 100 MPa, aligning with experimental observations. They also demonstrated that, in comparison to NNP63, NNP77 shows closer agreement with DFT-calculated energies of the configurations along the MEP.

1.3.2 Solute effects

Alloying elements have notable effects on prismatic slip in magnesium alloys. Solutes like Zn and Al, commonly used in commercial Mg alloys, tend to strengthen basal slip while softening prismatic slip. However, this softening effect on prismatic slip is primarily observed at and below room temperature. For instance as shown in Figure 1.8, the addition of 0.45% Zn reduces the CRSS by almost 50% at $T = 200\text{K}$ and 20% at $T = 250\text{K}$. The extent of softening

Figure 1.8: CRSS versus temperature for pure Mg and a number of Mg-Zn alloys. The samples were single crystalline and oriented in a direction parallel to basal plane so that during the tensile test the activation of basal slip is inhibited and only prismatic slip is activated. The addition of Zn leads to softening at low temperatures and hardening at high temperatures

increases with the increase in concentration of solute. As the temperature increases, the softening effects disappear and the trend shifts towards strengthening, although experiments do not show a consistent trend versus solute concentration. Generally, solutes pin dislocations and strengthen the material by causing the dislocation to adopt a configuration where its position is energetically favorable in terms of solute/dislocation interaction energy. However, this contrasting behavior in the prismatic slip of Mg alloys has attracted significant interest from researchers. Solute softening at low temperatures and solute strengthening at high temperatures were observed in dilute BCC alloys [46–49], which was attributed to a shift from kink nucleation to lateral kink glide which is analogous to basal-prism-basal mechanism in Mg. However there is no experimental or quantitative computational study that verifies this strongly. Tsuru and Chrzan [10], using DFT, studied the effect of the solute elements on the electronic state of the prism and basal dislocation core. They found Yttrium (Y) can actually have a strong interaction with dislocation cores, facilitating the basal-prism cross-slip by forming a compact basal core and stabilizing the prism core. However, their calculations showed that Zn and Al has insignificant effect on the cores structure. Yasi et al [7, 8] proposed a model to estimate the strength of prismatic slip from the solute/interaction energies. This model was developed assuming the kink-pair mechanism occurring at thermally activated region of the CRSS versus temperature curve. By modeling the effect of solutes on kink nucleation and migration they predicted softening at low solute concentration and hardening at athermal regime. However, the solutes they investigated were those that lowered the stacking fault energy of prism screw in order to be able to calculate the solute/dislocation interaction energy. Therefore, they were not able to study the elements such as Zn and Al. Also, they modeled a kink of length $l = 30b$ and height $h = c$, whereas more accurate NNPs show a

very short kink length (about $1 - 2b$) and height of $h = c/2$. Additionally, As they mention in the paper, their model is not intended to low temperature regime where other mechanisms than kink-pair is occurring.

Therefore, it is concluded from previous investigations that the mechanism behind softening and strengthening is not well understood. Gaining any fundamental insights into the relevant processes may enable more-informed design of alloys with tailored prismatic slip.

1.4 Scope and structure of the Thesis

The aim of this thesis is to investigate the fundamental mechanisms behind the softening and strengthening effects of solutes on prismatic slip in magnesium alloys, focusing particularly on the atomistic scale mechanisms of the interaction of solute with dislocations on prismatic plane. By utilizing computational methods, the open question that this thesis tries to answer is that why addition of solutes leads to softening of prismatic slip at low temperatures and strengthening at high temperatures. This is done by investigating the solute interactions with both edge and screw prism dislocations and considering different softening/strengthening mechanisms such as solute strengthening, dynamic strain aging, solute drag, kink nucleation/mobility, and cross-slip.

The thesis is organized into the following chapters:

Chapter 2: Computational Methods This chapter provides an overview of the computational techniques used throughout the thesis, including Density Functional Theory (DFT), molecular statics, and the Nudged Elastic Band (NEB) method. These methods are essential for calculating dislocation core structures, solute-dislocation interactions, and energy barriers related to dislocation glide and cross-slip and cross-core diffusion.

Chapter 3: Structure of Dislocation Cores In this chapter, we explore the structure of edge dislocation cores in hexagonal close-packed (HCP) and body-centered cubic (BCC) metals using First-principles calculations.

Chapter 4: Solute Strengthening of Edge Prismatic Dislocations This chapter investigates the solute strengthening of edge prismatic dislocations in Mg alloys focusing on Mg-Zn system. By examining the interaction between solute and edge dislocation we examine the high temperature strengthening effect of solutes at high temperatures.

Chapter 5: Edge prism strengthening by cross-core diffusion This chapter focuses on the dynamic strain aging (DSA) phenomenon in Mg alloys, which arises from solute diffusion across the dislocation core. The energetics and kinetics of cross-core diffusion mechanism is studied in detail, and the strengthening effect arising from this process at high temperatures is analyzed.

Chapter 6: Solute-Induced Softening of Screw Prismatic Dislocations In this chapter, we

explore the softening effect of solutes at low temperatures. The results reveal how solutes can soften the prismatic slip by facilitating the basal-prism cross-slip.

Chapter 7: Discussion and Conclusion In this chapter, we discuss the findings from the previous chapters and draw conclusions regarding the softening and strengthening mechanisms at low/high temperatures .

Chapter 8: Outlook The final chapter outlines potential directions for future research based on the findings of this thesis.

2 Computational Methods

To simulate the behavior of materials, it is crucial to understand the interactions between the atoms that constitute the material's structure. These atomic interactions determine fundamental properties such as the crystal structure, elasticity, magnetic behavior, and more. Additionally, they govern how a material responds to various external conditions, influencing processes like phase transformations, plasticity, and deformation mechanisms. All of these interactions are encapsulated in the material's total **potential energy surface (PES)**, which is a function of the positions of the atomic nuclei (ions):

$$U_{tot}(\mathbf{R}) = E_{tot}(R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N) \quad (2.1)$$

Here, $E_{tot}(R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N)$, represents the total energy of the system as a function of the ions positions $\mathbf{R} = (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N)$. Understanding and accurately modeling this surface is key to predicting material behavior in real-world applications. The equilibrium state of a material is reached when the forces acting on each ion, arising from various atomic interactions, are zero—meaning there is no driving force for ion motion. These forces, commonly referred to as configurational forces, can be derived from the PES as:

$$\mathbf{F}_i = -\nabla_{R_i} U_{tot}(\mathbf{R}), \quad (2.2)$$

where \mathbf{F}_i is the force on ion i , and $\nabla_{R_i} U_{tot}(\mathbf{R})$ represents the gradient of the total potential energy with respect to the position of ion i . At equilibrium, the configurational forces are zero, ensuring the material is in a stable or metastable state. As an example, the introduction of dislocations into a perfect crystal structure increases the total energy of the system. However, these defective structures relax to a local energy minimum (metastable state), and in the absence of external driving forces, the dislocations remain in their local equilibrium configurations because the forces acting on all nuclei in the crystal are zero. Common algorithms for finding the equilibrium state include gradient-based methods like steepest descent and conjugate gradient, which iteratively adjust atomic positions until the forces on each atom fall below a predefined threshold.

This chapter outlines the computational methods employed in this research. To understand the properties of dislocations involved in prismatic slip, we employ atomistic approaches, including first-principles calculations based on density functional theory (DFT) and molecular statics MS. Each of these methods computes the PES using different approaches. DFT relies on quantum mechanics to explicitly account for electron interactions when calculating the system's potential energy, while molecular statics utilize empirical interatomic potentials, which are typically derived by fitting parameters in complex equations using pre-calculated DFT data.

We use DFT to compute the core structure of dislocations and the interaction energies between solutes and dislocation cores, as detailed in Chapters 3 and 4. Additionally, DFT is used to calculate diffusion migration barriers within the framework of Transition State Theory (TST), employing the nudged elastic band method, as detailed in Chapter 5. Although DFT provides high accuracy, it is computationally expensive and scales poorly with the number of electrons in a system, limiting its application often to systems containing fewer than 1,000 atoms. Therefore, DFT is unsuitable for studying key mechanisms involved in prismatic slip in Mg, such as kink nucleation and cross-slip, as these processes require significantly larger system sizes. To investigate these more complex processes, a neural network potential (NNP) for the Mg-Zn system was retrained based on a recently developed NNP for the Al-Cu-Mg-Zn system, tailored to model dislocation behaviors in Mg-Zn alloys. This NNP is then employed in MS simulations of prismatic slip processes in large 3D structures, including the analysis of the basal-prism cross-slip and dislocation loop evolution as described in Chapter 6.

DFT calculations for obtaining dislocation structures, solute/dislocation interaction energies, and nudged elastic band (NEB) simulations were performed using the VASP code. The Quantum ESPRESSO code was used to prepare the data set for training the NNP. All molecular statics calculations were conducted using LAMMPS.

2.1 Density Functional Theory (DFT)

As all properties of materials including their plasticity are strongly dependent on their electronic structures, DFT can serve as an accurate method for probing the structure and properties of materials. DFT provides a computationally efficient framework for solving the many-electron Schrödinger equation

$$(\hat{T}_{\text{el}} + \hat{V}_{\text{el-el}} + \hat{V}_{\text{ext}}) \Psi(r_1, \dots, r_N) = E \Psi(r_1, \dots, r_N), \quad (2.3)$$

where \hat{T}_{el} is the quantum kinetic energy operator of the electrons, $\hat{V}_{\text{el-el}}$ is the repulsive Coulombic interaction between the electrons, and \hat{V}_{ext} represents the external potential experienced by the electrons, typically due to the positively charged nuclei in the system. $\Psi(r_1, \dots, r_N)$ is the many-body wavefunction, describing the quantum state of all N interacting electrons, and E is the total energy of the system. At the heart of DFT is the Hohenberg-Kohn theorem [50], which establishes that there is a one to one correspondence between the electron

charge density, $\rho(\mathbf{r})$, and the external potential. Due to this uniqueness of charge density we can determine uniquely the external potential, \hat{V}_{ext} , and principally solve the Schrödinger equation and obtain the ground state $\Psi(r_1, \dots, r_N)$ and finally the energy of the system, E . A universal functional of charge density can be defined now, $F[\rho] = \langle \Psi | \hat{T} + \hat{V}_{e-e} | \Psi \rangle$. Then using variational principle we can express the total energy of the system as a functional of charge density:

$$E_\nu[\rho(\mathbf{r})] = \langle \Psi | \hat{T} + \hat{V}_{e-e} + \hat{V}_{\text{ext}} | \Psi \rangle = F[\rho(\mathbf{r})] + \int v_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r})\rho(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \geq E_0 \quad (2.4)$$

Therefore we can obtain the ground state energy of the system by minimizing this energy functional with respect to charge density with the constraint that the total number of electrons must be conserved.

Since the exact form of the functional, $F[\rho]$ is unknown, Kohn and Sham [51–53], use the properties of a system of non-interacting electrons, with wave functions ψ_i , that reproduce the same charge density as the real electrons. They split $F[\rho]$ into three terms, $F[\rho] = T_s[\rho] + E_H[\rho] + E_{\text{xc}}[\rho]$. Here $T_s[\rho]$, the kinetic energy of the non-interacting electrons, and $E_H[\rho]$ the Hartree energy, $E_H[n(\mathbf{r})] = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}_1)\rho(\mathbf{r}_2)}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|} d\mathbf{r}_1 d\mathbf{r}_2$, is known and all the remaining unknown quantum interactions are encapsulated into the third term, $E_{\text{xc}}[\rho]$ known as exchange-correlation term. By minimizing the total functional, $E_\nu[\rho(\mathbf{r})]$, with the constraint, $\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_i^{\text{occ}} |\psi_i(\mathbf{r})|^2$, we obtain the single particle Kohn-Sham equations where the problem of interacting electrons is transformed into a set of single-electron equations that are easier to solve:

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + V_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{H}}(\mathbf{r}) + V_{\text{XC}}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \psi_i(\mathbf{r}) = \epsilon_i \psi_i(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.5)$$

where ϵ_i are the corresponding eigenvalues for each ψ_i .

Since the electron density depends on all Kohn-Sham states, eq (2.5) must be solved self-consistently through guessing an initial density $n(\mathbf{r})$, calculating the potential terms based on this density, and iteratively solving eq (2.5) until, $\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_i^{\text{occ}} |\psi_i(\mathbf{r})|^2$, is satisfied. However, Due to the complexity of exchange-correlation interactions, their exact functional form is unknown, necessitating the use of approximations. In this work, we employ the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) [54], which improves the simpler local density approximation (LDA) by incorporating the gradient of the electron density.

As we are focused on metals which have periodic crystal structures, our solutions must satisfy Bloch's theorem[55]. This means the solutions to eq (2.5) must take the form of periodic functions modulated by plane waves,

$$\psi_k(\mathbf{r}) = e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} u_k(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.6)$$

\mathbf{k} is the wavevector, and $u(\mathbf{r})$ is a periodic function, with periodicity of the crystal lattice,

$$u_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\mathbf{G}} c_{\mathbf{G}} e^{i\mathbf{G}\cdot\mathbf{r}}, \quad (2.7)$$

where \mathbf{G} is any vector between the points of the reciprocal lattice. Therefore $\psi_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$ can be written as:

$$\psi_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\mathbf{G}} c_{\mathbf{G}} e^{i(\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{G})\cdot\mathbf{r}}, \quad (2.8)$$

Using more \mathbf{G} vectors results in more accurate description of $\psi_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$. However, due to computational cost, a finite number of \mathbf{G} vectors are chosen so that the kinetic energy expressed as:

$$E = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} |\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}|^2, \quad (2.9)$$

remains below a cutoff value, E_{cut} .

A crucial computational technique employed in plane-wave DFT calculations is the use of pseudopotentials. The primary role of pseudopotentials is to simplify the description of the interaction between valence electrons and the ionic cores. Instead of explicitly treating all the core electrons, which would require a prohibitively large number of plane waves (due to the oscillatory nature of the core electron wave functions near the nucleus), pseudopotentials replace the core electrons with an effective potential that mimics their effect on the valence electrons. The effective potential generated by pseudopotentials ensures that the physical properties of the valence electrons are accurately captured without the need for a full all-electron treatment. Here we use PAW (Projector Augmented-Wave) [56] pseudopotentials, which provide an efficient approach for accurately representing valence electron behavior in complex materials. PAW pseudopotentials allow for the reconstruction of the all-electron wave function in the core region, thereby achieving a high degree of accuracy while reducing computational cost compared to all-electron calculations. This method effectively balances accuracy and efficiency by modeling core-electron interactions without explicitly calculating them, making it well-suited for density functional theory calculations in materials with periodic crystal structures

2.1.1 Smearing methods

In DFT calculations, unlike insulators and semiconductors where the electronic states at the Fermi level are typically well-separated by a band gap, in metals or systems with partially filled bands, the situation is different. Electrons occupy states continuously up to the Fermi level, and the electron occupation can change sharply between occupied and unoccupied states from 1 to 0. Since the integration in DFT are a sum on all occupied states, where each state is multiplied by its occupation number, in a metal at zero temperature we end up integrating functions that drop abruptly to zero when the corresponding band crosses

the Fermi energy. In DFT the integration is done discretely over k points, this can lead to inaccuracies unless the number of points are very large. Smearing methods[57] smooth the occupation of electronic states, helping to achieve faster and more stable convergence. The extent of smearing is controlled by a smearing parameter or broadening width σ , which effectively introduces a fictitious temperature for the electrons. However, care must be taken in choosing very large values of σ as this could lead to inaccuracies in the results. Here, we used Methfessel-Paxton[58] smearing in our calculations, which provides total free energies that are independent of the smearing temperature, while also delivering Hellmann-Feynman forces that are consistent with the total free energy. This ensures both accurate energy calculations and reliable force evaluations during the structural optimization process. In Chapter 3, we will explore how the use of a smearing parameter can assist in calculating the equilibrium structure of dislocation cores using relatively small supercells, while also mitigating surface forces caused by Friedel oscillations[59].

2.1.2 Atomic Forces

For calculation of the forces on each nucleus, using DFT, one can calculate the configurational force by Equation 2.2. However, calculating the total energy of the electrons and nuclei for every change in the positions of the nuclei is prohibitively expensive. Instead, in DFT calculations, the Hellmann-Feynman theorem[60] is used to determine the equilibrium state of a material. Hellmann-Feynman theorem states that the force on atom I in a system of electrons and nuclei can be computed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_I = - \left\langle \Psi \left| \frac{\partial \hat{H}}{\partial \mathbf{R}_I} \right| \Psi \right\rangle, \quad (2.10)$$

Assuming that Ψ is the exact eigenstate of the Hamiltonian, \hat{H} , this theorem demonstrates that the forces on each nucleus can be calculated as the derivative of the Hamiltonian with respect to the position of nucleus only. In other words they are purely classical, even though they arise from quantum mechanical electrons, and can be written using the following equation:

$$\mathbf{F}_I = -Z_I \sum_J Z_J \frac{(\mathbf{R}_J - \mathbf{R}_I)}{|\mathbf{R}_J - \mathbf{R}_I|^3} + Z_I \int \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r})(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_I)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_I|^3} d\mathbf{r} \quad (2.11)$$

Therefore according to this theorem, for a set of nuclear positions, R_J , the atomic force calculation requires only the calculation of the electron density, $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ as described in section 2.1. The equilibrium structure is obtained by numerical methods such as conjugate gradient method using the gradient of the total energy which is minus the atomic force.

2.2 Molecular Statics (MS)

Since DFT is computationally expensive and typically limited to small systems containing fewer than 1000 atoms, molecular statics simulations, which rely on empirical interatomic potentials to calculate the PES, and are employed to simulate larger and more complex systems, although with lower accuracy than DFT. These empirical potentials allow for more efficient calculations while still capturing the essential atomic interactions. For accurate MS simulations, the choice of the interatomic potential is crucial. In traditional methods, for metals and alloys, empirical potentials such as embedded atom method (EAM)[61] and its modified version (MEAM)[62] are employed, which are mathematical functions designed to approximate the PES. Inspired by DFT, MEAM expresses the total energy of the system as a sum of pairwise interactions and an embedding energy term, which accounts for many-body effects. The total energy E_{MEAM} is given by:

$$E_{\text{tot}}^{\text{MEAM}} = \sum_i F_i(\rho_i) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \neq j} \phi_{ij}(r_{ij}), \quad (2.12)$$

where $F_i(\rho_i)$ is the embedding energy, which is a logarithmic function of the local electron density ρ_i around atom i (see for example ref[62] for detailed description of these functions), and $\phi_{ij}(r_{ij})$ is the pair interaction potential between atoms i and j as a function of their separation distance r_{ij} .

In MEAM, the local electron density ρ_i includes contributions from both the radial distance and the angular environment of surrounding atoms, making it an improvement over the simpler EAM. For different materials and alloys, the parameters in function, ($F_i(\rho_i)$), are fitted either to experimental data (such as lattice constants and elastic moduli) or to DFT calculations.

Although these empirical potentials are very efficient. However they are limited in their ability to capture with high accuracy the properties of the systems with complex structures such as dislocations. To overcome these limitations, advanced approaches like NNPs are increasingly being employed [63]. NNPs are particularly effective because they learn the complex potential energy surface directly from data, often DFT, rather than relying on a predefined mathematical function with only a few adjustable parameters. NNPs define an energy for each atom i as E_i and calculates the total energy of the system by summing up the energy of all atoms:

$$E_{\text{tot}}^{\text{NNP}} = \sum_i E_i \quad (2.13)$$

The energy E_i for each atom is computed by a neural network construction. In such a network, the energy is expressed as a function of the input features (describing the local environment around atom i), and the energy calculation involves several layers, each composed of neurons with associated weights and biases. In principle one can use any number of layers and nodes, however we use a network with 2 layers each having 24 nodes. For this network the atomic

energy is expressed as:

$$E_i = f_3 \left(b_1^3 + \sum_{k=1}^{24} a_{k,1}^{2,3} \cdot f_k^2 \left(b_k^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{24} a_{j,k}^{1,2} \cdot f_j^1 \left(b_j^1 + \sum_{i=1}^{64} a_{i,j}^{0,1} \cdot G_i \right) \right) \right) \quad (2.14)$$

The term $a_{z,w}^{q,p}$ represents the weight connecting node z in layer q to node w in layer p , while b_z^q is the bias associated with node z in layer q . The activation function applied at layer q is denoted as f_q ; in our case, we use the softplus function $\ln(1 + e^x)$ for f_1 , while f_2 and f_3 are the identity functions.

The G_i functions are used to describe the local atomic environment and are commonly referred to as descriptors. In the Behler-Parrinello (B-P) Neural Network Potential framework[63], these are known as symmetry functions. We employ both radial and angular symmetry functions, which are defined as follows:

The radial symmetry function is given by:

$$G_i^{\text{radial}} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{atom}}} e^{-\eta(R_{ij}-R_s)^2} \cdot f_c(R_{ij}), \quad (2.15)$$

and the angular symmetry function is expressed as:

$$G_i^{\text{angular}} = 2^{1-\zeta} \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{k \neq i, j} (1 + \lambda \cdot \cos \theta_{ijk})^\zeta \cdot e^{-\eta(R_{ij}^2 + R_{ik}^2 + R_{jk}^2)} \cdot f_c(R_{ij}) \cdot f_c(R_{jk}) \cdot f_c(R_{ik}). \quad (2.16)$$

Here, R_c, η, ζ , and λ are predefined or hyperparameters for a given symmetry function. R_{ij} represents the distance between atoms i and j , while the cutoff function $f_c(r) = \tanh^3(1 - r/r_c)$ ensures that interactions beyond a certain distance r_c are smoothly decayed to zero.

This hierarchical structure allows the network to capture complex, non-linear dependencies between the atomic configuration and the energy.

By training on a comprehensive dataset that captures a wide variety of atomic configurations, NNPs can interpolate well within the range of the data, but their ability to extrapolate to unseen configurations remains a limitation[64]. Despite this, NNPs have shown great success in accurately modeling complex materials and processes, such as dislocation behavior and phase transitions, with much greater efficiency than first-principles methods[43, 65–69].

Molecular statics simulations, especially when coupled with modern interatomic potentials

like NNPs, are highly effective at predicting zero-temperature material properties. These simulations can compute lattice parameters, elastic constants, and other intrinsic properties. Moreover, they are essential for identifying the configurations and energetics of dislocations and other crystalline defects. Additionally, MS simulations are useful in finding transition paths between metastable states, as well as the corresponding saddle points, which are critical for understanding processes like defect migration in materials. In this work, all molecular statics (MS) simulations are performed using the LAMMPS code [70] with an NNP potential for the Mg-Zn system, trained via the n2p2 code[71, 72]. Visualization of the atomic configurations is carried out using OVITO software[73]. We use an accurate MEAM potential of pure Mg[74] developed for plasticity simulations only for the calculation of the pressure field around the prism edge dislocation. This calculation is not implemented in NNP framework.

2.3 Nudged Elastic Band Method (NEB)

Often, to understand mechanisms in materials such as chemical reactions, solute diffusion, and dislocation glide, we can determine the configurations and energies of the initial and final metastable states by finding the local minima in the PES, as discussed in the previous sections. As an illustration, Figure 2.1 shows a schematic representation of a PES with two metastable regions, initial and final. However, it is crucial to identify the minimum energy path (MEP) for the transition between initial and final. The MEP is important because it provides the activation barrier for the transition from initial to final state. The MEP represents the path along which the system encounters the lowest possible energy barrier during the transformation. The highest energy point along this path, known as the transition state, corresponds to a saddle point. The difference between the energy of this saddle point and the energy of the initial state determines the activation energy for the process. The activation energy then can be used in transition state theory, explained in the next section, to obtain the rate of a thermally activated process.

It is computationally infeasible to calculate the entire PES for all possible configurations of a system in order to determine the MEP. Instead, specialized methods such as the Nudged Elastic Band (NEB)[76] and string methods[77] are employed to find the MEP and transition state of an atomic process without scanning the whole PES. In this work, the NEB method is used to identify the transition states for solute diffusion, dislocation glide, and cross-slip.

The basic idea behind the NEB method is to construct a band of intermediate images (or replicas) of the system connecting the two meta-stable states (endpoints) (Figure 2.1 and to relax these images to approximate the MEP. In NEB, a set of M images are generated between the initial, \mathbf{R}_0 , and final, \mathbf{R}_{M+1} , states, as $\mathbf{R}_0, \mathbf{R}_1, \dots, \mathbf{R}_{M+1}$. These images are connected to each other by fictitious springs with a specified spring constant. The energy of each image is influenced by both the underlying PES and the elastic forces from the springs. Since the intermediate images are not in positions of local minima, the elastic spring forces are introduced to prevent them from sliding toward the endpoints and to ensure that the images

Figure 2.1: A schematic of a PES with two meta-stable regions[75]. Two different paths from the initial state to final state is shown. The different forces on a particular image is shown in the inset which corresponds to a path which is not yet converged to MEP. \mathbf{F}_i is the total ionic and spring forces

remain at equidistant separations. In NEB method, a path tangent vector which is a $3N$ component vector, with N being the number of atoms, is defined as:

$$\hat{\tau}_i = \frac{\mathbf{R}_{i+1} - \mathbf{R}_{i-1}}{|\mathbf{R}_{i+1} - \mathbf{R}_{i-1}|}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq M \quad (2.17)$$

then two forces are applied on each image i to move it towards the MEP. First, the perpendicular component of the potential energy to $\hat{\tau}_i$ denoted by F^\perp and second, the parallel component of the spring force, F^\parallel . Therefore the total NEB force on the image is written as:

$$\mathbf{F}^{\text{NEB}} = \mathbf{F}^\perp + \mathbf{F}^\parallel \quad (2.18)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}^\perp &= -\nabla U(\mathbf{R}_i) + (\nabla U(\mathbf{R}_i) \cdot \hat{\tau}_i) \hat{\tau}_i \\ \mathbf{F}^\parallel &= (\mathbf{F}_i^s \cdot \hat{\tau}_i) \hat{\tau}_i \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_i^s = k^s(\mathbf{R}_{i+1} - 2\mathbf{R}_i + \mathbf{R}_{i-1})$ and k^s is the spring constant. By utilizing these forces, the potential energy drives the images toward the minimum energy MEP, while the spring forces maintain separation between the images. The NEB method is typically initialized with an interpolated path connecting the initial and final states, after which the images are relaxed until the NEB force, \mathbf{F}^{NEB} falls below a specified threshold. Regular NEB has limitations in accurately identifying the saddle point (transition state). NEB can often locate the general path but sometimes fails to precisely converge on this highest-energy point. The Climbing

Image NEB (CI-NEB) is an enhancement of the regular NEB method, specifically developed to overcome the challenge of accurately locating the saddle point. In CI-NEB, one image in the NEB path is designated as the climbing image. This image, ideally close to the highest-energy point along the path, is selected to move uphill in energy during the optimization process. Unlike in regular NEB, where the force is minimized in both the perpendicular and parallel directions to the path, the climbing image experiences a different force treatment: The perpendicular force is minimized, as with regular NEB, to keep it on the MEP. The spring force in the direction along the path is replaced by the true force opposite to the energy gradient, effectively driving the image to ascend directly toward the saddle point. This pushes the climbing image toward the highest energy along the path, effectively "climbing" to the saddle point. The force on climbing image, \mathbf{R}_{CI} , is expressed now instead of Equation 2.18 as:

$$\mathbf{F}^{CI-NEB} = -\nabla U(\mathbf{R}_{CI}) + 2(\nabla U(\mathbf{R}_{CI}) \cdot \hat{\tau}_i)\hat{\tau}_i \quad (2.20)$$

In our work, we employ CI-NEB method as implemented in LAMMPS. However, for implementing NEB within the density functional DFT framework, we adopt a different approach. Specifically, we eliminate the spring force from our criteria, as its primary function is to keep the images equidistant. Since, during solute diffusion, the transition state is the only critical state of interest, we apply the following two criteria to identify the transition state: 1) The perpendicular force must be below a threshold value, and 2) The total atomic force, $-\nabla U$, on the transition state must also be below a threshold. The first condition ensures that the images lie on the MEP path, while the second condition confirms that the state is indeed a transition state, indicated by zero atomic forces. This is very similar to CI-NEB method, as it also eliminates the spring force on the climbing image. By using these criteria, computational time is significantly reduced, as the less critical spring force does not need to be nearly zero.

2.4 Transition State Theory (TST)

After determining the metastable states and identifying the MEP and transition state for a process using methods such as NEB, we are now in a position to calculate the time scale or rate of the process. This can be done using Transition State Theory (TST)[78, 79], which is particularly useful in systems where the transition rates between states are of interest. For example, in the context of dislocation slip, the net rate of dislocation motion is directly related to the strain rate of deformation, a measurable quantity in experiments. TST provides a framework for estimating reaction rates based on the zero-temperature quantities such as the energy barrier. TST is especially powerful because it allows us to predict reaction rates without having to rely on time-consuming simulations like molecular dynamics (MD), where events such as atomic rearrangements might occur on time scales that are not easily accessible. In many cases, MD simulations are limited by the computational cost required to simulate very long time scales, as atomic vibrations occur on the order of femtoseconds (10^{-15} s), while processes like dislocation glide or solute diffusion may take place over microseconds or longer. By using TST, we can bypass this limitation and calculate rates for such slow processes

Figure 2.2: a) contour plot of partitioning of the potential energy surface according to transition state theory. A hyper-surface S_D divides the meta-stable basin A from meta-stable basin B, saddle point is located on S_D b) three dimensional representation of PES [80]

effectively.

Transition State Theory (TST) calculates the rate of a process using equilibrium statistical mechanics. If we consider the PES of a system in configurational space, as shown in Figure 2.2, TST divides this space into two regions: one corresponding to the metastable basin A and the other to the metastable basin B. The dimensionality of the configurational space is $3N$, where N is the number of atoms in the system. The two regions representing the metastable basins are separated by a hyper-surface of dimension $3N - 1$, which is perpendicular to the contours of the potential energy surface.

Assuming that the transition occurs from meta-stable state A to meta-stable state B. The system initially resides in region A, fluctuating around the local energy minimum. Occasionally, these fluctuations are large enough for the system to reach the transition state and cross into region B. TST assumes that once the system reaches the transition state, it will cross over to region B without recrossing back to region A. However, this assumption makes TST an approximation rather than an exact theory, as in reality, the system may recross the energy barrier multiple times before finally transitioning into the metastable state B. Even if the system does not fall back into state A, it may linger near the transition state before fully settling in state B.

Considering the canonical (NVT) ensemble, TST demonstrates that the rate is proportional to the ratio of the partition function of the states that are immediately adjacent to the hyper-surface S_D to that of the states in basin A as:

$$v_{A \rightarrow B}^{\text{TST}} = \sqrt{\frac{k_B T}{2\pi m}} \frac{\int_{S_D} e^{-U(\mathbf{R})/k_B T} dS}{\int_A e^{-U(\mathbf{R})/k_B T} d\mathbf{R}} \quad (2.21)$$

where m is the atomic mass. By considering only the significant harmonic terms in potential energy, the integrals in eq 2.21 can be explicitly calculated and by further simplifications we

can recover the well-known empirical Arrhenius form:

$$v_{A \rightarrow B} = v_0 \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{kT}\right) \quad (2.22)$$

$v_0 = 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is taken to be Debye frequency and $\Delta E = U(\mathbf{R}_{\text{TS}}) - U(\mathbf{R}_A)$ is the energy difference between the transition state and the initial state.

In summary, Transition State Theory (TST) offers a simple yet powerful framework for calculating reaction rates, showing that the empirical Arrhenius equation is based on a solid physical law rooted in statistical mechanics. However, it is important to note that by assuming no recrossing of the transition state, TST may overestimate the rate of transition, as the system could potentially recross the barrier multiple times before fully transitioning into the final state.

2.5 Stroh formalism for dislocation solution

This section explains very briefly the anisotropic elasticity analysis formulated by Stroh[81] and outlines the steps that are needed to obtain the anisotropic displacement fields of a dislocation. The content of this section is largely derived from the material in Ting's book[82]. For a deformation in which the displacement only depends on the x_1 and x_2 directions, which is the case for the dislocation as its elastic field is constant along its length, it can be shown that the solution of the general elastic equilibrium equation can be written as

$$u_i = a_i f(z) \quad (2.23)$$

where z is a complex number of the form $z = x_1 + p x_2$ and $f(z)$ is an arbitrary function which depends on the boundary conditions of the problem. Inserting the above-mentioned displacement field in the elastic equilibrium equation, we obtain the sextic equation:

$$\{Q + p(R + R^T) + p^2 T\}v = 0 \quad (2.24)$$

Where

$$Q_{ik} = C_{i1k1}, \quad R_{ik} = C_{i1k2}, \quad T_{ik} = C_{i2k2} \quad (2.25)$$

Our aim is to find roots p and vector v . The sextic equation has six roots, and it can be shown that three of these roots are complex conjugates of the corresponding other three roots. Therefore, by summing the solutions for distinct roots, we have the general solution:

$$u = \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 [v^\alpha f^\alpha(z^\alpha) + \bar{v}^\alpha f^{\alpha+3}(\bar{z}^\alpha)] \quad (2.26)$$

Stroh showed that the problem can be reduced to an eigenvalue equation, $N\xi = p\xi$, where p

and $\xi = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ w \end{bmatrix}$, with $w = (R^T + pT^T)v$, are the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the 6×6 matrix N . By obtaining v and p , a solution for a dislocation with Burgers vector, b , can be written as:

$$u = \frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} (V \langle f(z) \rangle W^T) b \quad (2.27)$$

where

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} v_1^{(1)} & v_1^{(2)} & v_1^{(3)} \\ v_2^{(1)} & v_2^{(2)} & v_2^{(3)} \\ v_3^{(1)} & v_3^{(2)} & v_3^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad W = \begin{bmatrix} w_1^{(1)} & w_1^{(2)} & w_1^{(3)} \\ w_2^{(1)} & w_2^{(2)} & w_2^{(3)} \\ w_3^{(1)} & w_3^{(2)} & w_3^{(3)} \end{bmatrix}$$

and $\langle f(z) \rangle = \text{diag} [f(z^1), f(z^2), f(z^3)]$. For dislocation problems often the function $f(z) = \ln(z)$ is used. The reason for using this particular function is that it satisfies the discontinuity condition at the slip plane of the dislocation. In the present thesis, we use the AtomMan package for construction of dislocation cells according to the displacement field obtained from Stroh formalism (Equation 2.27).

3 First-principles modeling of dislocation cores

This chapter is in part extracted from the following publications

1. Rahbar Niazi. M, and Curtin. W. A. "Solute strengthening of prism edge dislocations in Mg alloys." *European Journal of Mechanics-A/Solids* 104 (2024): 105128.
2. liu. Xin, Barreira. Rui, Rahbarniazi. Masoud, and Curtin. W.A. "Strengthening by 110 and 112 edge dislocations in BCC high entropy alloys". *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering* (2024)

The atomic structure of dislocation cores plays a pivotal role in determining the configuration and mobility of dislocations, which directly influence a material's mechanical properties[83]. For instance, it is well-known that edge dislocations move significantly faster than screw dislocations in BCC metals, a difference largely attributed to the core structure of these dislocations [84–87]. In Mg alloys the CRSS value for edge basal slip is only about 0.5 MPa which is largely due to its extended planar core. The activity of cross-slip of screw dislocations also strongly depend on the difference in core energy of the dislocations on glide and cross-slip planes [84]. The difference in mobility between these core structures is reflected in the Peierls stress, which represents the intrinsic resistance to dislocation motion imposed by the crystal lattice.

The overall strength of a material can be dominated by either edge or screw dislocations[88], and in some cases, this dominance is temperature-dependent. For example, in Fe-C system, edge dislocations play a more significant role in strengthening at higher temperatures, whereas screw dislocations dominate at lower temperatures[89]. This shift is largely due to the stronger interaction between edge dislocations and solutes compared to screw dislocations, with solute atoms exerting a greater pinning effect on edge dislocations.

While classical linear elasticity theory can accurately describe the elastic fields of dislocations at distances far from the core, this approximation breaks down within the core region, where dislocation core spreads itself to prevent infinite strain energy. The core structure may exhibit

either compact or extended configurations with large differences in their mobility. Extended cores usually move faster than compact cores and may interact less strongly with solutes. The core region can interact with solutes through both chemical and elastic mechanisms, altering dislocation motion and, consequently, the material's plastic behavior [90, 91]. The interaction of solutes with dislocations vanishes as the solute is located only a few Burgers vector away from the core of the dislocation.

To accurately capture the detailed atomic interactions within the dislocation core, experimental methods often face significant limitations due to the very small scale of the core region. Hence, computational methods, particularly those based on first-principles calculations, have emerged as powerful tools for studying dislocation cores [92, 93]. Using techniques such as cluster methods including: fixed boundary conditions [45, 94], flexible boundary conditions [95–97], and periodic boundary methods including dipole and quadruple methods [98–101], researchers can calculate the core structure with atomic-scale precision. These methods allow for the investigation of core configurations at a reasonable computational cost while maintaining conditions that closely approximate the behavior of an infinite bulk material.

The periodic boundary approach involves forming a dislocation dipole, which contains two dislocations with opposing Burgers vectors, to ensure geometric compatibility. These dipoles are then repeated periodically across the simulation due to periodic boundary conditions. The advantage of this approach is that there is no free surface and therefore the problem of spurious forces due to free surfaces are eliminated. However, this benefit is countered by the complexity of calculating interactions within the dislocation dipoles and between their periodic images. Additionally, this method requires using a large number of atoms due to the presence of two dislocations. To mitigate issues related to image effects, extensions to this method sometimes include the use of quadrupolar arrays.

We use the cluster method, particularly the fixed boundary condition (FBC) method to obtain the core structure. The schematics of the super-cell geometry in FBC is shown in 3.1. In this method a super-cell with a sufficiently large size is constructed inside a simulation cell separated by a vacuum layer from its periodic images. A dislocation core is inserted at the center of the super-cell using the Volterra solution. The relaxed configuration of the dislocation core is then obtained by relaxation of the atoms located in the relaxation region (3.1) while keeping all the atoms at the boundary layer fixed. The FBC method is straightforward to implement and circumvents the image effects associated with other approaches, such as dipole construction. However, FBC has a notable disadvantage: it generates free surface forces arising from disruptions in electronic states near the surface. These disruptions alter the charge density, subsequently exerting additional forces on the inner ions. In contrast, the flexible boundary method offers a more sophisticated solution by employing a flexible boundary rather than a fixed one. This technique adapts dynamically to the internal displacements of the atoms in the core region and minimizes artificial forces by allowing the boundary to respond naturally to the dislocation-induced deformations using the lattice Green function. As a result, it provides a more accurate representation of the dislocation behavior without the

Figure 3.1: A schematic of a typical simulation cell for implementing the fixed boundary condition for the relaxation of dislocation structure. There are three regions; i) Relaxation region inside which the atoms are relaxed for obtaining the equilibrium structure of the core region where the atomic displacements are highly non-linear. ii) Boundary layer, where the atoms are fixed according to their displacements given by linear elasticity. This region should be sufficiently away from the core region so that the linear elasticity rules hold. iii) Vacuum region, for separating the cell from the effects of its periodic images.

constraint of immobile boundaries. However, this method is less straightforward than FBC and it requires more expensive computations in order to avoid the surface effects, either by using larger radius cylinder or by periodic conditions which itself can lead to defects at the boundary.

In this chapter, we demonstrate the use of first-principles calculations combined with the fixed boundary condition technique to simulate the core structure of edge dislocations in selected HCP and BCC materials with a manageable computational cost.

3.1 Prism edge dislocation core in HCP Mg

Here we study the core structure of the edge prism dislocation in Mg, which will be further explored in the next two chapters to examine the effects of solute addition on edge prism glide and solute strengthening at high temperatures.

The simulation size should be as large as possible but the scaling of computational cost as N^3 for N electrons requires that an optimum super-cell size be selected. Here, the size of the super-cell is determined based on two criteria. First, the positions of atoms near the boundary of the super-cell should closely match the positions predicted by the anisotropic elastic displacement field of the dislocation. This ensures that these atoms are already close

Figure 3.2: The variation of the dislocation line energy as a function of the radius of a cylinder surrounding the center of the dislocation. The red circles are calculated using MEAM and the blue line is a linear line with the slope K

to their relaxed positions allowing them to be fixed. Second, the atomic forces in the core region, due to free surface effects, must be minimized. The first criterion can be achieved by calculation of the total energy of the dislocation in cylinders of various size and its comparison with the atomistic calculations. Based on anisotropic elasticity, the total energy of a dislocation centered inside a cylinder of radius R can be expressed as:

$$E = K \ln \left(\frac{R}{r_c} \right) + E_c \Big|_{r_c} \quad (3.1)$$

where r_c is the cutoff radius related to the non-linear core region and $E_c \Big|_{r_c}$ is the core energy defined for the core radius r_c . The coefficient K which is related to elastic constants and Burgers vector can be fully determined using Stroh formalism [81]. Equation 3.1 shows that the total energy of the dislocation scales linearly with logarithm of the cylinder radius R with the slope K . For studying the edge prism core in Mg we have computed the dislocation energy as a function of the super-cell radius using the MEAM potential [74], which should be sufficient for capturing non-core elasticity effects, and we compare the scaling of the elastic energy versus cell radius to the predictions of anisotropic elasticity. This is done according to ref [102] in the following way: a large cylindrical cell with the radius of $300b$ is constructed with directions $X \parallel [11\bar{2}0]$, which will be the dislocation glide direction, $Y \parallel [\bar{1}100]$ normal to the glide direction, and $Z \parallel [0001]$ the dislocation line direction. A displacement field obtained from Stroh formalism of anisotropic elasticity is applied to the whole cylinder to create the prismatic edge dislocation. Then the atoms at the boundary of the cylinder and within the thickness of higher than the cutoff energy of the interatomic potential are held fixed at their position according to the Volterra solution and all the other atoms inside are relaxed. Figure 3.2 shows the variation of the total energy of the dislocation line as a function of the super-cell

size. The elasticity scaling is achieved at a distance of only about $3b$ from the center of the dislocation core. We therefore require the radius to be larger than $3b$.

The second criterion, minimizing the surface forces (Friedel oscillations) in the core region, can be evaluated by calculating the atomic forces in a perfect crystal cell of the same size and geometry as the dislocation-containing super-cell. If the atoms in the perfect crystal are in their equilibrium positions, the only forces acting on them would be surface forces. This allows us to quantify the surface forces in the region where the dislocation will be inserted. A perfect hexagonally-shaped super-cell with the same directions for the prism edge dislocation is constructed by the equilibrium lattice parameters. The minimum periodic distance along the line direction is used. Studies with increasing radius show that at a radius of $8a$ (384 atoms), and a vacuum layer of thickness 10 \AA surrounding the ionic domain, self-consistent calculations of the electronic forces perfect crystal held at the DFT-computed equilibrium lattice parameters ($a = 3.19 \text{ \AA}$, $c/a=1.62$) show spurious forces below 10 meV/\AA in the core region, (Figure 3.3a). An edge dislocation introduced at the center of this super-cell will thus be subject to low forces.

For the relaxation of the dislocation core We use DFT as implemented in VASP [103, 104]. The calculations use the GGA approximation, the PBE exchange correlation functional [54], and PAW pseudopotentials [56] (PAW_PBE Mg 13Apr2007) that treat the 3s electrons as the valence states. The valence electron eigenstates are expanded in a plane wave basis set with a cut off energy of 400 eV and the second-order Methfessel-Paxton [58] scheme with a smearing parameter of 0.2 eV is used to describe the partial occupancies of the orbitals. A Γ -centered Monkhorst-Pack [105] k-mesh is used with a spacing of 0.01 \AA^{-1} . For a given ionic configuration, relaxation of the electronic degrees of freedom is performed in a self-consistency loop with convergence at 10^{-8} eV .

The edge dislocation creates an atomistic step along the outer surface, and atoms are removed to eliminate this step, leaving a smooth boundary in a simulation cell containing 383 atoms (see Figure 3.3b). All ions within 3.7 \AA (4 atomic planes) of the outer boundaries are then held fixed; these fixed atoms have high spurious forces (as in Figure 3.3a) due to the free surface but those forces are not relaxed. All interior ions are then relaxed until all forces are below 10 meV/\AA . This procedure creates the initial prism edge dislocation in pure Mg as shown in Figure 3.3b, with the corresponding ionic forces after relaxation shown in Figure 3.3c. The core structure is similar to those obtained using various interatomic potentials [95, 106].

Figure 3.3: a) Magnitudes of ionic forces for HCP Mg fixed at the bulk Mg lattice constants within the hexagonal super-cell used here (outer vacuum region not shown); forces in the interior of the domain are small. b) The prismatic edge core structure obtain using the same super-cell after the introduction of an edge dislocation, removal of the atom at the end of the step caused by introducing the dislocation, and relaxation of the ionic forces (atoms colors using common neighbor analysis to differentiate core (grey) and boundary (grey) from HCP atoms (red)). c) The magnitude of ionic forces in the relaxed configuration (b)

3.2 Edge dislocation cores in BCC structures

In this section we investigate the edge core structures in specific BCC metals, namely Ta, Nb, and Mo. Understanding the core configuration of edge dislocations in BCC structures is important, because while it is well-known that screw dislocation motion controls the yield strength and flow behavior in elemental BCC metals and dilute BCC alloys due to the compact screw core, recent research suggests that edge dislocation strengthening is becoming increasingly competitive with screw strengthening, especially in BCC high entropy alloys (HEAs) with large

solute misfit parameters [107–109].

Deformation in BCC alloys is understood to occur predominantly by dislocations with Burgers vectors $1/2\langle 111 \rangle$ and most typically gliding on $\{110\}$ planes. However, non- $\{110\}$ slip is known to arise in some BCC metals and dilute alloys, and more recently has been seen in medium entropy alloys (MEAs) [110]. The competition between $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ slip is typically examined in the context of screw dislocations because the compact screw core in BCC metals can glide, in principle, on any crystalline slip plane containing the $1/2\langle 111 \rangle$ Burgers vector. Recent work on BCC alloys proposes that alloying can drive a change in core structure from a non-degenerate core to a degenerate core, with a concomitant change in slip from the $\{110\}$ to the $\{112\}$ planes [111]. Nonetheless, since screw motion on different planes is always feasible, the study of *edge* dislocations gliding on different planes becomes relevant. It is then possible that, in some alloys, edge dislocations control strength and that $\{112\}$ slip is preferred over $\{110\}$ slip. Recent room temperature studies on polycrystals and micropillars have shown that $\{112\}$ slip is preferred in TiZrNbHfTa but dominated by screw dislocations while $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ slip can be observed in MoNbTaVW with a mixture of edge and screw dislocations [112]. Application of $\{110\}$ edge theory has previously predicted the measured tensile yield strengths in both alloys [90, 113] in good agreement with experiments. In light of recent results suggesting $\{112\}$ slip to be competitive with $\{110\}$ slip, we develop the theory for strengthening of edge dislocations gliding on $\{112\}$ using the same framework as previously used for glide on $\{110\}$ in HEAs.

A key concept in the theory is the existence of an “average atom” [114] that is a single hypothetical atom that, when put into the same crystal structure as the HEA, has the same average material properties (e.g. elastic constants, lattice constants, stacking fault energies, etc.) as the true random alloy but without the randomness. The average dislocation core structure can then be created in this “average alloy”. Each of the n elements within an n -component HEA can then be considered as a solute in the “average atom” matrix, with misfit volume ΔV_n . The interaction energy between a solute and a dislocation in the average alloy can also be determined at every atomic position around the dislocation. The pressure field $p(x, y)$ around the average alloy dislocation core can also be computed, and then the solute-dislocation interaction energy at each atomistic point (x, y) can be approximated as $-p(x, y)\Delta V_n$. Explicit creation of an interatomic “average atom” potential has been demonstrated for EAM potentials, but it is the conceptual framework that is important.

By considering elasticity theory as the basis for comparing $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ slip, we require average dislocation core structures and pressure fields. The pressure field of the dislocation core can be obtained using interatomic potentials. However, we need to first ensure the accuracy of these potentials in predicting the core structure compared to DFT. Since the dislocation core structures and pressure fields depend predominantly on the alloy elastic constants and unstable stacking fault energy (USFE), we calculate the dislocation cores in three elemental metal Nb, Ta, and Mo which along with the dislocation core of W calculated previously we can use them as proxies for the average core structures of multicomponent

alloys spanning a range of potential core structures (range of elastic constants and USFEs). Furthermore, while it is possible to create dislocation in the true random multicomponent alloy using suitable interatomic potentials (see, for example, [90, 110, 113, 115–118]), it is not possible to extract the solute-dislocation interaction energies because the dislocations have already responded to the precise local solute configurations in any one realization of the random alloy. The motion of dislocations in a random alloy can also be studied by direct atomistic simulations, but such simulations must be done (i) at precise length scales dictated by theory or very long (and hence costly) lengths, (ii) always over many sample realizations to obtain statistically reliable results, and (iii) for each alloy composition of interest. Such brute-force investigation does not reveal intrinsic understanding nor enable any predictions of behavior of new alloys.

Following the methodology used for Mg prism edge core, here we also use fixed boundary condition method to obtain the relaxed core structures of the {110} and {112} edge dislocations in Nb, Ta and Mo. The calculations use PAW pseudopotentials with 13 (Nb), 5 (Ta) and 6 (Mo) states treated as valence electrons. Valence-electron eigenstates are expanded with a spin-free plane wave basis set, using a cutoff energy of 550 eV . The First-order Methfessel-Paxton scheme with a smearing parameter of 0.6 eV is used to describe the partial occupancies of the orbitals. Employing such a relatively large smearing parameter is justified below. A Γ -centered Monkhorst-Pack k-mesh is employed with the interval between neighboring k-mesh points along any reciprocal lattice vector set to 0.02 \AA^{-1} . For example, this k-mesh density is equivalent to a $15 \times 15 \times 15$ sampling for a 2-atom cubic unit cell BCC Nb ($a = 3.308\text{ \AA}$). For a given ionic configuration, relaxation of the electronic degrees of freedom is performed in a self-consistency loop with convergence at 10^{-6} eV . All interior ions are relaxed until all forces are below 10 meV/\AA .

As with the Mg case in the previous section, we need to select an optimal super-cell that provides a good approximation of the bulk material while remaining computationally feasible. It was shown [119] using various interatomic potentials (Figure 2 in reference [119]) that, with the exception of SNAP potential for Nb, both 110 and 112 edge dislocation cores in other BCC metals exhibit behavior closely aligned with elasticity beyond a distance of approximately $3b$ from the core. Therefore, similar to the Mg case, we must use a super-cell with a radius greater than $3b$ to ensure that the boundary layer is in the elasticity region.

To analyze the ionic forces resulting from electronic Friedel oscillations, we calculated the electronic forces in perfect BCC super-cells of the same size and orientation as the 110 and 112 dislocation super-cells. First, we investigated the effect of super-cell shape on surface forces. Figure 3.4a,b show the distribution of electronic forces for two super-cells of Mo: one circular and one rectangular. It is evident that, for a nearly identical number of atoms, the force values in the interior of the rectangular cell are significantly lower than those in the circular cell. This difference may be attributed to three factors: first, the difference is due to the low-index planes at the surface of the rectangular cell, which have lower surface energy and are more representative of the bulk structure compared to the high-index planes exposed to vacuum in

the circular cell. Second, it can be due to the larger length of the rectangular cell. If the latter case is true then for the same width the circular cell requires higher number of atoms which increases the computational cost. Third, it is not possible to reach a perfect circular shape due to the crystal structure and the surfaces are less smooth than rectangular cells. Therefore, to reduce computational cost and to ensure a more realistic representation of bulk behavior, we selected the rectangular cell for further calculations.

Figure 3.4: Distribution of ionic forces in calculations with super-cells of different shapes and different smearing parameters, σ . (a) and (b) differ by super-cell shape but use the same σ . (a) and (c) are the same super-cell but use different σ values

Using larger smearing parameters results in a significant reduction of Friedel oscillations, thereby mitigating the Friedel forces observed in simulations. Figure 3.4a,c compare the ionic force distributions in identical super-cells of Mo, calculated using two different values of the smearing parameter. It is evident that the forces are considerably lower when using a smearing parameter of $\sigma = 0.6 \text{ eV}$ compared to $\sigma = 0.2 \text{ eV}$, indicating a reduction in spurious surface effects. Friedel forces, which originate from perturbations in the electronic density near

surfaces or interfaces, tend to decrease with increased electronic smearing, as this effectively smooths the sharp transitions in electron occupation that contribute to these oscillations. However, it is important to note that using larger smearing parameters comes with certain trade-offs, specifically in the accuracy of material properties such as lattice parameters and elastic constants.

To evaluate how the choice of smearing parameter affects our simulation results, we calculated several bulk properties, including lattice parameters and elastic constants, using two different values of the smearing parameter: $\sigma = 0.2$ eV and $\sigma = 0.6$ eV. The properties are compared in Table 3.1. The difference is below 1% in all cases except C_{44} where there is about 11% difference for Nb and Ta, and 2% difference for Mo. C_{44} , is usually sensitive to the precision of the electronic structure calculations. We note, that simply increasing the k-point mesh to $16 \times 16 \times 16$ with the smearing $\sigma = 0.2$ eV yields $C_{44} = 16$ GPa, similar to the value for the larger smearing and slightly smaller k-point mesh.

Therefore, we have chosen to use a smearing parameter of $\sigma = 0.6$ eV for the subsequent calculations in this work, as it provides a balance between reduced Friedel forces and reasonable accuracy for material properties.

Table 3.1: Bulk properties of Nb, Ta, and Mo calculated using two different smearing parameters $\sigma = 0.2$ (eV) and $\sigma = 0.6$ (eV) and experiments

	Nb			Ta			Mo		
	$\sigma = 0.2$	$\sigma = 0.6$	Exp	$\sigma = 0.2$	$\sigma = 0.6$	Exp	$\sigma = 0.2$	$\sigma = 0.6$	Exp
a (Å)	3.308	3.308	3.299	3.308	3.295	3.301	3.151	3.150	3.143
C_{11} (GPa)	243	244	253	272	270	266	479	477	450
C_{12} (GPa)	133	132	133	164	165	158	162	162	173
C_{44} (GPa)	18	16	31	71	63	87	97	95	125

After selecting the super-cell shape and smearing parameter, the next step is to determine the optimal dimensions of the super-cell, balancing the reduction of surface forces and computational cost. Figure 3.5 illustrates the ionic force distribution for Mo super-cells with varying widths and lengths. It is apparent that the surface forces are highly sensitive to the super-cell dimensions, with certain configurations yielding significantly lower forces at the center. In particular, it seems that increasing the length of the super-cell is more effective at reducing surface forces than increasing its width. For example, the cell with 396 atoms shows larger surface forces at the center compared to the cell with 390 atoms, despite the higher atom count. This difference is likely due to the substantially lower packing density of the $\{111\}$ planes that form the width of the 396-atom cell. Therefore, we chose the super-cell with 370 atoms for simulating Mo $\{110\}$ slip. This cell size offers a suitable compromise, with sufficiently low surface forces while avoiding the computational expense associated with larger super-cells that would further reduce these forces. The same analysis was also performed to

select super-cell sizes for {112} slip of Mo and both slip systems of Nb and Ta.

The super-cells selected for dislocation analysis and the surface force distribution are shown in Figure 3.6 using smearing of $\sigma = 0.6eV$, with the corresponding equilibrium lattice parameters as shown in Table 3.1. In all cases, except Mo {112} where the surface forces are below $20 meV/\text{\AA}$, the forces on the ions in the core of the dislocations are below $15 meV/\text{\AA}$, which we deem sufficient for determining the core structure.

Figure 3.5: Ionic forces due to free surface in super-cells of different dimensions oriented in {110} slip system of Mo. The values of L and W are in Angstrom. The cell with 370 atoms is chosen for dislocation analysis of Mo.

Figure 3.6: Ionic forces due to free surface in super-cells selected for different elements.

Figure 3.7: Geometry of the super-cell (before relaxation) used for the relaxation of dislocation cores with fixed boundary condition. The positions of the atoms are derived from Volterra solution. Atoms represented by red color are fixed during the relaxation.

The dislocation cores are relaxed using a super-cell periodic along the dislocation line and fixed boundary condition applied on its external surfaces with a vacuum thickness of 10\AA . Figure 3.7 shows, as an example, the super-cell, obtained by applying Volterra solution to the perfect crystal, used for the relaxation of $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ dislocations in Nb. The positions of the ions located at the boundary layer (red colored in Figure 3.7) are fixed according to their Volterra displacement field and all the remaining ions (represented by blue color) are relaxed. Figures 3.8 show the common neighbor analysis (CNA) of the relaxed structure of the cores for Nb, Ta and Mo on the 110 and 112 slip planes. The atomic core structures are very similar across all the elements. Following atomic planes across the core, the Ta $\{112\}$ core shows a slightly more pronounced “kink” adjacent to the “extra” plane of atoms at the very core, but otherwise there are few identifiable differences among the core structures.

We also compared DFT cores with the cores obtained by a Machine learning SNAP potential. Figure 3.9, 3.10 and 3.11 show the atomic positions and edge component of the Nye tensor for the Nb, Ta and Mo edge dislocation in the $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ slip planes. In both slip planes, the SNAP cores in Nb, Ta and Mo are very similar to the DFT results, in all respects. This verifies the accuracy of the SNAP potential to study dislocations in high entropy alloys based on these elements. Based on the edge strengthening theory in BCC HEAs, Liu et al [119] used these SNAP potentials verified by DFT calculations here to calculate the dimensionless pressure field in pure elemental crystals of Nb, Ta, Mo and W that serve as proxy edge dislocation cores spanning the range of cores that would arise in real multicomponent alloys. The dimensionless pressure field is determined by the dislocation core structure, and elasticity theory shows that differences between $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ strengthening depend only on the differences in the dimensionless pressure field. From the atomistic dimensionless pressure fields, Liu et al [119] obtained dimensionless energy barrier and zero-temperature yield stress parameters for each slip system. Comparing the dimensionless quantities for $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ slip, they find that the strengthening is very similar.

Figure 3.8: Common neighbor analysis of edge dislocation cores in Nb, Ta, and Mo on {110} and {112} slip systems.

Figure 3.9: Edge component of Nye tensor for edge dislocations on (a) $\{110\}$ and (b) $\{112\}$ slip planes in Nb. For visualization purposes, the “extra” plane of atoms corresponding to the center of the core is indicated by dashed line.

Figure 3.10: Edge component of Nye tensor for edge dislocation on (a) $\{110\}$ and (b) $\{112\}$ slip planes in Ta.

Figure 3.11: Edge component of Nye tensor for edge dislocation on (a) {110} and (b) {112} slip planes in Ta.

4 Solute strengthening of edge prism dislocation

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In this chapter we will focus on the high temperature strengthening regime of prismatic slip in Mg alloys. The underlying mechanism of any strengthening of prismatic slip at higher temperatures has not been established. Normally, solute strengthening is prevalent in fcc alloys [120] and basal slip in Mg [121] due to edge dislocations because edge dislocations create a pressure field that interacts with the misfitting solutes to create pinning of the dislocation. On the other hand, softening at low temperatures and hardening at higher temperatures is observed in dilute BCC alloys that are controlled by screw double-kink nucleation and glide that is analogous to the basal-prism-basal cross-slip process in Mg [86]. Thus, the effects of solutes on both edge and screw dislocation motion in the prismatic direction in dilute Mg alloys merit investigation. Solute strengthening at very low solute concentrations is expected to be small based on studies of fcc Al alloys and basal slip in Mg alloys [1, 91]. However, unlike those cases, the prism $\langle a \rangle$ edge dislocation core is compact and so solute/dislocation interaction energies are likely higher and more localized spatially, both factors leading to higher strengthening than in the cases having dissociated dislocations. Here, we thus examine the solute strengthening of prismatic edge dislocations as the possible controlling strengthening mechanism at elevated temperatures.

4.1 Solute strengthening theory for edge dislocations

For a full review of the solute strengthening theory in random alloys and its application to various fcc and hcp alloys, the reader is referred to recent literature [91, 120, 122]. The central idea is that statistical fluctuations in the local solute configurations create attractive and repulsive regions for a dislocation, causing the dislocation to become wavy as it distorts to

find the low-energy (attractive) local solute configurations in the random alloy. Glide motion of the dislocation requires it to move from these low-energy favorable environments across adjacent unfavorable high-energy environments, and such motion requires stress-assisted thermal activation over the energy barriers. The energy, stress, and length scales for solute strengthening are established by minimizing the total dislocation energy, which consists of the solute/dislocation interactions that drive the waviness and the dislocation line tension that drives the dislocation to remain straight at its minimum length. The key components of the solute-strengthening are thus the interaction energies of a single solute with a dislocation segment as a function of the solute position relative to the dislocation and the dislocation line tension. The overall energy fluctuations due to a spatially-random distribution of solutes are a collective statistical result derived from the underlying single-solute interactions. Proceeding more specifically, the theory develops the total energy of a long dislocation having a waviness characterized by a wavelength 4ζ and amplitude w . The collective interaction of the solutes with a segment of length ζ leads to a characteristic energy change of the segment as it glides a distance w of

$$\Delta E_p = - \left[\left(\frac{c\zeta}{1.62b} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta \tilde{E}_p(w) \right] \quad (4.1)$$

where

$$\Delta \tilde{E}_p(w) = \left(\sum_{ij} \Delta U_{ij}(w)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4.2)$$

is the characteristic energy fluctuation per unit length of the dislocation, c is the solute concentration, b is the dislocation Burgers vector (here $b = a$), $\Delta U_{ij}(w) = U(x_i - w, y_j) - U(x_i, y_j)$ is the change in solute/dislocation interaction energy for a solute at position (x_i, y_j) after glide of the dislocation (aligned along z) from the origin to a distance w along the glide direction x . The additional line energy per length, ζ , of the wavy dislocation is $\Delta E_\Gamma = \Gamma \frac{w^2}{2\zeta}$, where Γ is the line tension. The minimum-energy wavy dislocation then has a characteristic length ζ_c and amplitude w_c , obtained by minimizing the total energy of a long dislocation line with length L ,

$$\frac{\Delta E_{\text{tot}}}{L} = \Gamma \frac{w^2}{2\zeta} - \left(\frac{c\zeta}{1.62b} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta \tilde{E}_p(w) \quad (4.3)$$

leading to

$$\zeta_c = \left(\frac{6.5\Gamma^2 w^4 b}{c\Delta \tilde{E}_p^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (4.4)$$

and w_c is then obtained from the solution of $\frac{\partial \Delta \tilde{E}_p}{\partial w} = \frac{\Delta \tilde{E}_p}{2w}$, which is performed numerically.

The total energy barrier ΔE_b , for moving dislocation segments of length ζ_c from an energetically favorable environment over the adjacent unfavorable energy environment at a distance w_c , is then derived as

$$\Delta E_b = \sqrt{2} \Delta E_p(\zeta_c, w_c) - \Delta E_\Gamma(\zeta_c, w_c) = 1.25 \left(\frac{\Gamma c \Delta \tilde{E}_p^2 w_c^2}{b} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (4.5)$$

Locally, the energy landscape for dislocation glide can be approximated as sinusoidal, $E(x) = \frac{\Delta E_b}{2} \left[1 - \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{w_c}\right) \right]$, and an applied stress τ reduces the energy by $-\tau b \zeta_c x$ as the dislocation glides over a distance x . At low to moderate temperatures, the stress-dependent energy barrier is then accurately described by

$$\Delta E(\tau) = \Delta E_b \left(1 - \frac{\tau}{\tau_{y_0}} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}, \quad (4.6)$$

where τ_{y_0} is the zero-temperature yield stress at which the barrier is reduced to zero and glide occurs with no thermal activation, with

$$\tau_{y_0} = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{\Delta E_b}{b w_c \zeta_c} \quad (4.7)$$

The flow stress at finite temperature T and strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ is then obtained using standard thermal activation theory via the Arrhenius law $\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E(\tau)}{k_B T}\right)$ where k_B is Boltzmann's constant and $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is a reference strain rate. At higher temperatures (or lower flow stresses), dislocation waviness at larger scales becomes relevant and the barrier increases.

Analysis has enabled an accurate but ad-hoc form for the flow stress over the full range of temperature and stress of [90]

$$\tau_y(T) = \tau_{y_0} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{0.55} \frac{k_B T}{\Delta E_b} \ln \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_0}{\dot{\epsilon}}\right)^{0.91} \quad (4.8)$$

Application of the theory then requires (i) the line tension, and (ii) the solute/dislocation interaction energies $U(x_i, y_j)$ at all sites around the core of the dislocation. The determination of $U(x_i, y_j)$ is by far the most important issue, and will be discussed in detail in the next section.

4.2 Yield strength of Mg prism edge dislocations

4.2.1 Elasticity estimates of solute/dislocation interaction energies

The solute/dislocation interaction energy can be estimated as the work done by the dislocation pressure field over the solute misfit volume, i.e., $U(x_i, y_j) = -p(x_i, y_j) \Delta V$, where $p(x_i, y_j)$ is

the pressure field at atomic site (x_i, y_j) in the plane normal to the dislocation line and ΔV is the misfit volume of the solute (here, Zn) when placed in the matrix material (here, Mg). Note that this approximation separates the role of the dislocation structure and stress fields and the role of the specific solute, which is very convenient theoretically. This elasticity approximation is certainly valid for positions (x_i, y_j) far away from the immediate core of the dislocation, but has often proven quite useful and sufficiently accurate even in the core of the dislocation where the local atomic structure deviates substantially from that of the crystalline matrix. The misfit strain tensor of Zn in Mg has been computed by DFT [32] and the mild anisotropy enables the misfit volume, which is the trace of the misfit strain tensor, $\Delta V = -10.6 \text{ \AA}^3$ to be used in modeling. The pressure field of the dislocation can be estimated using empirical interatomic potentials, provided that they are sufficiently accurate for dislocation properties. Figure 4.1 shows the pressure field of the prism edge dislocation in pure Mg obtained using an MEAM potential that has many suitable properties for modeling dislocations in Mg (but note that it is not suitable for modeling prismatic screw dislocations because it predicts stability against basal dissociation, which is unexpected based upon more accurate DFT calculations and the aforementioned in-situ TEM experiments. [42, 44]). The pressure field at the plane immediately above the slip plane is remarkably low, which is unexpected. The low values of $p(x_i, y_j)$ for these atomic sites in the immediate core region leads to a very low value for the interaction energies $U(x_i, y_j)$ and then very low solute strengthening. Such low interaction energies in a compact (non-dissociated) core are not expected to be accurate, and this motivates a direct first-principles study. A first-principles study has the further benefit of providing the $U(x_i, y_j)$ directly without any elasticity approximation. However, it is computationally intensive, and must be executed for many positions (x_i, y_j) and for any solutes of interest.

4.2.2 First-principles methodology for computing solute/dislocation interaction energies

The first principles calculation details for construction of edge prism dislocation in pure Mg are outlined in section 3.1. Here, We attempt to compute the Zn solute/dislocation interaction energies at each ionic site in the core region as follows. In the 383 atom cell (Figure 4.2) containing the edge dislocation, a Zn atom is inserted at the desired site in place of a Mg atom (labeled by the numbers in Figure 4.2) and all interior atoms are then relaxed until all the forces are less than 10 meV/\AA . The total energy of this system is $E_{\text{Zn+edge}}$, while E_{edge} is the energy of the original all-Mg cell containing the dislocation.

The interaction energy is then computed as

$$U(x, y) = (E_{\text{edge+Zn}} - E_{\text{edge}}) - (E_{\text{Mg+Zn}} - E_{\text{Mg}}) \quad (4.9)$$

Figure 4.1: Atomistic structure and atomic pressures p for the prism edge dislocation in pure Mg as obtained from an MEAM interatomic potential [14], showing very low pressures on atoms in the plane just above the slip plane where high solutedislocation energies U might normally be expected, casting doubt on the validity of the elasticity approximation $U(x_i, y_j) = -p(x_i, y_j)\Delta V$.

where E^{Mg} is the total energy of a perfect 384-atom hcp supercell (Figure 3.3a) and $E_{\text{Mg+Zn}}$ is the total energy of the same super-cell with one Mg atom in the center of the cell replaced with a Zn atom. Note that the computed energy includes the energy due to the interactions of the central solute with its periodic images along the line direction at a distance of c and beyond. However, DFT calculations in bulk Mg show that the Zn-Zn interaction energy at a distance of c is only about $0.01 eV$, which is negligible on the scale of the solute/dislocation interaction energies. In addition, we created a cell of thickness $2c$ and, for a solute at site 6, the difference in energy between the cells of thickness c and $2c$ is only $0.02 eV$, again negligible. We thus use Equation 4.9 with confidence. Due to symmetry, the interaction energies of sites to the right of the center of the core are equal to their symmetric counterparts on the left (indicated by identical site numbers in Figure 4.2). However, in reality, the dislocation core can move along the glide plane in response to the addition of the Zn solute. If the Zn solute has a negative interaction energy (lower energy) then the dislocation may glide toward the Zn solute position so that the Zn resides in the lowest energy position relative to the core. If the Zn solute has a positive interaction energy (higher energy) then the dislocation may glide away from the Zn solute position. In either case, if the dislocation moves, the resulting apparent interaction energy is incorrect and there is also a violation of the imposed boundary conditions that assume the dislocation remains in the center of the cell. As an example, Figure 4.3 shows the atomistic configuration and dislocation core position, which is most easily identified as the termination of an apparent extra plane of atoms in the center of the edge core, before and after relaxation when a Zn atom (blue sphere) is introduced at site 2. In the final configuration, the Zn atom is effectively at position 4 relative to the final core position. Due to the dislocation

motion, which is possible because the stresses needed to glide the prism edge dislocation are very low (a few MPa), it is not possible to directly measure many of the Zn solute/dislocation interactions energies. Among all sites in the immediate planes above and below the slip plane (sites 1-9) only Zn at sites 1, 5, 6, and 9 do not cause dislocation motion. Therefore, in all other cases, another approach must be taken to accurately measure the solute/dislocation interaction energy.

Figure 4.2: The prismatic edge core structure obtained by first principles calculation as described in section 3.1. (dotted line: slip plane; atoms colors using common neighbor analysis to differentiate core (grey) and boundary (grey) from hcp atoms (red)). The numbers label atomic sites at which the Zn/dislocation interaction energy is subsequently calculated by DFT.

Figure 4.3: Position of the edge dislocation (a) before DFT relaxation (b) after relaxation when a Zn solute has been placed at site 2. The Zn atom repels the dislocation, leading to motion of the dislocation and spurious results for the interaction energy.

We have solved the problem of the unwanted dislocation glide by adding an additional Zn solute at site 6 (the lowest energy site for Zn, with interaction energy $-0.34eV$) and correcting for interactions between the solute at site 6 and the solute at the desired position. The dislocation line is pinned due to the strong binding with the solute at site 6 and the energy cost (line tension) of becoming non-straight prevents motion or distortion of the dislocation line.

The pinning solute at site 6 enables calculation of the solute/dislocation interaction energy for solutes at other sites as

$$U(x, y) = (E_{\text{edge+Zn(site 6)+Zn}} - E_{\text{edge+Zn(site 6)}}) - (E_{\text{Mg+Zn(site 6)+Zn}} - E_{\text{Mg+Zn(site 6)}}) \quad (4.10)$$

where all structures (with and without the dislocation) contain one Zn atom at site 6. This interaction energy includes the interaction energy of the two solutes (one at site 6, the other at the desired site). For the minimum-thickness cell (Figure 4.3), the two solutes can be close in distance with significant solute-solute interactions. To reduce spurious solute-solute interactions, we use the simulation cell with periodic thickness $2c$ and place the two solutes in two different planes having interplanar distance c . The solute-solute distance is then always equal to or larger than c and the solute-solute interactions reduced significantly.

Since doubling the simulation cell size (766 atoms) incurs a very high computational cost, we have first verified the effectiveness of using a pinning solute using a newly-developed Neural Network Potential (NNP) for the Al-Cu-Mg-Zn system [68] that shows edge prism and edge basal core structures in excellent agreement with DFT calculations. Furthermore, the Zn solute/dislocation interaction energies for Zn at sites 5 and 6 as computed using the NNP are in very good agreement with the DFT values, as shown in Table 1. Doubling the cell size and introducing the additional “pinning” solute at site 6 (which is not actually necessary in studying sites 1, 5 and 6 but enables examination of the energetic effects of this second solute) leads to interaction solute/dislocation energies that remain in very good agreement with the single-solute result as shown in Table 1 for both DFT and NNP 4.1. The agreement between NNP and DFT values at site 1 is not as good as sites 5 and 6 but the small effect of the pinning solute is demonstrated. The good performance of the NNP is rather remarkable because the NNP was not developed for the Mg-Zn system and no dislocation structures of Mg, with or without Zn solutes, are contained in the dataset used to training the NNP. We do note, however, that when a Zn solute is introduced at site 9, the NNP predicts dislocation motion that is not observed in DFT. This difference may be due to the fact that the stress to move the prism edge in the NNP is very small (0.5 MPa or less) so that the NNP dislocation can move due to smaller perturbations caused by a solute. In any case, we only use the NNP to verify that the use of the pinning solute at site 6 still enables an accurate determination of the Zn/dislocation interaction energies at other sites, which are then computed by DFT.

With the above success of the NNP, we performed NNP studies of the energetic effects of adding the pinning Zn at site 6 for all solute sites in and around the core in the double-thickness cell. With the exception of site 2, the pinning solute was successful in fixing the dislocation. The pinning solute at site 6 was thus used in DFT to determine the solute/dislocation interaction energies at other sites. As an example, Figure 4.4 shows the position of the extra plane of the dislocation after DFT relaxation for a solute at site 8 with and without the pinning solute at site 6; with the pinning solute at site 6 the dislocation core remains in the correct center position in the presence of the solute at site 8. To estimate the interaction energy of Zn at site 2, we fixed

Table 4.1: Zn/edge dislocation interactions energies in eV at three sites in the core as calculated by DFT and NNP for a single solute in a super-cell with thickness c and for a single solute plus a pinning solute at site 6 in a super-cell with thickness $2c$. The effects of the pinning solute are small.

Solute Site	DFT (single solute)	DFT (pinning solute at site 6)	NNP (single solute)	NNP (pinning solute at site 6)
1	-0.05	-0.06	-0.15	-0.13
5	-0.26	-0.29	-0.27	-0.28
6	-0.34	-0.36	-0.34	-0.34

the entire row of atoms at site-type 6 during relaxation, which basically enforces symmetry. To check the accuracy of this approach, we computed the dislocation core structure of pure Mg with the atoms in site 6 held fixed and then the Zn solute interaction energy for a solute at site 5 in this constrained geometry. The difference relative to the interaction energy of site 5 as determined by the original method is only 0.004 eV.

Using the above methods, the Zn/edge dislocation interaction energy map $U(x_i, y_j)$ is shown in Figure 4.5a, with the interaction energies computed by DFT indicated by bold-outlined sites and the remaining site interaction energies computed using $-p(x_i, y_j)\Delta V$ with the pressure field of the MEAM potential. The interaction energies for Zn in the core and in the plane just above the slip plane are much larger than computed using $-p(x_i, y_j)\Delta V$, (Figure 4.5b) confirming that the detailed DFT analysis is necessary. As anticipated, these interaction energies of ± 0.34 eV are also much larger (3x) than those found for Zn in the Mg basal edge [7] and more-spatially localized, both factors that should lead to much higher solute strengthening. Other sites around the immediate core also differ from the $-p(x_i, y_j)\Delta V$ estimate but sites slightly further from the center agree well with the $-p(x_i, y_j)\Delta V$ estimate and the transition from DFT values to elasticity values is smooth. DFT calculations at sites beyond those studied here is thus not necessary.

4.3 Prediction of yield strength for Mg prism slip

The interaction energies in Figure 4.5 serve as the inputs to the solute strengthening theory along with the estimated line tension $\Gamma = 0.2 \text{ eV}/\text{\AA}$. We focus on the Mg-0.45%Zn alloy ($c=0.0045$). Following the analysis of Eqs. 4.1–4.7 in Sec 4.1, we compute the energy barrier as $\Delta E_b = 0.51 \text{ eV}$ and the zero-temperature strength as $\tau_{y_0} = 21.4 \text{ MPa}$, with the characteristic waviness scales being $\zeta_c = 147 \text{ \AA}$ and $w_c = 12.8 \text{ \AA}$ ($=4b$). The $T = 0\text{K}$ strength is not so small compared to experiments, but the barrier is not large and so the strengthening is expected to decrease rapidly with increasing temperature. Figure 4.6 shows the CRSS versus temperature of edge prism dislocation in Mg-0.45%Zn as predicted by the solute strengthening theory (Eq. 4.8) along with the experimentally measured CRSS. Over the entire temperature range,

Figure 4.4: a) Initial dislocation position, b) Dislocation motion after adding one solute at site 8 (represented by yellow color), c) Fixing the dislocation position by adding an extra pinning solute at site-6. The position of the pinning solute can be seen in the inset picture showing the cross-section of the cell.

the edge theory predictions are much lower than the experiments. Modest variations in the value of the line tension do not change the results significantly. The low predictions at low temperatures are expected since this is the domain where plastic flow is dominated by screw dislocation motion, as shown by many TEM studies. The notable under-prediction at higher temperatures (300-400K) shows, however, that edge strengthening is not the controlling factor in these dilute Mg-Zn alloys at elevated temperatures. This is the main conclusion of this paper.

4.4 Discussion and Summary

The basic application of solute strengthening of the edge dislocation fails to account for the experimental strengths at elevated temperatures. Thus, we consider further concepts, the first of which arises from our findings above.

Our DFT studies reveal very large solute/dislocation interaction energies in the core of the dislocation (Figure 4.5). These results show that there is an enormous difference between the interaction energies of adjacent atomic site on either side of the core, with the largest

Figure 4.5: Interaction energies of Zn with the prism edge dislocation. (a) DFT (bold-outlined sites) and elastic approximation $-pdv$ (all other sites), (b) Elastic approximation $-p(x_i, y_j)\Delta V$ for all sites.

Figure 4.6: Critical resolved shear stress for prism slip as a function of temperature as predicted for the prism edge dislocation and as measured experimentally [34]

difference of 0.64 eV between sites 2 and 6. This difference acts as a very large driving force for cross-core diffusion of Zn solutes from the tension to compression side of the core, only in the core region. If cross-core diffusion occurs, then the system energy is significantly lowered when the dislocation is at this position, i.e. the Zn atoms that diffuse across the core pin the dislocation. Additional stress is then required to move the dislocation away from this lower-energy environment. Such a cross-core diffusion mechanism has been shown to be the origin of dynamic strain aging, and its associated strengthening at moderate temperatures, in Al–Mg alloys where the energetic driving force is only $\sim 1/3$ that found here [123, 124]. Cross-core diffusion is a kinetic process and so depends on the migration barriers for vacancy-assisted Zn diffusion from sites such as 1, 2, 3 to sites such as 5, 6, 7 in the prism edge core. The vacancy-assisted Zn migration energy in bulk Mg is only $\sim 0.46\text{eV}$, and the large driving forces across the core are thus expected to reduce this barrier significantly and greatly accelerate

this diffusion. The migration barrier in the core can also be reduced further because of the highly distorted environment in the core. Strengthening due to cross-core diffusion then also depends on the solute concentration (how many solutes are available to diffuse per unit length of the dislocation line) and the atomistic region over which cross-core diffusion can occur on relevant time scales. So, while cross-core diffusion is guaranteed to increase the strengthening with increasing temperature, the magnitudes and temperature scales over which it operates remain to be quantitatively determined. This is the subject of the next chapter.

Another possible explanation for the experimental trends at elevated temperature is that solute strengthening of the screw dislocation supersedes the solute softening that occurs at lower temperatures. Theory developed for dilute bcc alloys [47, 48] indicates that there is a single collective solute/screw interaction energy parameter $\Delta\tilde{E}_p$, analogous to the quantity entering the edge strengthening theory, that controls both softening and strengthening as a function of temperature and solute concentration. The quantitative assessment of solute strengthening of screw dislocations thus requires knowledge of the solute/screw interaction energies around the prism screw dislocation. However, DFT results show [44] that the prism screw core in pure Mg is, at best, very weakly metastable because it can cross-slip onto the basal plane and then dissociate to achieve a low energy. Thus, the standard approach of introducing solutes into positions around the screw core is not immediately possible – many cases will simply drive the cross-slip behavior. Some DFT studies have been performed and show that certain solutes at certain positions can stabilize the prism screw core; this mainly supports mechanisms of solute softening of prism slip. Building on our recent DFT study of the prismatic screw core in pure Mg [44], we can confirm that a Zn solute in the center of the prism screw core in a cell with periodic spacing $b=a$ has an interaction energy of -0.19eV , and hence stabilizes the otherwise metastable prism screw core. Use of a solute at this position to pin the screw core, as done here for the prism edge, might then allow for the interaction energies of Zn at other sites to be computed in DFT. Another path for guidance on this mechanism would be the further application and development of the Mg-Zn NNP. A related family of Mg NNPs has recently been used to provide significant insights into the low-temperature behavior of the prism screw dislocations [44]. This is also a topic for chapter 6. In summary, the solute strengthening of the prism edge dislocation in Mg-Zn system has been studied using theory and first-principles calculations of the Zn solute/edge-dislocation interaction energies. Several algorithmic approaches to resolve operational challenges in computing the solute/dislocation interaction energies have been demonstrated, and these approaches should prove necessary and useful in many other alloy systems. However, in spite of very large solute/edge interactions within a compact prism edge core, the resulting solute strengthening at a Zn concentration of 0.0045 remains far lower than experiments. We conclude that direct strengthening of edge dislocations is not the mechanism operative in experiments at such low Zn concentrations. Two directions for future study are the evaluation of dynamic strain aging via cross-core diffusion as an additional strengthening mechanism, motivated by the very large driving force for such diffusion as computed here by DFT. Further evaluation of a softening-to-strengthening transition of the prism screw dislocation by solutes is recommended. The

further development of machine-learning potentials for Mg-Zn and other Mg alloys would facilitate direct atomistic studies of these additional phenomena, and so is also recommended.

5 Strengthening of edge prism motion by dynamic strain aging

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First-principles calculations in chapter 4 revealed very large solute/dislocation interaction energies for Zn in the prism edge core. But solute-strengthening at dilute Zn concentrations (0.5% or less) remains much smaller than the experimental CRSS for prism slip in Mg-Zn at all temperatures. The substantial difference in the interaction energies between Zn sites in the core of the dislocation just above and just below the slip plane (0.6 eV, see below) provides, however, a very strong driving force for the “cross-core” diffusion of Zn atoms from the tension side to the compression side of the dislocation core. If there is sufficient Zn and a sufficient diffusion rate, this process can lead to additional strengthening that increases with increasing temperature (due to the increase in diffusion). So, this is a possible mechanism for the observed higher-T strengthening in dilute Mg-Zn alloys. The present chapter develops the theory of cross-core diffusion for the Mg prism edge dislocation, presents relevant first-principles results for vacancy-mediated Zn diffusion in the edge core, and quantitatively determines the cross-core strengthening in Mg-0.5%Zn. Results show that the strengthening is significant, compared to the very low strength when no solute diffusion is considered, but that the strength remains 30% of the experimental value. Thus, while cross-core diffusion can be expected, it does not directly control the CRSS of prismatic slip at elevated temperatures and other mechanisms must be investigated. The remainder of the present chapter is organized as follows. In Section 5.1, the mechanism, energetics, and kinetics of the cross-core diffusion process are analyzed. The strengthening due to cross-core diffusion in Mg-Zn is calculated and compared with the experimental results in Section 5.3. We summarize our results and examine several additional possible strengthening mechanisms in Section 5.3.

5.1 Cross-core diffusion in Mg-Zn

5.1.1 Mechanism

Since solutes interact with the dislocation (see Figure 4.5), solutes prefer to reside at atomic sites with the largest negative interaction energies. There is thus a thermodynamic driving force for solutes to move from higher (less negative) energy sites to lower (more negative) energy sites. Any such motion requires vacancy-assisted diffusion, which depends on the vacancy concentration, solute migration barriers, and temperature. At low temperatures, the vacancy concentration is low and the solute migration rate is very slow so that diffusion is unable to occur during the waiting time. With increasing temperature, diffusion can occur faster, and solutes will migrate to the lower-energy sites around the dislocation. Due to the strong driving force across the core and due to reduced migration barriers in the core (see below), the dominant diffusion is “cross-core” [123] from sites on the tension side just below the glide plane to adjacent sites on the compression side (for Zn solutes in Mg). Solute diffusion from sites further from the core tends to be much slower due to the negligible driving forces and higher migration barriers [123]. Figure 5.1, derived from Figure 4.5a, shows the dominant cross-core diffusion paths in Mg-Zn and the associated energetic driving forces; sites are labeled by an integer and “top” or “bottom” relative to the glide plane. We will justify the choice of these subsets of diffusion paths later by analysis of the migration barriers.

Figure 5.1: The difference in the Zn/dislocation interaction energy Δw_n between the sites n below and above the glide plane and connected by dashed lines. Atoms are labelled by the integer n according to their lateral position away from the center of the dislocation core.

As solutes diffuse to energetically-favorable sites, the energy of the system with the dislocation in its current position is lowered. That is, the dislocation becomes increasingly pinned at its current location. There is then a larger energy barrier for dislocation motion and hence a higher stress must be applied to sustain an imposed strain rate. Since diffusion increases with increasing temperature, the alloy can be strengthened with increasing temperature. Cross-core diffusion is thus a mechanism of dynamic strain aging (DSA), and was introduced and analyzed in the context of long-standing DSA effects in fcc Al-Mg alloys [124]. Given the driving forces for cross-core diffusion of Zn in Mg, the determination of the strengthening as a function of temperature at a specified strain rate requires several steps of analysis. First, the energy change of the system (dislocation plus solutes) due to diffusion must be established. Second, the change in the stress-dependent energy barrier for dislocation motion must be determined. Third, the solute diffusion kinetics between the various sites in and around the core must be computed. Assembling these components, the net effects of cross-core diffusion on strengthening can be determined as a function of temperature and solute concentration. These steps are described in detail in the following sections.

5.1.2 Energetics

Starting from Figure 4.5, we label sites as n^{bot} and n^{top} , as shown in Figure 5.1, according to whether they are above or below the glide plane, and numbered versus lateral (glide) distance from the center of the core. The solute/dislocation interaction energy for a Zn atom at each site is then labeled as Δw_n^{top} or Δw_n^{bot} . Before any cross-core diffusion, at time $t = 0$, the energy of the system contained in an average random solute environment at solute concentration c_0 is

$$E(t = 0) = \sum_n c_0 \left(w_n^{top} + w_n^{bot} \right) \quad (5.1)$$

While dislocations actually reside in locally-favorable solute configurations, it is not feasible to consider the cross-core diffusion starting from individual local configurations. The cross-core contribution to strengthening is also fairly independent of the initial state because the solute strengthening depends on many solutes around the core (see ref [125]) – not just those in the core – and the local fluctuations of the few solutes just above and below the core is not a dominant contributor to the overall strengthening. After a time t during which solute diffusion has occurred, the solute concentrations in each site will change from c_0 to $c_n^{top}(t)$ and $c_n^{bot}(t)$. The energy of the system after cross-core diffusion for time t is then

$$E(t) = \sum_n \left[c_n^{top}(t) w_n^{top} + c_n^{bot}(t) w_n^{bot} \right] \quad (5.2)$$

The concentration evolution ($c_n^{top}(t), c_n^{bot}(t)$) of different sites will be considered in the next section. The energy landscape that determines dislocation glide is then determined, in the presence of the cross-core diffusion, by considering motion of the dislocation in increments

of one Burgers vector while the solutes remain fixed in their positions. The position of the dislocation relative to the solutes is thus changing or, conversely, the position of the solutes relative to the dislocation is changing (in the opposite direction). Glide of the dislocation by one Burgers vector shifts a solute at original site n to a new relative position $n - 2$ with respect to the dislocation core. The concentration of this site remains unchanged, but its interaction energy with the dislocation has changed by virtue of its new position relative to the dislocation. Therefore, after dislocation glide over a distance $x = mb$, the energy of the dislocation is

$$E(t, x = mb) = \sum_n \left[c_n^{top}(t) w_{n-2m}^{top} + c_n^{bot}(t) w_{n-2m}^{bot} \right] \quad (5.3)$$

After some algebra, we obtain the change in energy at time t and dislocation glide $x = mb$, relative to the initial energy at time $t = 0$, as

$$\Delta E_{xc}(t, x = mb) = E(t, x = mb) - E(0, 0) = \sum_n \left[\Delta c_n^{top}(t) w_{n-2m}^{top} + \Delta c_n^{bot}(t) w_{n-2m}^{bot} \right] \quad (5.4)$$

where $\Delta c_n^{top/bot} = c_n^{top/bot} - c_0$. Since the driving force decays with distance from the core (increasing n), the energy change is the largest (most negative) at the initial position $m = 0$. The energy change slowly increases with increasing glide distance mb until it reaches zero. At this point, there are no longer any diffused solutes inside the current position of the core – all diffused solutes have been left far behind the core and have (nearly) zero interaction energy with the core in its present position. The energy change of Equation 5.4 creates the additional barrier for dislocation motion due to cross-core diffusion. The total energy barrier is then the sum of the pre-existing random solute energy landscape with barrier ΔE_b and the additional cross-core energy barrier ΔE_{xc} . With application of an external stress τ , the total energy of the dislocation segment at time t and position $x = mb$ is

$$E(t, x = mb, \tau) = \frac{1}{2} \Delta E_b \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{\pi x}{w_c} \right) \right] + \left(\frac{\xi_c}{1.62b} \right) \Delta E_{xc}(t, x = mb) - \tau b \xi_c x \quad (5.5)$$

where 1.62 is the c/a ratio of the HCP lattice. Equation 5.5 is the basis for determining the stress-dependent and time-dependent energy barrier. We will apply Equation 5.5 at the average waiting time, $t = t_w$, of the dislocation segments. This is the average time that a segment sits in its local solute environment before it is thermally-activated to the next local minimum environment. From Orowan's Law, the waiting time at strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ is

$$t_w = \frac{2\rho_m b w_c}{\dot{\epsilon}} \quad (5.6)$$

The average waiting time, while not exact (see [124, 126]), enables efficient evaluation of the strengthening. To determine the quantitative strengthening then requires the determination of the solute concentrations $c_n^{top}(t), c_n^{bot}(t)$ as a function of time t and site n , which is discussed in the next section.

5.1.3 Kinetics

Due to the variations in solute/dislocation interaction energy versus specific position along the dislocation core, an analysis requires consideration of all individual solute diffusion paths. Figure 5.2 shows a close-up schematic of the cross-core diffusion paths considered in this study, indicated by dashed lines and where, due to symmetry, only sites to the right of the dislocation core ($n \geq 0$) are shown. This schematic is a projected view of the atomistic core along the dislocation line, and all the paths shown are between sites that can be considered as neighbors based on interatomic distance. The high distortions in the core lead to differences between “core” and “bulk” site coordination; for instance, sites 7^{bot} and 9^{top} away from the core are near neighbors in the HCP crystal structure but the seemingly-corresponding sites 1^{bot} and 3^{top} in the core are too far apart to be considered as neighbors. We consider only cross-core diffusion. Diffusion could occur in principle between neighboring sites on the same side of the slip plane but the driving forces are much smaller and the migration barriers are much closer to the (larger) bulk migration barrier; as briefly discussed in Section 5.3, including lateral paths has a negligible effect on strengthening.

Figure 5.2: Potential cross-core diffusion paths considered in this study.

For a given set of allowed diffusion paths, we use a discrete form of the master equation for the evolution of the concentrations of all sites [127]. In general, for a set of sites $\{i\}$, the master equation is a coupled system of partial differential equations describing the concentration evolution $c_i(t)$ of each site i accounting for the flux of solutes flowing into site i from neighbors $\{j\}$ with activation barriers $Q_{(j \rightarrow i)}$ and out of site i into sites $\{j\}$ with activation barriers $Q_{(i \rightarrow j)}$. Specifically, the rate of change of $c_i(t)$ is

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} = \sum_{j=1}^z \left[c_j(1 - c_i)v_0 \exp\left(-\frac{Q_{j \rightarrow i}}{k_B T}\right) - c_i(1 - c_j)v_0 \exp\left(-\frac{Q_{i \rightarrow j}}{k_B T}\right) \right] \quad (5.7)$$

where z is the number of neighbors of site i . The activation energy for diffusion is the sum of

the vacancy formation energy ΔH_{vf} and the migration barriers $E_{mig}^{j \rightarrow i}$ and $E_{mig}^{i \rightarrow j}$,

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{j \rightarrow i} &= \Delta H_{vf} + E_{mig}^{j \rightarrow i} \\ Q_{i \rightarrow j} &= \Delta H_{vf} + E_{mig}^{i \rightarrow j} \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

In this formulation, the vacancies necessary to accomplish the solute motion are implicit. We apply this formulation to all the pairs of sites where cross-core diffusion is considered, as indicated in Figure 5.2. Since vacancies also interact rather strongly with the dislocation core, the general formulation above must be adapted to consider the overall diffusion process. Such details were neglected in the original cross-core diffusion work, in part because the vacancy/dislocation interactions in Al were much smaller than we find here (see below) for the compact edge prism core in Mg. In principle, the dislocation arrives at its current location at $t = 0$ and the vacancies in the vicinity are randomly distributed with equal probability at every atomic site independent of the dislocation. Diffusion normally assumes that the probability of a vacancy at the necessary site for solute diffusion is equal to the bulk vacancy concentration; this is why the vacancy formation energy appears in the master equation. However, there are very few vacancies, and so the actual underlying assumption is that the vacancy diffusion itself is fast enough to enable vacancies to arrive adjacent to the solute so that it is suitable to use the equilibrium vacancy concentration as the probability that a vacancy is present. In actuality, the situation is better represented by the schematic in Figure 5.3 showing the overall process by which Zn solutes diffuse across the core. At $t = 0$ when the dislocation arrives at its current position, there are Zn atoms along the core and vacancies somewhere around the core (Figure 5.3a). In the first stage, a nearby vacancy will diffuse to the core, aided in part by the attractive elastic vacancy/dislocation interactions (Figure 5.3b). The vacancy migration energy in bulk Mg is $0.40 eV$, and so there is significant diffusion of existing vacancies at the temperatures of interest (e.g. at $400K$ the vacancy can make $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ random transitions in the bulk during the waiting time). The vacancy/dislocation interactions in the core are large, with DFT computations showing vacancy binding energies of $-0.44 eV$ and $-0.39 eV$ at sites 0^{top} and 1^{top} , respectively. A vacancy reaching the core will thus remain in the core, diffusing in/around the core region, and eventually arrive at a site adjacent to a Zn atom on the other side of the core (Figure 5.3c). The ‘‘cross-core’’ diffusive step corresponding to exchange of the vacancy and Zn can then occur (Figure 5.3d). However, the vacancy formation energy for sites on the other side of the core is more positive (e.g. $-0.26 eV$ at site 0^{bot} and $+0.02 eV$ at site 1^{bot}) and so the energy lowering due to the Zn binding (see Figure 5.1) is partially offset by the increase in energy due to the vacancy binding. The vacancy can then, however, diffuse to another neighboring site on the favorable (lower energy) side of the core, with a significant reduction in the system energy (Figure 5.3e). The vacancy can then move away from the Zn atom (Figure 5.3f), diffusing to other locations and facilitating further cross-core diffusion events. Binding of the vacancy/Zn pair can inhibit this last process, but this is offset by the entropy gained in enabling the vacancy to explore more sites in the core. In principle, the vacancy can also move back into the bulk Mg (away from the core) as in Figure

5.3g, but this is much less favorable due to the strong vacancy binding in the core. The net result of these diffusion processes is the “cross-core diffusion” of the Zn atom with an energy gain $\Delta w = w^{top} - w^{bot}$, independent of the vacancy energetics and diffusion. Figure 5.3h shows a schematic of the relative energies of each configuration in Figure 5.3a-g. The net cross-core driving force Δw is indicated and can be associated with the energy difference between Figures 5.3d,f or Figures 5.3a,g. The energy difference between Figures 5.3c,e differs from Δw only by the difference in vacancy-Zn binding energies in the two configurations.

Figure 5.3: a-g) Schematic representation of the sequence of atomistic configurations relevant to the cross-core diffusion process involving a vacancy, a solute, and a dislocation, h) schematic of the corresponding energies, with the net driving force Δw shown as the difference between configurations (b, f) or (a, g).

The sequence of configurations in Figure 5.3 illustrates that there are many paths by which an actual vacancy can arrive at a position adjacent to a Zn atom in the core, as the vacancy explores the system. All of the vacancy diffusion steps occurring away from the solute are assuming the existence of an initial vacancy, and are not embedded in the master equation. The assumption in the master equation is thus that there is a vacancy at the necessary site adjacent to the Zn with a probability given by the vacancy concentration $c_v = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_{vf}}{k_B T}\right)$, entering through the presence of ΔH_{vf} in the $Q_{i \rightarrow j}$ and $Q_{j \rightarrow i}$.

The initial and final states for cross-core solute migration are those in which the vacancy is remote from the Zn atom, and so can then be taken as configurations shown in Figure 5.3b and f, respectively, with the energy difference being the driving force Δw . The relevant migration barriers for cross-core diffusion (b to f) and its reverse process (f to b) are then determined by the highest energy point along the transition path from b to f that involve the Zn solute, and hence the highest point along the transition path from c to e. Due to the large decrease in

energy between configurations d and e, the controlling cross-core barrier is expected to be the step from c to d, corresponding to the motion of the Zn atom. The reverse barrier from f to b will differ by Δw and so will automatically satisfy detailed balance (which is embedded in the master equation). We use the Nudge Elastic Band (NEB) method in DFT to compute the transition paths between configurations c and d using 5 intermediate images. Chapter 3 provides details of the dislocation construction method, size, and energy minimization used. A vacancy and Zn atom are introduced into the relaxed simulation cell, and further ionic relaxations are performed holding all ions within 4 atomic planes of the outer boundaries fixed at the relaxed dislocation-only configuration while periodic boundary conditions are maintained along the dislocation line. Initial and final states for the NEB calculation are obtained by relaxing all other ions until all forces are below $10 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}$ and electronic degrees of freedom are converged at $10 - 8 \text{ eV}$. During the NEB calculation, the Minimum Energy Path (MEP) is found by minimizing the true ionic forces on each image perpendicular to the path and the spring forces between the images along the path in order to keep the images equi-distant. The transition state is the highest energy state along the MEP. The transition state is a saddle point at which both perpendicular and parallel components of the ionic force should vanish. Here, we use the NEB algorithm in VASP but use the two convergence criteria of perpendicular and total ionic force both below $10 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}$ in the transition state replica. NEB calculations were performed for Zn-Vacancy exchange among the pairs of sites shown in Figure 5.4a with the corresponding barrier energies indicated. The Minimum Energy Paths for these transitions are shown in Figure 5.4b. A number of these cross-core paths have very low ($< 0.1 \text{ eV}$) migration barriers due to a combination of the distorted core environment and the net driving force for the transition. Thus, cross-core diffusion in these paths is very fast relative to bulk diffusion. We note in Figure 5.4b that the energy differences between initial and final states (configurations c and d in Figure 5.3) for paths near the core remains fairly small because of the competition between Zn and vacancy binding energies in the core. Paths such as $1^{bot} - 0^{top}$ and $1^{bot} - 2^{top}$ are between sites in different atomic planes with atomic distances of $\sim 3.6 \text{\AA}$ that are much larger than other pairs (e.g. the atomic distance for $1^{bot} - 1^{top}$ is 3.03\AA) so we expect these barriers to be significantly larger than 0.2 eV . For instance, although not shown in Figure 5.4, the path $3^{bot} - 5^{top}$ (with distance 3.9\AA) has an NEB-computed migration barrier of 0.49 eV in spite of the large driving force, and we expect path $1^{bot} - 3^{top}$ to be similar and so diffusion between these pairs is neglected. Then, for those paths shown in Figure 5.4a with dashed black lines that also have distances greater than the bulk distance, and paths further from the core (not shown), are assigned the bulk migration barrier $E_{mig}^{bulk} = 0.38 \text{ eV}$ for migration along the basal plane. Paths $4^{bot} - 4^{top}$, $6^{bot} - 6^{top}$, and $8^{bot} - 8^{top}$ (represented by red dashed lines) have distances less than the bulk interatomic distance but are further from the core than $2^{bot} - 2^{top}$ and with negligible driving force so their barriers are most likely higher than 0.2 eV ; we use the value 0.26 eV that is the average of the forward and reverse barriers for path $2^{bot} - 2^{top}$. Analysis and testing show that the final results for cross-core strengthening are not sensitive to the precise values of these higher-barrier paths. Therefore, due to high computational cost, we did not compute precise values. Two cases, $3^{bot} - 3^{top}$ and $9^{bot} - 9^{top}$, did not reach our convergence criterion for the total ionic force near the transition

state, reaching only $\sim 25 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}$ after 60 iterations. However, in both cases, the image near the transition state had perpendicular forces well below $10 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}$ indicating that the image is along the MEP. Thus the estimated barrier using this image is a lower bound to the true barrier. Since the barriers in these two cases were 0.06 and 0.30 eV , and the change in total energy with increasing the number of iterations were negligible compared to these values, we did not attempt to converge these transition state images further.

Figure 5.4: a) Cross-core diffusion paths considered, with initial “bottom” states (Figure 5.3c) and final “top” states (figure 5.3f). Orange dashed lines represent the paths with DFT calculated barriers. Dashed red lines represent barriers for paths assumed to be the average value of the barriers along the forward and backward direction of path $2^{bot} - 2^{top}$. The barriers of the paths shown by black dashed lines are assumed to be the bulk barrier, 0.39 eV . b) Minimum Energy Path versus NEB image/replica, for the cross-core paths shown by the dashed orange lines in (a) and for bulk migration.

5.2 Results

In the previous section, we computed the migration barriers for cross-core diffusion, and so we can now calculate the concentration evolutions of $c_n^{top}(t)$, $c_n^{bot}(t)$ using the framework of

Equation 5.7. Then, using Equation 5.5, we can calculate the energy landscape for dislocation glide versus time. We determine the yield strength using the concentration changes at the waiting time t_w . The details and results are as follows.

For the prism edge dislocation in Mg-0.45%Zn, with a typical dislocation density in a well-annealed crystal of $\rho_m = 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and at typical experimental strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the average waiting time is $t_w = 0.0049 \text{ s}$. Equation 5.7 is thus solved numerically for 112 sites (112 equations) located to the right and left sides of the dislocation center, on both bottom and top sites along the slip plane for this waiting time. The initial conditions are solute concentration $c_i = 0.0045$ for all sites. Figure 5.5 shows the concentration profiles $c_n^{top}(t_w)$, $c_n^{bot}(t_w)$ for different temperatures. The equilibrium vacancy concentration is also shown for each temperature using $\Delta H_{vf} = 0.79 \text{ eV}$.

At $T = 300 \text{ K}$, no cross-core diffusion is observed because the vacancy concentration is too low (the cross-core migration barriers in the core being so low that vacancy concentration dominates the rate). Noticeable diffusion begins at $T = 350 \text{ K}$ where Zn solutes are diffusing from bottom to top sites near the center of the core where the migration barriers are very low (odd numbered pairs of sites). At $T = 400 \text{ K}$, the concentration of site 1^{top} is twice the initial concentration as a result of complete diffusion of all solutes at site 1^{bot} into site 1^{top} . At $T = 450 \text{ K}$, the diffusion into nearby top sites (odd numbers) also reaches the maximum values while some diffusion along other paths with higher migration barriers (sites labeled with even numbers) begins. At $T = 500 \text{ K}$, there is more extensive diffusion, with activation of paths such as $4^{bot} - 4^{top}$.

Figure 5.6 shows the total energy landscapes $E(t, x = mb, \tau = 0)$ computed using Equation 5.5 at the waiting time and under zero stress, for different temperatures as derived from the concentration fields shown in Figure 5.5. The total energy consists of the initial solute strengthening contribution plus the additional contribution due to cross-core diffusion contribution $\Delta E_{xc}(t, x = mb)$, which is also shown separately as the red curve. With increasing temperature, the energy at the initial dislocation position $x = 0$ decreases steadily due to the increasing cross-core diffusion. The effect of the cross-core diffusion extends out to dislocation glide distances of $\sim 2w_c$ but the main energy lowering is in the regime $x < 1.5w_c$.

For plastic flow to occur, the stress must be sufficiently large to drive the system to lower total energy when the dislocation has moved to the next local minimum solute environment at typical distance $2w_c$. At any lower stress, if the dislocation glides by thermally-activation over the barrier to the next local minimum, the barrier for the reverse motion, returning the dislocation to the initial state, is smaller and the dislocation will rapidly return to the initial state. The net rate of plastic deformation at temperature T is then the difference between the glide rates in the forward and reverse directions, with energy barriers E_b^f and E_b^r respectively,

Figure 5.5: Solute concentration profiles after cross-core diffusion over the dislocation waiting time t_w versus site n in the core (top sites in blue, bottom sites in red), for increasing temperatures as indicated. The equilibrium vacancy concentration at each temperature is also shown.

so that

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_0 \left[\exp\left(-\frac{E_b^f(T, \tau)}{k_B T}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{E_b^r(T, \tau)}{k_B T}\right) \right] \quad (5.9)$$

Using Equation 5.5, the barriers E_b^f and E_b^r , evident in Figure 5.6, are computed as a function of temperature. At the specified strain rate, the shear stress at which Equation 5.9 is satisfied is the yield stress (CRSS). As an example, Figure 8 shows the energy landscapes at $T = 450\text{K}$ for increasing applied stresses. At the experimental strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the shear yield stress at $T = 450\text{K}$ is 4.4 MPa.

Calculations of the yield stress versus temperature at $\dot{\epsilon} = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ are shown in Figure 5.8. At low temperatures, there is no cross-core diffusion, and the strength is due solely to static solute strengthening, and is well below experiments. At $T = 350\text{K}$ and above, the cross-core diffusion leads to non-negligible strengthening that shows a saturation of $\tau_y \sim 4.5 \text{ MPa}$ versus

Figure 5.6: Energy versus dislocation glide distance (in units of b) due to cross-core diffusion at the waiting time t_w and under zero stress, for different temperatures (blue lines); the contribution due to cross-core diffusion alone is shown as the red line.

temperature up to $T = 500\text{K}$. The cross-core diffusion of Zn solutes at a concentration of 0.0045, while non-negligible, is thus not sufficient to explain the experimentally-measured strength. This is the main conclusion of the present chapter.

The apparent increasing strength with increasing temperature for $300\text{K} < T < 400\text{K}$, which is equivalent to an apparent negative strain rate sensitivity, is an artifact of fixing the dislocation waiting time. Theory (see [126]) shows that the strain rate sensitivity can never be negative due solely to cross-core diffusion of mobile dislocations. Hence, the true behavior will be a plateau in strength at $\sim 4.5\text{ MPa}$ over an extended temperature range including below $T < 400\text{K}$. The full calculation is, however, not computationally feasible and, since it does not affect our main conclusion, we have not attempted to execute it.

Figure 5.7: Energy versus glide distance, after cross-core diffusion over the waiting time, for different applied stresses at $\dot{\epsilon} = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ and $T = 450K$. Plastic flow occurs when the net rate of motion matches the strain rate (see Equation 5.9), requiring $> 4 MPa$ under these conditions.

5.3 Discussion

We have studied the cross-core diffusion of Zn solutes on the strength of the prism edge dislocation in Mg, motivated by the very large energetic driving force computed by first-principles DFT (Figure 5.1). In addition to a large driving force, the migration barriers for cross-core diffusion of Zn in the core are found to be very small (Figure 5.4), enabling cross-core diffusion to occur very easily in the presence of a vacancy. However, the vacancy concentration remains very low at $T = 300K$ and below and greatly limits cross-core diffusion during the dislocation waiting time, leading to no strengthening. At temperatures $T = 350K$ and above, the Zn solute diffusion becomes fast enough to create strengthening but the strengthening saturates at $\sim 4.5 MPa$, lower than the experimental strength of $\sim 25 MPa$ at $T = 425K$. Thus, while cross-core diffusion can operate at these temperatures, the Zn concentration of 0.0045 remains too low to create the strengthening observed in experiments. In this study, we did not consider lateral diffusion between sites located on the same side of the slip plane. These additional diffusion paths could lead to higher solute concentrations at the lowest solute binding sites ($0^{top}, 1^{top}$), leading to further lowering of the dislocation energy and increasing of the CRSS. However, repeating our analysis by including additional lateral paths $0^{top} - 1^{top}$ ($E_{mig} = 0.22eV, \Delta w = -0.08eV$) $2^{top} - 1^{top}$ ($E_{mig} = 0.14eV, \Delta w = -0.16eV$), and $2^{top} - 0^{top}$ ($E_{mig} = 0.22eV, \Delta w = -0.16eV$) with optimistically low migration barriers estimated as $E_{mig} = 0.30 + \Delta w$ increases the strength by only $\sim 2 MPa$. Furthermore, these paths would only be activated at $T > 400K$. It is also possible that the real solute/dislocation interaction energies

Figure 5.8: Yield strength versus temperature, as measured (red) and as predicted by solute strengthening plus cross-core diffusion (green). The contribution due to solute strengthening is shown as the blue line.

could be higher than computed by DFT, leading to higher strengths, but repeating our analysis with solute/dislocation interaction energy of sites 0^{top} and 1^{top} by increased by $0.1eV$ results in a negligible $0.02eV$ increase in the total energy barrier. Finally, the vacancy concentration could be larger if the vacancy formation free energy is lower than the $T = 0K$ value used here. However, this would mainly shift the temperature range of cross-core diffusion to slightly lower temperatures without significant change in the magnitude of the strengthening. Since strengthening by cross-core diffusion does not reach values comparable to experiments, we here briefly assess other possible strengthening mechanisms. With a low Zn migration barrier, Zn diffusion at higher temperatures might enable the operation of solute drag of the prism edge dislocation. Solute drag is due to the formation of a steady-state solute cloud that trails a steadily-moving dislocation, and is controlled more by the solute cloud outside of the core than by cross-core diffusion. Data on Al-0.0052Mg [127], with a similar concentration and bulk diffusion activation energy (vacancy formation plus migration of $1.28eV$) as Mg-0.0045Zn, shows strengthening of 5-10 MPa at $T = 600K$. It is thus valuable to estimate solute drag strengthening in Mg-Zn. We use results of Zhang et al. [127], who used the Master Equation for discrete diffusion around an FCC edge dislocation core described by a Peierls-Nabarro model with core-spreading parameter of $\zeta = 1.5b$. This value is close to the core spreading of $\zeta = 1.6b$ derived from the Mg prism edge structure shown in Figure 4.2. James and Barnett [128] had previously used a continuum model for the same problem. Zhang et al. [127] found the maximum solute drag strengthening to be $\tau_{max} \cong 0.5c \frac{\mu}{3\pi} \frac{1+\nu}{1-\nu} \left(\frac{\delta v}{v_a} \right)$ where δv and v_a are the solute misfit volume and atomic volume, respectively, in a material with shear modulus μ and Poisson's ratio ν . James and Barnett showed the same scaling but with a

pre-factor of 0.25. Using the material values for Mg-0.0045Zn, the maximum solute drag strengthening is estimated as 2.5 MPa. This strength remains well below the experiments. Therefore, independent of the strain rate at which this maximum strengthening occurs, the solute drag mechanism is unlikely to be responsible for the observed strengthening of Mg-Zn at high temperatures. With screw dislocations controlling the stress at low temperatures [3, 4] it is also possible that there is a dynamic strain aging phenomenon related to Zn diffusion in the screw dislocation core. Normally DSA is not associated with screw dislocations because there is no long-range pressure field to attract solutes. However, solute/screw interactions in the core exist and can drive local segregation. We have performed first-principles calculations of the interaction energy of Zn with the prism screw core; DFT details are the same as those used for the edge core. The Zn/screw interaction energies are shown in Figure 6.2. Unlike for the basal or prism edge dislocations, all of these interaction energies are negative. Furthermore, there is a large interaction energy of -0.27eV for Zn in the central site in the core and of $\sim -0.15\text{eV}$ for several other sites near the center of the core. At higher temperatures, “near-core” solute diffusion could increase the stress required for screw motion. An analysis of the cross-core diffusion of screw dislocation in Mg-Zn is well beyond the scope of the present chapter, but the results here provide an initial quantitative basis on which possible mechanisms can be studied in the future.

6 Solute-induced softening of prism screw

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The investigations in the preceding chapters revealed that the glide of screw dislocations predominantly governs the strength throughout the temperature range. Therefore, it is concluded that both low-temperature softening and high-temperature strengthening result from the interaction of solutes with the glide of screw dislocations.

The transition from softening to strengthening indicates a thermally activated behavior, where the interaction mechanism between solutes and the glide of screw dislocations undergoes a fundamental change as temperature rises. To comprehensively understand the influence of solutes on prismatic slip across all temperature ranges, it is crucial to uncover the underlying mechanisms responsible for low-temperature softening and to determine why this effect diminishes with increasing temperature.

The slip mechanism for pure Mg at low temperatures is not fully understood. In situ microscopy experiments [5] show that in the low-temperature regime screw dislocations glide in a jerky fashion, characterized by intermittent rapid slipping on the prism plane over several Burgers vectors, followed by abrupt halts. However, at higher temperatures, the dislocation glide is viscous. These observations necessitate a thorough investigation of the potential impacts of solutes on such different behaviors.

Since, as shown by first-principles calculations [45], the prism screw is unstable or only weakly meta-stable on the prismatic plane relative to the basal screw, it is widely believed that prismatic slip occurs through a sequence of cross-slip events: the basal screw dislocation cross-slips onto the prism plane, transforming into a prism screw dislocation, and then reverts to the basal screw configuration either at the next basal plane or after gliding on the prism plane for several Burgers vectors. The former scenario is thought to occur at higher temperatures,

where viscous motion is observed, while the latter dominates at lower temperatures, where jerky motion is characteristic.

This chapter aims to understand the potential effects of solutes on both low-temperature and high-temperature regimes. Initially, first-principles methods will be employed to examine the effects of solutes on the stability of the prism screw core in two dimensions (infinite dislocation length). Subsequently, a Neural Network Potential (NNP) will be developed to study the impact of solutes on more complex three-dimensional prismatic slip mechanisms, such as kink-pair and single-kink processes. Finally, the chapter will introduce a novel mechanism to explain the experimentally observed softening at low temperatures.

6.1 Solute effects on the stability of prism screw

Before exploring complex three-dimensional mechanisms such as kink-pair and single-kink, it is essential to first understand how solutes impact the stability of the prism screw dislocation. In pure Mg, the stability of the prism core against dissociation onto the basal plane has long been a subject of controversy. Initially, the observation of jerky motion via in-situ TEM studies [5] led to the hypothesis that the prism screw is meta-stable on the prismatic plane, which was thought to explain the extended glide distances on this plane. However, subsequent atomistic studies utilizing DFT and interatomic potentials have yielded mixed outcomes; the MEP for basal-prism-basal cross-slip calculated by DFT and accurate interatomic potentials show that the prism core is unstable or it shows very flat surface close to the prism core [44, 45, 129], while in [45, 129] it is also reported that the full relaxation of the prism core can lead to stability. This ambiguity in understanding the stability of the prism screw complicates the investigation of solute effects on prismatic slip, adding layers of subtlety to the analysis.

Liu et al. [44] employed several NNPs for NEB calculations to determine the minimum energy path for basal-prism-basal cross-slip. Their findings indicated that the prism core is unstable across all NNPs used. We adopted their transition configuration, obtained by one of their NNPs (NNP77), which aligns more closely with DFT data, added Zn to certain sites, and relaxed the structure using DFT. The parameters for this relaxation is the same as discussed in Chapter 3 for Mg edge prism. This structure corresponds to the lattice and elastic constants of NNP77 and not obtained by DFT. However we used it to explore the effects of zinc at different atomic sites in the core under the same conditions. Additionally, the lattice parameters of NNP77 differ from those obtained by DFT by less than 0.5%.

Figure 6.1 displays the initial structures (left) derived from NEB calculations using NNP77, and after DFT relaxation (right) with one Zn solute at two different sites (highlighted by red circle) within the core. During DFT relaxation, the two outer layers at the boundary were kept fixed, and a vacuum layer of 10 Å thickness was employed. Although these small-sized super-cells may not be ideal for highly accurate calculations, they are sufficient to investigate whether Zn aids in stabilizing the core and to compare the effects of Zn at different locations. The two sites were specifically chosen in the middle row of the core to take advantage of the core's

symmetric structure and to inhibit basal dissociation as much as possible. For the Zn site depicted in Figure 6.1a, relaxation leads to basal cross-slip; the relaxation was stopped at the onset of dissociation. In contrast, positioning Zn at the site shown in Figure 6.1b results in a stable dislocation after complete relaxation. Upon achieving a stable core configuration, we calculated the interaction energy between Zn and the screw dislocation at this site, which is found to be -0.27 eV. This highly negative value demonstrates the stabilizing influence of Zn at this specific site, potentially indicating the initial signs for softening.

As discussed in Chapter 4, we now designate the stabilizing site in Figure 6.1b as the pinning position for the solute, enabling us to calculate the interactions between Zn and screw dislocation at other sites. Similarly to the edge case, we use a super-cell with double thickness ($2b$) to minimize solute-solute interactions as much as possible. The super-cell used for the calculation of interaction energies is shown in Figure 6.1a. The interaction energy values calculated for sites inside the black hexagonal are indicated in Figure 6.1b. For the other sites we did not calculate the interaction energy as they are nearly approaching zero. In addition to color-map, we also labeled the sites with numbers corresponding to their interaction energy values. It is seen that the pinning solute indeed has the highest negative interaction energy among all other sites. There are also a few high energy sites with interaction energies of about -0.15 , and -0.17 eV. Overall it is seen that all the sites has negative (attraction) interaction energies pointing towards stabilizing effect. However it should also be noted that in the basal-prism cross slip, the solute/basal interaction is also important because a site might be more negative in the basal core than the prism core which then makes the basal-prism cross-slip even harder.

6.2 Training of an NNP for Mg-Zn

To gain a clearer understanding of the prismatic slip process, we developed an NNP for the Mg-Zn system. This NNP focuses on the properties of prismatic slip, enabling detailed studies of the prismatic slip process in large three-dimensional structures. This potential was developed based on the previous NNP trained for Al-Mg-Zn-Cu system [68]. We used the same symmetry functions and the same neural network architecture for training the potential. We selected all relevant training data from the Al-Mg-Zn-Cu system that include Mg and Zn, supplementing it with our DFT calculations on edge and screw dislocations. Additionally, we incorporated DFT data on the effect of Zn within stacking faults across different Mg slip systems. The original Mg-Zn database consisted of 1,288 structures, to which we added 245 new data entries focused on dislocation and stacking faults.

All DFT calculations for dislocation studies were initially conducted using VASP. However, to maintain consistency with the previously developed NNP [68], which was based on data prepared with Quantum ESPRESSO, we recalculated all relevant data using Quantum ESPRESSO. To ensure compatibility with the original dataset, we applied exactly the same DFT parameters as detailed in [68].

The original dataset primarily covered bulk structures across various crystal systems, Mg-Zn

Figure 6.1: DFT relaxation of screw prism core with one Zn solute at two different sites in the core. a) Relaxation leads to basal dissociation, b) prism core is stable. The thickness of the cell along the periodic direction is $1b$ as shown in the inset. The initial core is adopted from the transition state replica of 2d NEB calculations in ref [44]. Two outer layers are kept fixed during the relaxation.

intermetallics with different compositions, and some distorted configurations. The added structures, however, often involve large super-cells with over 300 atoms each. While our additions account for a modest increase in the number of structures, they significantly increase the total atom count—91,683 atoms in the augmented dataset compared to 11,929 in the original. The inclusion of these large super-cells may bias the training toward accurately modeling configurations with dislocations and stacking faults, which is beneficial given our focus on Zn's effect on dislocation behavior. With the choice of new DFT parameters and pseudopotentials, properties such as lattice parameters and elastic constants may show slight variations compared to the VASP data as shown in Table 6.1. However, this has minimal impact on our analysis, as it does not rely on the exact numerical values of these properties. Additionally, for training the NNP, we require the energies and forces for all structures, regardless of whether they are fully relaxed or not. The most crucial feature of a well-trained potential is its ability to accurately predict key bulk properties of a material. Figure 6.3 shows the predictions of the newly trained NNP for lattice parameters, elastic constants, basal stacking fault energy, and

Figure 6.2: a) Super-cell used for calculation of Zn/screw dislocation interaction energy, with the pinning solute position highlighted as red circle. The thickness of the cell is also shown in the inset. b) The interaction values calculated by DFT method for the sites within the hexagonal surrounding the core, shown by solid black line.

Table 6.1: Comparison of lattice parameters in (Å) and elastic constants in GPa, obtained using VASP and Quantum ESPRESSO (QE).

Method	a	c/a	C11	C12	C13	C33	C44
VASP	3.190	1.627	61	28	22	64	18
QE	3.193	1.625	63	25	21	65	18

prismatic unstable stacking fault energy of pure HCP Mg. These properties must be within an acceptable range for simulation of prismatic slip and basal-prism cross slip in dilute Mg-Zn alloys. It is seen that overall the NNP is able to predict the properties in close agreement with DFT and also it is performing better than the NNP developed for Al-Mg-Cu-Zn system[68]. The relatively higher errors in the elastic constants, compared to lattice parameters, are typical. Elastic constants are related to the second derivative of the energy, making them more sensitive to errors in the potential. The stacking fault energy of the basal dislocation plays a critical role here, as the most energetically demanding step in basal-prism cross-slip is the constriction of the dissociated basal dislocation—a process heavily influenced by the stacking fault energy. This parameter was therefore the most important criterion in selecting the current NNP among the series of potentials we trained.

Figure 6.3: Deviation of NNP from DFT reference values (%) for lattice constants, elastic constants, stable and unstable stacking fault energies for basal and prismatic slip, respectively. The DFT properties are calculated by QE.

To further evaluate the accuracy of the NNP in modeling prismatic slip in Mg, Figure 6.4 shows the comparison between NNP and DFT calculations for the energy difference across a series of structures interpolated linearly between basal and prism dislocation configurations. The endpoints were relaxed using DFT, while the NNP was used to compute the energies of these exact same structures without allowing them to relax to their equilibrium states. The prism core (replica 8) is stable during ionic relaxation by DFT [44, 45]. It is important to emphasize that this plot does not represent an MEP, and therefore it does not provide the true energy barrier for the transition between basal and prism states. Instead, it serves as a benchmark to assess the consistency of NNP in capturing energy variations across these interpolated configurations. The agreement between NNP and DFT is promising, though the energy drop from Replica 6 to Replica 8 is more pronounced in the NNP calculations. This discrepancy may have implications for the stability and behavior of the prism core under specific conditions, as discussed below.

Figure 6.5 shows the MEP for basal-prism-basal cross-slip obtained from a NEB calculation using the NNP. This is a two-dimensional calculation with a thickness along the periodic direction set to $1b$. It is seen that the energy difference between the prism core and basal core is close to DFT value— 0.67 meV/b as opposed to 0.62 meV/b from DFT. However, the NNP curve exhibits a distinct local minimum at the prism core, which introduces a barrier for the prism-to-basal cross-slip. This finding contrasts with previous NEB-DFT results [45, 129], where no local minimum was observed along the MEP, even with a low force threshold of 1 meV/Å. One possible explanation for the pronounced meta-stability in the NNP could be the inclusion of numerous large super-cells with stabilized screw cores due to the presence of Zn in the training data, which may have biased the NNP model.

Figure 6.4: The energy difference between the linear interpolated configurations starting basal to prism. The structures are obtained by DFT relaxation of the end points [44, 45]. The prism core (replica 8) is stable under the relaxation.

Figure 6.5: The MEP for basal-prism-basal cross-slip in 2d calculated by NNP. The configuration of some of the replicas are also shown colored by their CNA analysis, where green represents FCC regions, blue represents BCC, red indicates HCP, and light gray denotes atoms with undefined structure.

The meta-stability of a configuration can also be analyzed by generalized stacking fault energy (GSFE) curves. Figure 6.6a shows the GSFE curve for prismatic plane along $\frac{a}{3}[11\bar{2}0]$ direction calculated by NNP and DFT. The agreement between NNP and DFT is very good. Also, consistent with various DFT and interatomic potential calculations, there is no indication of a local minimum along the curve. However, the GSFE curve along $\frac{a}{6}[11\bar{2}0] + c[0001]$ shows a very shallow local minimum at point $\frac{a}{6}[11\bar{2}0] + 0.05c[0001]$. This minimum has been reported by Yasi et al [8, 130] using PAW pseudopotentials, based on which they concluded that the prism core is indeed meta-stable.

Figure 6.6: The GSFE curve for the prismatic plane along a) $\frac{a}{3}[11\bar{2}0]$, and b) $\frac{a}{6}[11\bar{2}0] + c[0001]$. A local minimum can be seen in (b) at point $\frac{a}{6}[11\bar{2}0] + 0.05c[0001]$

For finite temperatures, the prism-basal cross-slip barrier observed with the NNP is very shallow, suggesting that it has minimal impact. For instance, in our molecular dynamics (MD) simulation at low temperature of 50 K, the prism-to-basal cross-slip occurred within only 7 ps. Nevertheless, this observed meta-stability could have implications at 0 K, and one needs to be careful when interpreting the results.

Another key property of interest for us is the interaction energy between Zn atoms and the screw dislocation in Mg, as this interaction plays a critical role in determining the effect of

Zn on the prismatic slip. Figure 6.7 compares the Zn/screw dislocation interaction energy maps obtained from the newly trained NNP and DFT calculations for identical super-cell configurations. The DFT interaction energy maps were generated using VASP, as described in the previous section.

Figure 6.7: Zn/screw interaction energy maps obtained by a)NNP and b)DFT

The comparison reveals that the NNP performs well in predicting the high-energy interaction sites with close alignment to the DFT values. This alignment is particularly important because accurately identifying high-energy sites is essential for understanding solute-dislocation interactions, which directly affect the ease of cross-slip, the pinning and mobility of dislocations and kinks. These interactions are key factors in controlling prismatic slip behavior in dilute Mg-Zn alloys. One of the key contributors of the interaction energy is the elastic interaction energy, which is usually determined, as discussed in Chapter 3, by calculating the solute misfit volume in the matrix. The misfit volume of the Zn in Mg calculated by NNP is -0.425 which is close to DFT value of -0.467 [121]. Table 6.2 shows the maximum values for the interaction energy of Zn with prism edge, basal edge, and basal screw. While NNP is close to DFT for prism edge, it predicts too strong values for both basal edge and screw. As basal screw play the key role in the prismatic slip in Mg, we need to also consider this too strong Zn/screw interaction energy value in our interpretations of any simulations. In summary, the new NNP demonstrates high accuracy in capturing the key bulk properties of pure Mg, as well as providing reliable predictions for the energy differences between prism screw and basal screw dislocations. Additionally, it yields interaction energy values for Zn in the prism screw core that are in close agreement with DFT calculations. However, the NNP also indicates a weak meta-stability for the prism core and shows stronger Zn/basal screw interaction energies, both of which are significant factors that must be considered during simulations and when interpreting results.

It is challenging to calculate the interaction energies for all the sites in the screw basal dislocation because it has very low Peierls stress and moves in the presence of the solute along the slip plane until the solute is in the site with the highest attractive interaction energy. However, we found that in a dislocation loop, which will be discussed in the following sections, the screw component - primarily consisting of dissociated basal dislocations - remains fixed on the basal plane, allowing us to measure the interaction energies for all atomic sites. Figure 6.8a

Table 6.2: Comparison of maximum Zn/dislocation interaction energy for different dislocations obtained using NNP and DFT. All values are in eV.

	Prism edge	Basal edge	Basal screw
DFT	-0.34	0.13	-0.07
NNP	-0.35	0.22	-0.13

shows the CNA-colored core of the basal dislocation obtained via relaxation of a periodic two-dimensional cell of pure Mg and Figure 6.8b is the cross-section of the basal core formed within the loop. The core configuration is not exactly the same as that shown in Figure 6.8a, because it is part of a small dislocation loop. For example, it clearly has a shorter stacking fault region. Despite these differences, the interaction energies at various sites in the core (Figure 6.8c) still follows the same anti-symmetric trend previously reported by Yasi et al. [130], albeit with a higher maximum energy of -0.15 eV.

In the following sections, we will use the newly developed NNP for investigating the effects of Zn on kink-pair mechanism, single-kink mechanism, and loop expansion.

Figure 6.8: CNA of the cross-section of the core of a basal dislocation formed at a) 2d periodic relaxation and b) the screw component of a dislocation loop. c) Zn/screw basal interaction energy map as calculated for the core shown in (b). CNA is shown with green representing FCC, blue BCC, red HCP, and gray undefined structure.

6.3 Kink-pair mechanism

6.3.1 Pure Mg

The kink-pair (jog-pair) mechanism has been proposed as an explanation for the glide of screw dislocations in pure Mg at high temperatures. Although the exact occurrence of this mechanism is still under debate, it is nonetheless valuable to explore and understand the potential effects of solutes on this mechanism. Since this mechanism is thought to operate in the temperature regime where solute-induced softening diminishes, understanding the effect

of solutes on the kink-pair mechanism could provide valuable insights into the transition from softening to strengthening that occurs across different temperatures. In addition, by studying the kink-pair mechanism in the presence of solutes, we can better understand whether solutes hinder or facilitate kink formation and mobility, which is directly linked to dislocation glide behavior. This insight can reveal how solutes interact with dislocation in different temperatures, providing a clearer picture of the mechanisms driving material softening at low temperatures and why that same mechanism might no longer operate or even reverse at higher temperatures.

One of the key pieces of information required to gain a clear understanding of a mechanism is its activation enthalpy. By determining the activation enthalpy, we can predict the ease with which kinks form/glide and how the solutes influence them. To achieve this, we initially performed an NEB calculation for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip, using a linear interpolation as the starting path for the relaxation. However, we found that this linear interpolation approach resulted in the complete transformation of the basal dislocation into the prism screw without forming kinks—essentially replicating the two-dimensional scenario depicted in Figure 6.5, but for a longer dislocation segment. We repeated the same calculation for various dislocation lengths, ranging from 100 Å up to a considerably long length of 500 Å, with all of these configurations yielding the same outcome. This outcome is clearly not representative of the true MEP, as the energy barrier for this mechanism becomes directly proportional to the dislocation length. Essentially, the energy barrier for the two-dimensional process (Figure 6.5) is multiplied by the total number of Burgers vector lengths along the dislocation line. For example for the dislocation with length 500 Å the barrier is about 11 eV which is huge. This issue may stem from the presence of a local minimum in the energy landscape, as observed in the energy profile of the two-dimensional simulations (Figure 6.5).

The prism core is locally stable, causing the spring forces employed in the NEB calculations to be insufficient for pulling the replica out of its local energy basin. In such cases, methods for global path optimization can be employed, such as those described in [131], where the optimal path is identified using finite temperature techniques like simulated annealing. These methods are effective in escaping local minima by introducing thermal fluctuations that help to explore the energy landscape more comprehensively. However, due to the complexity and the significant computational cost involved — particularly given the large cells containing more than 300,000 atoms — we chose not to utilize these approaches in this study.

Instead, we utilized a path for the kink-pair mechanism that was previously obtained using another NNP for pure Mg, referred to as NNP63 [42]. NNP63 predicts an energy barrier of 1.6 eV for the kink-pair mechanism. Importantly, unlike the barrier observed in our linear interpolation method, the energy barrier for the kink-pair mechanism is not dependent on dislocation length. This is because the mechanism involves the nucleation of two kinks and the subsequent kink-kink interaction, which diminishes to zero once the kinks are separated by a certain distance.

To determine the MEP for the kink-pair mechanism using our newly developed NNP, we began by performing an NEB calculation with NNP63 to generate initial replicas. We used the fixed boundary condition method in a cylinder with a radius of 150 Å and length of 100 Å (approximately 309,000 atoms). The initial basal dislocation was obtained by relaxing the Volterra dislocation, while the final state required introducing approximate displacements to the core atoms and relaxing them to avoid the second inconsistent cut-plane. The replicas from the NNP63 NEB calculation were then rescaled to match our NNP's lattice parameters, followed by endpoint relaxation and a subsequent NEB calculation using 36 replicas. The resulting MEP is presented in Figure 6.9.

The MEP (Figure 6.9) begins with the constriction observed in Replica 10, followed by cross-slip to the prism plane (Replicas 11-12), and a subsequent cross-slip back to the basal plane (Replicas 13-14). Finally, the kinks separate, allowing the entire dislocation line to transition to the next adjacent basal plane over a distance of $c/2$. The calculated energy barrier is 1.5 eV, which is in good agreement with the NNP63 barrier of 1.6 eV (Figure 1.7b), and NNP77 barrier of 1.47 eV [12]. The transition state (Replica 17) features basal segments located on two planes, connected by two kinks. The length of the second basal segment in the transition state is about $16b$, which is also close to previously developed NNPs for pure Mg [12].

The activation energy of 1.5 eV is nearly twice the experimentally deduced barrier of approximately 0.8 ± 0.1 eV at 300K. To address this discrepancy, the single-kink mechanism was proposed [12], which will be discussed in the next section. As noted earlier, the kink-pair mechanism is relevant in the high-temperature regime. The 0 K CRSS for the kink-pair mechanism is around 900 MPa, significantly higher than the experimental CRSS of 100 MPa. Liu et al. [44] proposed an instability mechanism to explain the low CRSS in experiments conducted at low temperatures.

Figure 6.9: The minimum energy path (MEP) for the kink-pair mechanism in pure Mg, calculated using the newly developed NNP for the Mg-Zn system. Dislocation configurations along the MEP are illustrated with CNA coloring, showing different views for each configuration, labeled by their respective replica numbers. The kink-pair mechanism proceeds through the following stages: constriction (10), basal-to-prism cross-slip (11-12), prism-to-basal cross-slip with the formation of basal-basal kinks (13-14), and subsequent glide of the basal-basal kinks (14 onward). Throughout the process, the basal dislocation undergoes double cross-slip to the next adjacent basal plane over a distance of $c/2$. The movement of the dislocation is indicated by red lines.

While the kink-pair mechanism is irrelevant at low temperature, a close examination of the MEP for this mechanism may still reveal valuable insights into prismatic slip, even at low temperatures which is the main focus of the present chapter as the solute softening effect is observed at the low temperature regime. In the kink-pair mechanism, the transition state consists of two basal-basal kinks separated by a distance of approximately $16b$, without any prism segment. The transition state for our potential, which indicates meta-stability, is the same configuration as those for other potentials like NNP63 and NNP77, which indicate instability featuring two basal-basal kinks. Therefore, when it comes to the activation energy of the kink-pair mechanism in 3D, the system effectively "forgets" about the meta-stability or instability of the prism core, as it does not influence the transition state configuration.

In the current calculation of the MEP for the kink-pair mechanism, we effectively forced the system to cross-slip onto the next basal plane. At high temperatures and low applied stresses, thermal fluctuations could indeed facilitate cross-slip of the prism segment to the adjacent basal plane. However, under real conditions at 0K, without thermal fluctuations and under high stress, this forced cross-slip is unrealistic. Without the constraint of immediately falling onto the next basal plane, the prism segment, once formed, could take an alternate path than cross-slip, such as gliding along the prismatic plane. This extensive gliding can be due to instability as investigated by Liu et al [44]. Stricker and Curtin [42] performed an NEB calculation for the transition of basal dislocations over a distance of c rather than $c/2$, finding that the MEP essentially repeated the cross-slip process by increments of $c/2$. However, their calculation also imposed the constraint that the endpoint be a fully basal dislocation. As they noted in their study, for further understanding, NEB calculations are needed for other scenarios, such as the glide of the prism segment over several Burgers vectors following the basal-prism cross-slip.

6.3.2 Solute effect on kink-pair mechanism

Including solutes in the NEB calculation of the kink-pair mechanism provides a straightforward way to study the effects of solutes on key aspects of prismatic slip, such as kink nucleation and migration. Before proceeding, it is helpful to clearly identify the different atomic sites in both basal and prism dislocations. Therefore we labeled different atomic sites involved in the core of the dislocations as shown in Figure 6.10. Three columns are labeled as A , B , and C . In the transformation from the initial basal (b_1) to the second basal (b_2) the signs of the partials change and therefore the column A in b_1 is equivalent to column C in b_2 . Column B is the common plane between the two basals. From this figure, it is evident that any solute located in column B will have no effect on the relative energies of the initial and final basal dislocations, as it is common to both configurations. The site $B2$ is the site with the largest Zn/prism dislocation interaction energy, as shown in Figure 6.7. The highest interaction energy, measured -0.13 eV (in a cell with thickness $2b$), for basal dislocation is found for sites $B1$ and $A6$ in dislocation b_1 as shown in Figure 6.10.

Figure 6.10: CNA analysis of the dislocation core structures in basal(b_1)-prism(p)-basal(b_2) double cross-slip process. The identical sites are labeled in different configurations for better understanding of the process. Three columns of atoms that form the core of the dislocations are labeled by letters A , B , and C . From b_1 to b_2 the signs of the partials change. The column B is the common plane for both basals and column B in b_1 is equivalent to column C in b_2 .

To investigate the effect of solutes on the kink-pair mechanism, we placed individual solute atoms at different positions along the dislocation line and conducted NEB calculations to assess their influence on the energy barrier. The addition of single solute atoms provides a systematic approach to understanding solute effects on kink-pair mechanism. Moreover, our target alloys are very dilute, making it likely that only a single solute atom will be present within the activation length of the kink-pair process. For instance, if we consider 20 atomic sites around the core of a dislocation line with a length of $10b$, in an alloy of Mg-0.45% Zn, there would be an average of 0.9 solute atoms around the dislocation length. This also indicates that the effects of solutes on the kink-pair and single-kink mechanisms—discussed in the next section—are local rather than being a collective effect caused by a random distribution of solutes around the dislocation, as in solute strengthening.

The NEB calculations were performed in the same manner as for the pure Mg case. We introduced a solute atom at the same location in all the replicas generated by NNP63, then relaxed the endpoints before conducting the NEB calculation. By doing this, we essentially predetermined the kink nucleation position. In reality nucleation occurs at a position with lower energy barrier. Adding the solute at varying distances from the kink nucleation site allows us to systematically assess its effect on the energy barrier for kink-pair mechanism.

First, we positioned a solute at site $B1$, which exhibits the largest interaction energy with the basal dislocation core. Figure 6.11 presents the calculated MEP alongside the corresponding replica configurations, compared to the MEP of pure Mg. The solute is depicted in red for clarity. The MEP of the system with the solute shows minimal deviation from the pure Mg case, which aligns with our expectations. As seen in Figure 6.10, column B represents the shared plane between the two basal configurations. Consequently, the solute located at site $B1$ in

Figure 6.11: MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with a solute (colored in red) placed at site *B1*. The result is compared to the pure Mg case, which has been redrawn from Figure 6.9.

the initial configuration (Replica 0) maintains an identical interaction energy with the second basal plane in the transition state (Replica 17). This explains why the solute presence does not alter the overall MEP. The interaction energy with the prism segment does not play a role here because neither the initial nor the transition states contain any prism component. Moreover, the identical energies of the initial and final replicas further confirm the equivalence of plane *B* in both basal dislocations.

Introducing Zn at other crystallographic positions often leads to the basal dislocation gliding in the initial configuration due its very low lattice resistance. To avoid this, we used site *B1* as a pinning site before adding additional solute atoms. If the dislocation moves toward the most energetically favorable solute position in the initial state, its relative energy compared to the transition state will change, making it difficult to accurately assess the effect of the solute on the energy barrier. The solute placed at site *B1* ensures that the dislocation remains fixed in place and, since it has no significant effect on the MEP, it serves as an ideal anchoring point. This approach allows us to confidently study the impact of additional solutes without complications due to dislocation movements.

Using site *B1* as a pinning site, with the same location as shown in Figure 6.11 along the dislocation line, we introduced an additional solute at site *B2*, which has the highest interaction energy with the prism core. Figure 6.12 presents the resulting MEP and corresponding replicas. The *B2* solute was specifically positioned at the basal-basal kink nucleation site, as observed

Figure 6.12: MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes (colored in red) placed at sites $B1$, upper solute, and $B2$, lower solute. Solute $B2$ is placed at the lower basal-basal kink nucleation position.

in Replica 12. The MEP reveals a notable reduction of 0.32 eV in the energy barrier compared to pure Mg. Up to Replica 12, the energy profile remains very similar between the two cases; however, at Replica 12, the curves start to diverge. Replica 12 represents the configuration in which the basal-basal kinks form. Therefore, the energy reduction is due to the attractive interaction of solute with basal-basal kink. On the other hand, the solute has no significant interaction with the basal-prism kink (replica 11). Also it is seen that the solute at site $B2$, pins the lower basal-basal kink and the process proceed through the migration of the upper kink until the periodic image kinks are annihilated, leading to the full formation of the second basal plane.

By comparing the transition state (Replica 17) to the initial state, it can be concluded that the energy reduction is due to the interaction of Zn with the lower basal-basal kink. The basal solute, site $B1$, does not have a significant effect, as discussed above. Also we can see that the lower kink is sharper than that of the pure case which is an indication of its high interaction with the kink. The structure of the kink is similar to the prism core which aligns with the high interaction energy of site $B2$ with the prism core (Figure 6.7). It is also seen that as the basal-basal kink forms in replica 12, the presence of the solute $B2$ leads to the pinning of the lower kink and the process continues via migration of the upper basal-basal kink until the annihilation occurs. Therefore, although the presence of the solute $B2$ leads to the lower energy barrier for kink formation, this does not necessarily mean that this will lead to softening because the same energy reduction also leads to kink pinning and inhibits its migration. To

Figure 6.13: MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes placed at sites $B1$, upper solute, and $B2$, lower solute.

observe the pinning effect of the solute on kink more clearly, Figure 6.13 shows another MEP where depinning of the lower kink from solute $B2$ occurs before complete annihilation. It is seen that as soon as the kink frees itself from solute $B2$ the energy increases to the pure level creating a significant barrier.

Solute $B2$ is effective only when it is inside the lower kink. Figure 6.14 shows the MEP when we have two solutes $B1$ and $B2$, such that $B2$ is placed in the middle of the two kinks. The energy barrier doesn't change at all which is due to, as discussed above, solute being at the common plane B . As there are no solutes inside the kinks, they move freely, similar to the pure case, and annihilate each other. We also performed NEB calculations with the solute $B2$ this time at the upper kink. However, the results showed little impact on the energy barrier. This suggests that, due to the structural differences between the two kink configurations, the interaction energy between the solute and the kink is different. For the upper kink, however, we found that the solute $B3$ has a significant effect on the energy barrier, as shown in Figure 6.15. Similar to previous results, we observe the pinning of the upper kink until the annihilation occurs. Pinning effect is not seen in the energy profiles because of the kinks annihilation.

In summary, solutes can significantly influence the kink-formation energy. Due to the sharp nature of kinks, a single solute can greatly affect both kink nucleation and migration. While solutes can considerably reduce the energy barrier for kink nucleation, they also strongly pin the kinks. Therefore, it cannot be conclusively stated that the presence of solutes will lead to a substantial softening of the kink-pair mechanism.

Figure 6.14: MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes placed at sites $B1$, lower solute, and $B2$, upper solute. Solute $B2$ is placed in the middle of the two kinks.

Figure 6.15: MEP calculated for the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip via the kink-pair mechanism, with two solutes placed at sites $B1$, lower solute, and $B3$, upper solute.

6.4 Single-kink mechanism

6.4.1 Pure Mg

Although studying the kink-pair mechanism offers significant insights into the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip process and the impact of solutes, the calculated activation energy of approximately 1.5 eV remains about twice the experimental value of 0.8 ± 0.1 eV. To rectify this discrepancy, Liu and Curtin [12] proposed the single-kink mechanism. We recap the theory below, as it will be useful for analyzing solute effects in the next section.

The single-kink mechanism approaches the basal-prism-basal double cross-slip problem by examining a dislocation loop on a prismatic plane rather than a long straight dislocation. Figure 6.16(a-f) illustrates this mechanism schematically, and Figure 6.16g shows the energy change during each step of single-kink process as a function of the cross-slipped length, l . A dislocation loop on the prismatic plane has an screw component dissociated onto the basal plane and a non-screw component (Figure 6.16a). The screw component is connected to the edge component through a transition region that is similar to the structure of a basal-prism (bp) kink. Under applied stress, the loop expands through the glide of the edge component (Figure 6.16b) and the transition region cross-slips by thermal activation onto the prism plane along the length, l , connected to the remaining basal segment through the pre-existing bp kink of height $c/4$ (Figure 6.16c). For a pure material, under the applied external stress, τ , the change in enthalpy due to basal-prism cross-slip in a dislocation segment of length l can be written as

$$\Delta H_{pb}^{pure}(l) = E_p l - \tau b \frac{c}{4} l \quad (6.1)$$

We use the superscript, *pure*, to distinguish these parameters from the corresponding parameters when the solutes are incorporated in the next section. Here, E_p represents the energy difference per unit length between the prism and basal dislocations, which, based on DFT calculations, is approximately 62 meV. For our newly developed NNP, this value is estimated at 67 meV. ΔH_{pb}^{pure} under zero stress and as a function of l is illustrated by the black line in Figure 6.16g.

When the length of the prism segment reaches a critical value l_t as seen in (Figure 6.16d) the process continues with the cross-slip of the prism segment to the next basal plane forming a basal-basal kink with a height of $c/2$. Relative to the initial state (Figure 6.16a) the enthalpy increase is

$$\Delta H_{bb}^{pure}(l) = E_{bb}(l) - \tau b l \frac{c}{2} \quad (6.2)$$

Figure 6.16: (a-f) Schematic of single-kink mechanism [12] in a dislocation loop on the prism (p) plane. Basal-prism and basal-basal kinks are represented as bp and bb. a) The initial state with basal dissociated screw component and an already existing bp kink in the transition region. b) The non-screw component begins to glide, c) basal-prism cross-slip occurs as bp kink moves away from the non-screw segment. d) The prism formed at the transition segment cross-slips onto the adjacent basal plane and a bb kink forms when bp kink has moved by a critical distance, l_t . A bp kink forms again at the transition region. e) The bb kink moves away until a characteristic distance, l_m , where the kink-kink interaction disappears. f) The entire dislocation line glides by $c/2$ and the whole process repeats leading to continuous screw prism slip. The energy evolution as a function of l during the single-kink process under zero applied stress is shown in (g). l_{t0} and ΔH_{t0} are the values of l_t and ΔH_t at zero stress, and similarly for l_m and ΔH_m

Where $E_{bb}(l)$ is the energy of one basal-basal kink at a distance l from the non-screw portion of the loop. At the critical length l_t the energy of states with basal-prism kink (Figure 6.16c) and basal-basal kink (Figure 6.16d) are equal,

$$\Delta H_{pb}^{pure}(l_t) = \Delta H_{bb}^{pure}(l_t) = \Delta H_t \quad (6.3)$$

After the nucleation of basal-basal kink, l increases by the kinks moving away from each other (Figure 6.16e) until the kink-kink interaction vanishes at length l_m , and finally the entire dislocation line glides by a distance $c/2$ (Figure 6.16f). To calculate the enthalpy change for basal-basal kink formation, $\Delta H_{bb}(l)$, we need, $E_{bb}(l)$. Liu and Curtin[12] formulated $E_{bb}(l)$ by simulating a system consisting of a basal-basal kink and a basal-prism kink under zero stress and measured the energy of the system as a function of their distance, l . They used NNP63 for these simulations. By fitting a quadratic function to energy values at different distances, they expressed $E_{bb}(l)$ as,

$$E_{bb}(l) = \begin{cases} \Delta H_{m0} - \frac{\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_0}{(l_{m0} - l_0)^2} (l_{m0} - l)^2, & l_0 < l \leq l_{m0} \\ \Delta H_{m0}, & l > l_{m0} \end{cases} \quad (6.4)$$

Where l_0 represents the minimum length at which a basal-basal kink forms under zero-stress conditions in the simulation, with a corresponding energy denoted as ΔH_0 . The parameter l_{m0} indicates the length at which the interaction energy between the kinks vanishes, causing the energy to reach a constant value, ΔH_{m0} . The functions $E_{bb}(l)$ and ΔH_{m0} are plotted in Figure 6.16g, by red and blue colors, respectively.

With E_p and $E_{bb}(l)$, we can now formulate the enthalpy barrier, $\Delta H^{pure}(\tau)$, for basal-prism-basal double cross-slip by the single-kink mechanism as a function of the applied stress, τ . In the single-kink mechanism, there are two distinct stress regimes (see Figure 9 in ref[12]). At low applied stresses, the enthalpy barrier is predominantly governed by the nucleation and migration barrier of basal-basal kinks, ΔH_{bb}^{pure} , corresponding to the configuration shown in Figure 6.16e. However, as the applied stress increases to a characteristic level, τ_{mt}^{pure} , the controlling factor transitions to the energy required for prism formation at the critical length, l_t , ΔH_{pb}^{pure} (Figure 6.16c,d). At low applied stress, $\tau < \tau_{mt}^{pure}$, the enthalpy barrier is the maximum of $\Delta H_{bb}^{pure}(l) = E_{bb}(l) - \tau b l \frac{c}{2}$,

$$\Delta H^{pure}(\tau) = \Delta H_{m0} + \frac{1}{16} [\tau b c (l_{m0} - l_{t0})]^2 \frac{1}{\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0}} - \frac{\tau b c l_{m0}}{2} := \Delta H_m^{pure}(\tau) \quad (6.5)$$

at the activation length $l_m^{pure}(\tau)$ of

$$l_m^{pure}(\tau) = l_{m0} - \frac{\tau b c}{4} \frac{(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2}{\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0}} \quad (6.6)$$

Characteristic stress, τ_{mt}^{pure} , is the stress at which $l_m^{pure}(\tau) = l_t^{pure}(\tau)$, obtained as,

$$\tau_{mt}^{pure} = \frac{4}{b c} \frac{(\Delta H_{m0} - E_p l_{m0})(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0})}{l_{m0}(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0}) - E_p (l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2} \quad (6.7)$$

with the corresponding enthalpy of,

$$\Delta H_{mt}^{pure} = \Delta H_m^{pure}(\tau_{mt}) \quad (6.8)$$

and the activation length l_{mt}^{pure} of

$$l_{mt}^{pure} = l_{m0} - \frac{(\Delta H_{m0} - E_p l_{m0})(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2}{l_{m0}(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0}) - E_p(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2} \quad (6.9)$$

At high applied stresses, $\tau > \tau_{mt}^{pure}$, the barrier is controlled by ΔH_{pb}^{pure} . Therefore, the enthalpy barrier is,

$$\Delta H^{pure}(\tau) = \left(E_p - \frac{\tau bc}{4} \right) l_t := H_t^{pure}(\tau) \quad (6.10)$$

with activation length,

$$l_t^{pure}(\tau) = l_{m0} - \frac{(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2 (E_p + \tau b \frac{c}{4})}{2(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0})} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{4(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0})}{(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2} \cdot \frac{\Delta H_{m0} - (E_p + \tau b \frac{c}{4}) l_{m0}}{(E_p + \tau b \frac{c}{4})^2}} \right] \quad (6.11)$$

The total energy barrier $\Delta H^{pure}(\tau)$ reaches zero at $\tau_{y0} = E_p / (bc/4)$. Finally, using the Arrhenius model, the strength, τ_y , can be estimated at a certain temperature, T , and strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$ as,

$$k_B T \ln \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_0}{\dot{\epsilon}} = \begin{cases} \Delta H_{m0} + \frac{1}{16} [\tau_y bc (l_{m0} - l_{t0})]^2 / (\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0}) - \frac{\tau_y bc l_{m0}}{2}, & \tau_y \leq \tau_{mt} \\ (E_p - \tau_y \frac{bc}{4}) l_t, & \tau_{mt} < \tau_y < \tau_{y0} \end{cases} \quad (6.12)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ is a reference strain rate.

6.4.2 Solute effect on single-kink mechanism

In this section, we extend the single-kink formulation to incorporate the effect of solutes, aiming to understand their influence on the strength of prismatic slip mediated by this mechanism. In the previous sections, we calculated the interaction energy of Zn with basal and prism screw dislocations. Using this data, we can now estimate how the presence of a solute at specific positions can alter the energies of the different states depicted in Figure 6.16.

Figure 6.17 shows, schematically, the effect of a solute on the energy profile of the single-kink mechanism. We consider a solute positioned within the dissociated basal dislocation at a specific distance, l_s , from the non-screw segment of the loop. This configuration is labeled by number 0. Due to the interaction energy between the solute and the basal screw dislocation,

denoted as h_{b1} and h_{b2} , the energies of the initial and final configurations are lower compared to the pure case. In this scenario, we have assumed a negative interaction energy for both basal screws.

The basal screw gradually starts transforming into the prism screw as the basal-prism kink glides into the basal dislocation (configurations 1-2). As each unit length of the basal dislocation converts into the prism dislocation, the energy of the system increases by E_p . Before the basal-prism kink reaches the solute, the energy increase from the initial configuration, calculated as $E_p l$, is the same as that of the pure case. As the basal-prism kink continues to glide along the basal dislocation, it eventually reaches and moves past the solute position, l_s , (configuration 3). The energy of this state is now lower than in pure Mg, by an amount equivalent to the solute/prism screw dislocation interaction energy, h_p . In this analysis, we did not account for the effect of the solute on the kink itself due to two reasons, first the NEB calculations for kink-pair mechanism showed that the solute has a minimal effect on the basal-prism kink and second the purpose here is to analyze the effect of the solute on the energetics of each step in single-kink mechanism as shown in Figure 6.16 without considering the interaction of solute with kinks.

The kink continues to glide, creating an extended prism screw segment (configuration 4) until the critical length, l_t^{solute} , is achieved leading to the prism-basal cross-slip (configuration 5). The slope of the line after l_s is again E_p . In this scenario, the presence of the solute results in an increased critical length compared to that of pure case, l_t^{pure} . The basal-basal kink then moves further from the transition region until it reaches the constant energy region, l_m (configuration 6).

By considering the schematics shown in Figure 6.17, we will now calculate the parameters of the single-kink theory involving solute. These analysis are general and not limited to the specific case illustrated in Figure 6.17. The addition of a solute alters $E_{bb}(l)$ by simply shifting it upward or downward, depending on the sign of the interaction energy, h_{b2} . However, the total energy barrier at low stresses, $\Delta H_m(\tau)$, depends now on the solute position, l_s , its interaction with the prism screw, h_p , and also with the basal screw, h_{b1} . A larger, negative h_{b1} results in increased energy barrier via lowering the energy of the initial state. If the solute is near the transition region or if h_p is significant such that, after the kink passes the solute, the energy drops below that of the initial state, then the reference energy for the barrier calculation should be the energy at position l_s , which is, $E_p l_s - h_p$, not the energy of the initial basal state. Thus, we have:

$$\Delta H_m^{solute}(\tau) = \begin{cases} \Delta H_m^{pure}(\tau) + h_{b2} - h_{b1}, & \text{if } E_p l_s - \tau b l_s \frac{c}{4} + h_p - h_{b1} > 0 \\ \Delta H_m^{pure}(\tau) + h_{b2} - (E_p l_s + h_p), & \text{if } E_p l_s - \tau b l_s \frac{c}{4} + h_p - h_{b1} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6.13)$$

Where the first equation is used when the initial state is the global minimum, and the second equation is used when the global minimum is located at l_s . l_m^{solute} , which is the length at which $E_{bb}^{solute}(l)$ is maximum, would be identical to the pure case.

Figure 6.17: Schematics of the effect of solute on the energy profile of single-kink mechanism. h_{b1} and h_{b2} are the solute interaction energies with the initial and final basal dislocations. h_p is the interaction energy of solute with the prism dislocation. The position of the solute is represented by l_s , the critical lengths for pure and alloy cases by l_t^{pure} and l_t^{solute} , and the length corresponding to the maximum energy by l_t^{pure} and l_m^{solute} . The transition part from screw to non-screw component of the loop is not shown in the configurations. The solute is colored in red.

The characteristic stress, τ_{mt}^{solute} , can be obtained by solving

$$\Delta H_m^{pure}(\tau) + h_{b2} = (E_p - \tau \frac{bc}{4}) l_m^{solute} + h_p, \quad (6.14)$$

which yields, τ_{mt} , as,

$$\tau_{mt}^{solute} = \frac{4}{bc} \frac{(\Delta H_{m0} + h_{b2} - h_p - E_p l_{m0})(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0})}{l_{m0}(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0}) - E_p(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2} \quad (6.15)$$

For high stresses, $\tau > \tau_{mt}^{solute}$, the enthalpy barrier is controlled by prism formation, $\Delta H_t^{solute}(\tau)$, and depends also on the position and interaction energies of the solute as

$$\Delta H_t^{solute}(\tau) = \begin{cases} (E_p - \tau \frac{bc}{4}) l_t^{solute} + h_p - h_{b1}, & \text{if } E_p l_s - \tau b l_s \frac{c}{4} + h_p - h_{b1} > 0 \\ (E_p - \tau \frac{bc}{4}) l_t^{solute} - E_p l_s + \tau b l_s \frac{c}{4}, & \text{if } E_p l_s - \tau b l_s \frac{c}{4} + h_p - h_{b1} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6.16)$$

Where similar to Equation 6.13 the first equation corresponds to the case where the initial

state is the global minimum and the second equation to the case where l_s is the location of global minimum. l_t^{solute} can be obtained by solving

$$\Delta H_m^{\text{pure}}(\tau) + h_{b2} = (E_p - \tau \frac{bc}{4}) l_t^{solute} + h_p, \quad (6.17)$$

which gives,

$$l_t^{solute}(\tau) = l_{m0} - \frac{(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2 (E_p + \tau b \frac{c}{4})}{2(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0})} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{4(\Delta H_{m0} - \Delta H_{t0})}{(l_{m0} - l_{t0})^2} \cdot \frac{\Delta H_{ms} - (E_p + \tau b \frac{c}{4}) l_{m0}}{(E_p + \tau b \frac{c}{4})^2}} \right] \quad (6.18)$$

where $\Delta H_{ms} = \Delta H_{m0} + h_{b2} - h_p$.

Now we have all the elements we need to compute the strength as

$$k_B T \ln \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_0}{\dot{\epsilon}} = \begin{cases} \Delta H_m^{solute}(\tau), & \tau_y \leq \tau_{mt} \\ \Delta H_t^{solute}(\tau), & \tau_{mt} < \tau_y < \tau_{y0} \end{cases} \quad (6.19)$$

6.4.3 Case studies

We applied the single-kink formulations, extended to include solute effects, to several case studies to examine their impact on strength. To this aim, we considered different interaction energies of solute with basal/prism dislocations at various solute positions. For single kink parameters we used the same values used in ref [12], which were obtained as the average of several NNPs for pure Mg, namely $l_0 = 8.96 b$, $H_0 = 0.65$ eV, $E_p = 0.62$ eV, $l_{m0} = 15.01 b$, and $H_{m0} = 0.71$ eV.

Left column of Figure 6.18 presents energy profiles at varying applied stress levels for different solute/dislocation interaction energies. The right column illustrates the corresponding CRSS values as function of temperature. For comparison, the dotted curves represent the energy profile of the pure case for the corresponding stress level. In Figure 6.18a, the solute exhibits a negative interaction energy with the initial basal plane, $h_{b1} = -0.1$ eV, and zero interaction with prism and the second basal plane. Consequently, the dislocation starts at a lower energy level compared to the pure case. As l increases, the energy rises according to $E_p l - \tau b l \frac{c}{4}$, until the kink moves past the solute at $l_s = 3b$. When $l = l_s$, the solute is positioned within the prism segment. Given that $h_p = 0$, the energy returns to the same level as in the pure Mg case. From this point onward, the system follows the energy profile of the pure case. Notably, at a stress of 700 MPa (green curves), the energy barrier for the pure case is nearly zero. However, in the alloy, an energy jump remains at l_s , which results in a barrier, despite the large applied stress. The critical resolved shear stress (CRSS) for the alloy is significantly higher than pure case across all temperature regimes. This is expected, as lowering the energy of the initial state while keeping the energy of the final state constant results in a higher energy barrier in both

Figure 6.18: Solute effect on the single-kink mechanism energy profiles under various applied stresses and corresponding CRSS value as a function of temperature. a) Solute is placed at position $l_s = 3b$ with interaction energies $h_{b1} = -0.1$ eV, $h_p = 0$, and $h_{b2} = 0$. b) Solute at position $l_s = 3b$ with interaction energies $h_{b1} = 0$, $h_p = -0.2$ eV, and $h_{b2} = 0$. The dotted curves corresponds for the pure case.

stress regimes.

Figure 6.18b shows another scenario where the solute, positioned at $l_s = 3b$, has a negative interaction energy with the prism, $h_p = -0.2$ eV but zero interaction energy with the basal screws, $h_{b1} = h_{b2} = 0$. In terms of the single-kink energy barriers, these interaction energies correspond to the realistic interaction energies of site B2, $h_p = -0.27$ eV, and $h_{b1} = h_{b2} = -0.07$ eV. These values effectively shift the entire energy curves by 0.07 eV. However, presenting the curves in the former manner offers a clearer comparison with the pure case. The energy barrier is slightly higher than pure due to the drop in energy at l_s , reaching a level lower than the initial state. This drop also increases significantly the critical length, l_t , and consequently the transition to prism controlled regime will occur at much lower stress levels. This is evident from the small value of $\tau_{mt} = 13$ MPa as opposed to the pure value of $\tau_{mt} = 119$ MPa. However, the barrier which is now measured from the energy level at l_s does not change significantly. Consistent with these energy barriers, the CRSS does not show significant changes compared to the pure case, although a slight strengthening at high temperatures and softening at low temperatures can be observed. At 0 K, or the athermal stress level the pure and alloy have identical strengths because their barrier goes to zero at the same stress level.

We also investigated how strongly the barriers and CRSS can be influenced by the position

of the solute. A solute with interaction energies, $h_p = -0.2$ eV and $h_{b1} = h_{b2} = 0$ is placed at different positions of $l_s = 2b, 3b, 4b$ and $5b$ and the energy profiles and CRSS were calculated (Figure 6.19). When $l_s = 2b$, the solute is close enough to the transition region that its interaction energy with the prism reduces the energy to below the initial state at very low stress. As a result, the energy barrier strengthens from very low stress levels or high temperatures, as shown in the CRSS plot. As stress increases, by predominance of prism screw barrier, the alloy's strength converges with that of the pure material.

When the solute is positioned at $l_s = 3b$, it is further away from the transition region, and the increased barrier caused by the energy reduction at l_s vanishes, resulting in strengths that are almost identical to those of the pure material. When the solute moves to $l_s = 4b$, the energy no longer drops to negative values at the solute position, meaning that the low-stress barriers and CRSS remain unchanged. As stress increases, the prism-controlled region dominates, which results in softening.

At $l_s = 5b$, the softening effect begins earlier and is more pronounced; however, around 500 MPa, the strength matches that of the pure material. The reason for the longer equal-strength regime at high stresses for $l_s = 5b$ is that above 500 MPa, $l_s > l_t$. Consequently, before reaching the critical length, basal-basal nucleation and glide occur spontaneously, meaning the solute has no effect on softening.

In summary, while the single-kink mechanism offers a lower energy barrier for prismatic slip in pure magnesium because it involves the nucleation of a single kink instead of kink-pair, it fails to account for the pronounced softening effect of solutes at low temperatures. Our analysis indicates that, based on the single-kink mechanism, for realistic solute/dislocation interaction energies the 0 K barrier remains comparable to that of the pure material. At elevated temperatures, this mechanism provides insights into solute effects, predicting either strengthening or negligible impact in certain scenarios. However, its applicability at low temperatures remains ambiguous. Notably, Liu and Curtin proposed this theory for high-temperature studies, as parameters like l_t are derived from the intersection of the prism-controlled energy region with the basal kink controlled energy regime. Consequently, the theory was not designed to examine processes involving extensive glide, which are more likely mechanisms at low temperatures.

Figure 6.19: Single-kink energy profiles and the corresponding CRSS versus temperature values for a solute with interaction energies of $h_p = -0.2$ eV and $h_{b1} = h_{b2} = 0$ located at different positions $l_s = 2b, 3b, 4b,$ and $5b$. Dotted lines show the energy profiles of the pure material

6.5 A new mechanism for solute softening

The kink-pair and single-kink mechanisms discussed in the preceding chapters offer valuable insights into the effects of solutes on prismatic slip in magnesium alloys. In the kink-pair mechanism, we observed that basal-basal kinks are sharp, and individual solutes can significantly affect both the nucleation energy and the migration energy barrier of these kinks. On the other hand, the single-kink mechanism focuses on the corners of the dislocation loop, highlighting the importance of these transition regions in facilitating the basal-prism cross-slip by requiring half the energy cost of kink-pair. However, both these mechanisms are suggested for the high temperature regime where basal-prism-basal double cross-slip occurs from one basal dislocation to the adjacent one. At low temperature regime, where the softening effect is more pronounced, the prismatic slip occurs via basal-prism cross-slip and then glide of the prism screw by several Burgers vector.

Building on insights from the single-kink mechanism, in this section, we investigate the effects of a solute positioned at the corners of a dislocation loop on the glide of the screw component. Our simulations of the interaction between the solute and the corner of an expanding dislocation loop reveal a new mechanism that could explain the low-temperature softening effect of solutes.

We indicate the new mechanism by a series of molecular statics simulation of dislocation loops containing Zn under stress. To do that, initially, we construct a dislocation loop on the prismatic plane by displacing the atoms based on the elasticity solution [132] using the package ATOMSK [133]. The simulation cell for introducing the loop has dimensions, $l_x = 31$ nm, $l_y = 22$ nm, and $l_z = 40$ nm containing about 1 million atoms. A square dislocation loop with a side length of 16 nm is introduced on a prismatic plane at the center of the simulation cell. The normal vector of the prismatic plane is along the direction y . We used periodic boundary condition along Z direction while using fixed boundary condition along the axes x and y . The Burgers vector is along x direction.

6.5.1 Pure Mg

Before analyzing the effect of solutes on loop evolution, we first simulate dislocation loops in pure Mg under various applied stresses to establish a baseline for comparing the influence of solutes on the process.

Since dislocation loop has a self energy and it will collapse without the application of stress, for the construction of the dislocation loop, first we applied a shear strain, then displaced the atoms to make the loop, and then relaxed the structure under fixed boundary condition. We tried different strain/stress levels, and found 320 MPa as the minimum equilibrium stress required to prevent the collapse of the loop. The relaxed structure of the loop is shown in Figure 6.20 seen from two different angles. The screw components of the loop dissociate onto the basal plane after relaxation making straight screw segments.

Figure 6.20: The equilibrium loop shape of pure Mg under the applied shear stress of 320 MPa to prevent it from collapse. The starting configuration is a square loop constructed by displacements based on elasticity. (b) is the oblique view of (a)

Applying additional stress on the relaxed structure of the loop shown in Figure 6.20 leads to the loop expansion in the edge direction due to very low Peierls stress. The expansion in screw direction only occurs when the applied stress is sufficiently high for the basal-prism cross-slip of screw components. Figure 6.21 displays the relaxed structure of the loop under a total shear stress of 1000 MPa. This was achieved by applying an additional stress of 680 MPa to the already relaxed loop structure from Figure 6.20. Therefore the effective stress acting on the loop is 680 MPa.

As shown in Figure 6.21, the edge components move until they reach the boundaries of the simulation cell (not visible in the figure) and then stop. No slip occurs in the screw direction, and as the loop expands along the edge direction, the straight segment of the screw component, formed due to basal dissociation, becomes elongated leading to larger proportion of pure

Figure 6.21: Relaxation of the loop shown in Figure 6.20 under total shear stress of 1000 MPa. The final configuration is displayed from two different angles.

edge and pure screw dislocations.

However, when a higher effective shear stress of 780 MPa is applied, cross-slip occurs at two corners of the loop, as shown in Figure 6.22b. This observation further supports the preference for cross-slip from the corners over the kink-pair mechanism, as suggested by the single-kink mechanism. Loop expansion continues until the edge components reach the simulation boundary (Figure 6.22c) and cross-slipped segment elongates. The cross-slipped segment then begins to bow out, leading to the glide of the screw dislocation on the prism plane (Figure 6.22d). The dislocation continues to glide along the prismatic plane until it is annihilated by its periodic image. The significant screw prism glide observed here may be attributed to the intrinsic meta-stability of the prism screw as predicted by the NNP. However, the critical point is the initial cross-slip (Figure 6.22b), which was absent at a shear stress of 680 MPa.

Figure 6.22: Configurations during the relaxation steps of the loop shown in Figure 6.20 under a total applied shear stress of 780 MPa. (b) The loop expands in the edge direction, and cross-slip occurs at the corners. (c) The edge component reaches the simulation boundary and stops. The cross-slipped segment elongates. (d) Screw prism slip on the prismatic plane leads to further expansion of the loop along the screw direction.

It is important to note that the effective stress values reported here represent the difference between the total applied shear stress on the simulation cell and equilibrium stress of 320 MPa. As will be discussed at the end of this chapter, the actual effective stress is uncertain because when additional stress is applied, the loop expands, and the equilibrium stress will no longer remain at 320 MPa.

6.5.2 Solute effect

To examine the effect of solute on the evolution of loops, we placed a Zn atom at site *B2* in the transition region of the loop shown in Figure 6.21 and relaxed the structure under the stress of 680 MPa. Figure 6.23a illustrates the initial configuration of the loop and the position of the solute before relaxation, while Figure 6.23b shows the configuration after relaxation. The solute atom is highlighted in red. It is seen that at the corner in which there is a Zn atom, cross-slip to prism screw occurs while the corner with no solute remains at the basal configuration. This, clearly shows the effect of solute on the easiness of the basal-prism cross slip when it is placed at the transition region.

The softening effect is not observed when we position Zn at a slightly farther distance than the transition region. Figure 6.24a shows, for instance, the case where the solute is positioned at the same *B2* site but not in the transition region. After relaxation (Figure 6.24b), no cross-slip happens, though some amount of constriction can be observed around the solute, however it is not strong enough to trigger basal-prism cross-slip.

Figure 6.23: Solute effect on the cross-slip of the screw component when the solute is located on the transition region of the loop (red colored). a) Before relaxation. This is the same loop, relaxed under 680 MPa, shown in Figure 6.21a. b) The configuration after relaxation.

Figure 6.24: Solute effect on the cross-slip of the screw component when the solute (red colored) is located away from the transition region of the loop. a) Before relaxation. This is the same loop, relaxed under 680 MPa, shown in Figure 6.21a. b) The configuration after relaxation.

These simulations demonstrate that a solute located at the transition regions of the loops can indeed facilitate a cross-slip process originating from the corners. This behavior contrasts with the pure case under 680 MPa, where no cross-slip is observed. Also, the screw component of the loop which has no solute in it, does not show cross-slip when the other corner does. Therefore, according to these simulations, a single Zn atom located at the corner can reduce the strength and induce softening. However, the observed softening is not as significant as expected from experiments, since the simulation at 580 MPa did not exhibit cross-slip.

Cross-slip initiates from the corners because the transition region possesses significantly higher energy compared to a dissociated basal dislocation. While the exact structure and energy level of this region are difficult to determine, it is evident from NEB calculations of the kink-pair process that a substantial amount of energy is required to constrict the basal dislocation. In contrast, the transition regions naturally bypass this constriction requirement, making them favorable initiation sites for cross-slip.

6.5.3 Solute effect on loop expansion

The simulations presented so far, to examine the effect of solute, have all involved static loops. With static loops, as in Figure 6.23, we choose a particular site along the loop which has already stopped expansion in the edge direction due to the presence of the simulation boundaries.

However, in reality loops expand continuously along their edge components due to very low resistance to edge glide even with solute strengthening (as demonstrated in Chapter 4). Consequently, the loops grow predominantly in the edge direction, quickly forming long, straight screw dislocations. Therefore, the static simulation loops do not accurately capture the realistic behavior of these loops in terms of their possible interaction with solutes. For this reason, We did further simulations to see the role of solutes when they encounter an expanding loop.

A solute is placed at site *B2*, positioned in front of an expanding loop, as illustrated in Figure 6.25a. The initial loop is the equilibrium loop (Figure 6.20). A total stress of 580 MPa is applied during the relaxation. After several relaxation steps, the loop expands through the easy glide of the edge component, and the basal dislocation encounters the solute. At this point, the solute acts as a pinning point, preventing further dissociation of the screw component (Figure 6.25b). Due to the solute pinning, the screw component elongates through the formation of prism screw (Figure 6.25c). The prism segment formed as a result of the expansion of the loop in the presence of the pinning effect of solute begins bowing out when its length is sufficiently long and eventually moves past the solute (Figure 6.25d). Relaxation proceeds with additional bowing out and slip on the prismatic plane until the dislocation sweeps across the entire simulation cell.

This process already decreases the stress required for screw prism glide to 580 MPa compared to the stress required for cross-slip in pure Mg which is in the range 680-780 MPa, Aa shown in Figure 6.21.

Figure 6.25: Interaction of Zn solute (colored with red) with an expanding loop. The stress level is 580 MPa and steps (a)-(d) are the steps during relaxation.

We repeated the same simulation with the same solute position, $B2$, for even lower stresses down to 280 MPa, as shown in figure 6.26. In all cases, we can see that the cross-slip occurs at the corner where there is a solute. For these stresses, as well, the mechanism is the same as 580 MPa (6.25), pinning the basal dislocation, and increasing the length of the screw component through the formation of compact prism dislocation. Therefore, these simulations show that a single solute encountering an expanding loop, can reduce the strength of prismatic glide by huge amount of about 500 MPa in the simulations.

Understanding the causes of this large softening through this mechanism requires further investigations. A possible reason can be as follows: The transition region can act as a pre-existing constriction to reduce the energy barrier for the cross-slip. However in the simulations of pure samples this transition region is too short for processes like prism formation and bow-out requiring high stress levels. When solute acts as a barrier against the propagation of the dissociated basal, the expansion of the loop results in long prism segment which can easily glide on the prismatic plane without the need for the constriction of the dissociated basal. Pinning may happen due to the transformation of the transition compact segment to prism core. The solute, $B2$, has an interaction energy of -0.27 eV with the prism core. When the prism segment forms having the highly attractive solute in it, the dissociation into basal will result in energy cost due to lower interaction energy with basal. Therefore, there is a barrier for dissociation into basal.

Figure 6.26: Cross-slip of the screw component due to the interaction of a Zn solute with an expanding loop at different stress levels a) 480 MPa, b) 380 MPa, c) 280 MPa, d) 280 MPa. The position of the solute at (a-c) are identical but closer to the initial basal segment in (d). In all cases the solute pins the dissociated basal and cross-slip occurs along the sufficiently long transition region.

This mechanism aligns with the experimental results in terms of temperature effect. As we go to higher temperatures, the solute cannot pin the basal dislocation anymore and the strength would be equal to pure Mg similar to what we see in experimental results. We conducted MD simulations and observed that, at room temperature, the dislocation easily bypasses the solute, resulting in no solute-induced softening of the cross-slip. An interesting aspect of this mechanism is that it does not rely on the probability of a solute being positioned at the loop corners, as is required for static cases. An expanding loop will inevitably encounter a solute somewhere along its path, with the frequency of such encounters depending on the solute concentration.

Our simulation results doesn't show close quantitative agreement with experiments which reported only 100 MPa for prismatic slip whereas we obtain an order of magnitude difference. The reasons behind this is not clear. One important factor could be the self stress of the loop. Since the self-stress is not known, we cannot confidently determine the exact amount of stress being applied to the dislocation lines. We did a discrete dislocation dynamics (DDD) calculation and found out that at the corners of the loops we investigated here the self-stress can be quite high as 700 MPa. Understanding the value of the local stress is crucial for

quantitatively investigating the strength of prismatic slip. While the total applied stress can be substantial, the presence of similarly large self-stress can significantly reduce the effective local stress experienced by individual dislocation segments. Consequently, even under high applied stress, the actual driving force for dislocation motion at specific segments may remain relatively small. Another possible reason for the discrepancy between the experimental CRSS and computational results could be the presence of pinning or anchoring points in experimental samples. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) studies clearly reveal the existence of these anchoring points.

It is plausible that a dislocation segment near such obstacles develops regions resembling the transition segments of a loop. As a result, in real experiments, the strength of pure Mg might already be lower due to these localized effects. In contrast, computational studies typically involve perfectly relaxed structures without inclusions or obstacles, leading to an overestimation of the critical stress required for cross-slip.

An atomistic study by Itakura et al. [129] further supports this idea, demonstrating that the presence of obstacles can significantly reduce the stress required for basal-prism cross-slip.

Finally it is important to take into account the meta-stability of the prism core which is an artifact of the developed NNP. In our simulations, screw slip occurs in two distinct steps: first, the pinning of the dissociated basal segment through the formation of a prism screw segment, and second, the subsequent bow-out process. The pinning effect primarily arises from the strong interaction between the solute and the prism core, which has a significant binding energy of -0.27 eV. This interaction is notably large compared to the prism-basal barrier, which exists due to the meta-stability of the prism core. However, despite this pronounced effect of the solute, it remains essential to fully understand the extent to which the meta-stability of the prism core influences the initial stages of pinning. The meta-stability of the prism screw dislocation can play a decisive role in determining the extent to which the bow-out process can proceed. A meta-stable prism screw can glide relatively easily on the prism plane without reverting to the basal plane, provided that the applied stress exceeds the Peierls stress. The Peierls stress obtained from the present NNP is remarkably low, at just 14 MPa. In contrast, if the prism screw configuration is unstable, the dislocation can still glide over large distances if the applied stress exceeds the *instability stress*. This stress represents the threshold beyond which an unstable dislocation can move several Burgers vectors while remaining in a high-energy state. Given the small prism-basal energy barrier resulting from the weak meta-stability of the prism screw configuration, even minor inhomogeneities in the microstructure could trigger cross-slip between the prism and basal planes. Therefore, in practical scenarios, it is unlikely that such a weakly meta-stable configuration would remain confined to the prism plane for an extended period.

7 Discussion and conclusion

This thesis investigates the atomic-level mechanisms underlying the effects of solutes on prismatic slip in Mg alloys. Specifically, it aims to understand how certain solutes can soften prismatic slip at low temperatures while contributing to strengthening at higher temperatures. The Mg-Zn alloy was used as a model system to explore these phenomena in detail.

First we analyzed and implemented the fixed boundary condition method to accurately calculate the core structure of the dislocation. We showed that by careful examination of the surface forces due to Friedel oscillations and ensuring that the boundaries follow elasticity, accurate calculations can be done with reasonable computational cost. We used this method to calculate the core structure of edge prism and some BCC elements.

Then, starting with the high-temperature regime of the prismatic slip where strengthening has been observed in experiments, the solute strengthening of edge prismatic dislocations in Mg-Zn was investigated. We employed first-principles methods to calculate the interaction energies between Zn solutes and edge prismatic dislocations. These interaction energy maps were then used within a solute strengthening framework to correlate the atomic-scale interactions with the macroscopic yield strength of the material. Tackling the issues arising from the motion of the dislocation in the presence of the solute which inhibits accurate calculation of the solute/dislocation interaction energies for certain sites, we developed a methodology to fix the dislocation using a pinning solute.

First-principles calculations revealed relatively large interaction energies between Zn solutes and edge prismatic dislocations, with a maximum value of -0.34 eV. However, despite the large interaction energy and the compact core structure of the prismatic edge dislocation, our analysis indicated that the strength of the edge dislocation remains insufficient to explain the experimental strengthening results.

The substantial differences in interaction energy values above and below the slip planes prompted further investigation into the effect of dynamic strain aging through cross-core diffusion on the strength of the edge dislocation. We found that vacancy-mediated diffusion

across the dislocation core becomes active within the temperature range where strengthening is observed. However, the calculated strengthening effect was still significantly lower than experimental observations. Nudged elastic band (NEB) calculations showed that within the core of the dislocation, there are specific pathways along which the diffusion energy barrier is nearly zero.

Subsequently, we studied the effect of solutes on the cross-slip of prism screw dislocations. This was aimed to understand the softening effect of the low temperature regime. Our small scale DFT calculations showed that when Zn is placed at certain sites, it can indeed stabilize the prism dislocation core against dissociation onto the basal plane. The interaction energy map also showed large interaction energy values with maximum of about -0.27 eV.

To gain a deeper understanding of the behavior of screw basal and screw prism dislocations in 3d, we developed an NNP for Mg-Zn system with good accuracy to study prismatic slip phenomena. Using the new NNP first we studied the kink-pair mechanism and the effect of Zn on this mechanism by NEB calculations. The results showed that for certain crystallographic sites, a single Zn atom can substantially influence the energy barrier of kink-pair mechanism by lowering the kink nucleation energy. Also it was shown that Zn at specific sites can strongly pin the basal-basal kink. From these results it was shown that a solute can have a substantial softening effect and at the same time it also can significantly increase the kink migration barrier.

Then we examined the single-kink mechanism for possible effect of solutes on this mechanism. By incorporating the solute interaction energies with prism and basal screws into the single-kink mechanism we used those formulations to calculate the strength at different temperatures. Using our calculated interaction energies, we found that single-kink mechanism does not predict a strong softening effect. Therefore we concluded that the solutes must play a role in a different mechanism than single-kink.

Finally, at the end of the thesis, we proposed another mechanism for solute softening based on our simulations of the interaction of solutes with an expanding loop. In this mechanism, solute pins the dissociated basal segment while not affecting the edge component. By pinning the screw basal a long transition segment is created that can easily transform into prism dislocation. This mechanism predicts significant lowering of the strength at 0K. Increasing temperature have detrimental effect on this mechanism. Therefore again aligning with experimental results which show disappearance of softening by increasing temperature.

8 Outlook

The results of the present thesis demonstrate that the high-temperature strengthening of prismatic slip cannot be attributed to solute strengthening, dynamic strain aging, or solute drag mechanisms acting on the prism edge dislocation. One alternative possibility worth exploring is the possibility of strengthening due to local ordering of solute atoms. However, given the dilute concentration of Zn in the alloy studied in this thesis, this mechanism seems unlikely to play a significant role in the observed high-temperature strengthening.

At high temperatures, strengthening mechanisms can also influence prismatic screw dislocations. Two plausible mechanisms that may explain this behavior are:

1. **Dynamic Strain Aging (DSA) within the Screw Dislocation Core:** The large interaction energy between solute atoms and the screw dislocation core could drive the diffusion of solutes toward high-energy interaction sites within the core. This diffusion can effectively pin the dislocation by reducing its energy and increasing the energy barrier for its glide, leading to strengthening.
2. **Effect of Solute on Basal-Basal Kink Pinning:** Our results indicate that Zn can significantly pin basal-basal kinks. At high temperatures, where thermal fluctuations are strong, it is likely that screw dislocations glide via a *basal-prism-basal cross-slip* mechanism between adjacent basal planes. In such a scenario, the pinning of basal-basal kinks by Zn atoms could become the rate-controlling factor for dislocation motion, thereby contributing to the observed strengthening.

The new mechanism introduced in this thesis for explaining the low-temperature softening, based on the interaction of solutes with an expanding loop, should be formulated to verify the simulation results. However, an accurate analysis requires knowledge of the local stress on each segment of the dislocation.

One approach is to implement an accurate discrete dislocation dynamics (DDD) model to calculate the local self-stress at each stage of the loop expansion. Another method is to

investigate the solute pinning effect on a straight dislocation instead of a loop. However, this investigation must ensure that one segment of the dislocation line remains in a dissociated basal configuration, while the remaining segments exist in either prism or constricted basal configurations. By using this approach, the applied stresses are much closer to the real scenario compared to using a dislocation loop.

Another factor to consider may be the influence of metallurgical extrinsic inhomogeneities in the microstructure and forest dislocations, on the glide of the screw dislocation. These obstacles can perturb the configuration of the dissociated basal dislocation by creating constrictions or prism segments, thereby facilitating prismatic glide. Additionally, they can induce curving of the dislocation line during the glide, leading to local prism segments similar to the transition regions observed in expanding loops.

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Curriculum Vitae

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Education

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Ph.D. in Material science

Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran
Research Focus: Martensitic transformation in Ni-Mn alloys

M.Sc. Selection and Characterization of metallic materials

Sahand University of Technology, Tabriz, Iran
Thesis: Directional solidification of Magnetostrictive Fe-ga alloy.

B.S. in Industrial Metallurgy

University of Tabriz, Tabriz, Iran

Specialization in material engineering.

Professional Experience

Teaching Assistant

École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)

Courses: Solid Mechanics, Mechanical behavior of materials.

Research Intern

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Focused on the development of a MEAM interatomic potential for Ni-Mn system.

Professional Development

Summer Schools

- **Computational Materials Science Summer School**

Texas A&M University, College Station, TX 2022

Participated in a rigorous program focused on advanced computational techniques and tools for materials science research,.

Publications

Journal Articles

- Rahbarniazi, M., & Curtin, W. (2024). Strengthening of edge prism dislocations in Mg-Zn by cross-core diffusion. *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*.
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Conference Presentations

- **European Mechanics of Materials Conference 2024 (EMMC19)**, Madrid, Spain
Presentation title: Solute effect on softening/strengthening the prismatic slip in Mg
Note: This presentation was selected as the best presentation in the symposium: Advanced modelling techniques.
- **International Conference on Strength of Materials 2022 (ICSMA19)**, Metz, France
Presentation title: Solute effects on prismatic slip in Mg alloys.
- **International Conference on Multiscale Materials Modeling (MMMI)**, Prague, Czech Republic
Presentation title: Solute effect on softening/strengthening the prismatic slip in Mg.